

Grant Agreement No.: 680708

Project acronym: HIT2GAP

Project title: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap

Innovation Action

Topic: EeB-07-2015 New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings

Starting date of project: 1st of September 2015

Duration: 48 months

D5.3 – Effects brought by the HIT2GAP solution in all four pilot sites (results Evaluation) and overall evaluation of the HIT2GAP solution

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: BES		
Version 1 – Rev.0	Due Date	M46 - 30 th of June 2019
	Submission Date	11 th of October 2019
	Primary Authors	BES – BEDELL-HARPER Amelina, MOUAWAD Jessica
	Contributors	FISE, GIR, MOS, CYL, R2M, API, CYR, ENE, UDG, NUIG, UOS, EGE
	Reviewers	BRASSIER Pascale (NBK), GARCIA Elena (TEK), MESSERVEY Tom (R2M)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4	
1 Introduction	7	
1.1 Purpose.....	7	
1.2 Contributions of partners.....	7	
1.3 Report structure.....	7	
2 Challenger (France, BES)	9	
2.1 Use cases.....	9	
2.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot.....	11	
2.2.1 Load forecasting (developed by UDG).....	11	
2.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)	14	
2.2.3 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (Machine Learning based)	(developed by FISE).....	18
2.2.4 Behaviour modelling – Semantic approach (developed by EGE).....	21	
2.2.5 Behaviour modelling – Event driven approach (developed by API).....	26	
2.2.6 Energy management (developed by ENE).....	29	
2.2.7 ESP-r – Simulation module (developed by UOS).....	35	
2.2.8 REnSim (Renewable Energy Simulator) (developed by CYR).....	44	
2.2.9 Facility management visualisation module (developed by FISE).....	51	
2.2.10 Occupants’ visualisation module (developed by INO).....	58	
2.3 Gap evaluation.....	60	
2.4 Lessons learnt during the operation.....	60	
3 Wilanów Town Hall (Poland)	62	
3.1 Use cases.....	62	
3.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot.....	63	
3.2.1 Load forecasting (developed by UDG).....	65	
3.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)	73	
3.2.3 Energy management (developed by ENE).....	81	
3.2.4 BIM visualisation module (developed by ZUT).....	94	
3.3 Gap evaluation.....	99	
3.4 Lessons learnt during the operation.....	99	
4 Nanogune (Spain, GIR)	100	
4.1 Use cases.....	100	
4.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot.....	102	
4.2.1 Load Forecasting (developed by UDG).....	102	
4.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)	110	
4.2.3 Behaviour modelling – Semantic approach (developed by EGE).....	113	
4.2.4 Energy management (developed by ENE).....	116	
4.2.5 Gap Reasoner (developed by FISE).....	133	
4.3 Gap evaluation.....	135	
4.4 Lessons learnt during the operation.....	136	
5 National University of Galway (Ireland)	137	
5.1 Use cases.....	137	
5.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot.....	142	
5.2.1 Load Forecasting (developed by UDG).....	142	
5.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)	155	

5.2.3	Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (Machine Learning based) (developed by FISE).....	163
5.2.4	ModSCO – Simulation module (developed by NUIG).....	166
5.2.5	BIM visualisation module (developed by ZUT).....	174
5.2.6	ESP-r – Simulation module (developed by UOS).....	181
5.3	Gap evaluation.....	190
5.4	Lessons learnt during the operation.....	198
6	HIT2GAP Platform.....	200
7	Conclusion.....	202
8	Acronyms and abbreviations.....	211
9	Annexes.....	213
9.1	Annex 1: Identification of the performance improvement capacity of the tool – Key performance indicators.....	213
9.1.1	Energy performance indicators.....	213
9.1.2	Heating and cooling energy performance indicators.....	215
9.1.3	Indoor quality indicators.....	217
9.1.4	Organization and management indicators.....	218
9.1.5	Application performance indicators.....	219

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the effect brought by the HIT2GAP solution in all four pilot sites and includes an overall evaluation of the solution. The aim of the report is to provide an in-depth analysis of the results obtained within the project at two levels: tool integration level and running of the tool in the pilots. The document defines the testing methodology to test the proper functioning of the system and the sturdiness of the HIT2GAP platform. It compiles the lessons learnt during the operation of the whole solution in the pilot sites (benefits gotten from the use of the platform and the modules), an assessment of the pilot managers' feedback, and the identification of the performance improvement capacity of the tool. The document also evaluates how the HIT2GAP solutions reduces the energy gap between the simulated data and the real measured data on each pilot.

The HIT2GAP platform has been implemented and tested on four different pilot sites: Challenger (France), Nanogune (Spain), National University of Galway (Ireland) and Wilanów Town Hall (Poland). Each of these sites had different use cases and different constraints. Modules tested included load forecasting, fault detection and diagnosis, calibrated simulations, occupant behaviour modelling, renewable energy simulation, building information modelling, visualization tools for energy managers, facility managers and occupants.

The following results have been obtained for Challenger site:

- Forecasting of electrical, lighting, ventilation and plug load consumption for South Triangle with average error between 12 and 35%;
- 9 out of 36 relevant alerts using fault detection module (PCA);
- Low supply air temperatures on one air handling unit using fault detection module (ML);
- Conforming indoor conditions using behavior modelling (semantic);
- Some overconsumptions during non-working hours using behavior modelling (event driven);
- Simplified interface for synthesizing building energy data and alerts using energy management module;
- Simulated model to identify comfort discrepancies (when calibrated) using ESP-r module;
- 250 PV panels out of service detected using Rensim module;
- Evaluation of COP performance using FM visualization module;
- Simplified and user-friendly interface for occupants.

The following results have been obtained for Wilanów site:

- Successful connection of the demo building with the BEMServer through the Plat.One and sharing data from the sensors installed at the site;
- Implementation of four selected modules;
 - Forecasting of electricity and heating consumption for the third floor with average error between 7 and 20% which helps to investigate the possible deviation (overconsumption) by comparing the prediction with the real values;
 - Satisfying alerts using fault detection (PCA) module after narrowing down the area of

interest. Correct detection of failure work of the chiller that serves AHU (NW1);

- Simplified interface for aggregating bill data and comparing energy performance from several years using energy management module;
- Creation of the 3D model of Wilanów Town Hall and implementation of the BIM module showing alerts on temperature, CO₂, humidity levels and presenting the historical data from the sensor on the user-friendly 3D model.

The following results have been obtained for Nanogune site:

- Forecasting of general electricity, general gas and chiller consumption with average error between 2 and 10%;
- Alert during abnormal warm season using fault detection (PCA) module;
- Simplified interface for visualizing energy saving using energy management module;
- Comparison of simulated and measured consumption using gap reasoner.

The following results have been obtained for NUIG site:

- Successful creation of a database including 364 variables, for more than 12 months, fully interoperable with the BEMServer platform;
- Real time, stable and reliable connection between amazon cloud server, where the pilot site BMS stores all the measured data, and the BEMServer platform: a complete set of 364 variables was made available on the HIT2GAP platform and the comprehensive and reliable communication flow was set and verified;
- Part of this large amount of measured data was made available as open access data on the scientific platform Zenodo: 2 sets of data were selected as significant for further research investigations, specifically about a complete monitoring layout of one of the AHU and about 2 selected energy meters, involved in the HIT2GAP test;
- AHU malfunctioning captured and faults detected in reliable and precise way: they represent significant faults for the pilot site and in general typical faults that can happen in an AHU and to their sensors and components;
- Achievable saving in electrical and thermal energy for AHUs of 25-65%;
- Real time connection between BIM model and BMS of the building, so real time values from the installed data-points can be visualized in the 3-dimensional BIM environment;
- Measured values outside acceptable comfort and operation ranges can be easily visualized in the BIM model with different colors, for fast and easy detection;
- All the following functions successfully integrated in BIM environment thanks to the ZUTEC tool: 3-dimensional virtual visualization of building and systems components, architectural and MEP parts of the BIM model both involved, real time visualization of the measured data from the BMS, technical information, documents, photos and other information materials directly accessible and integrated, snags list and asset lists for AHUs and other components in order to check needed actions and features of buildings zones, components and systems parts;
- Forecasting of demand of thermal energy for heating and electrical energy for cooling (for chillers) with average error between 0,7 and 16%;
- A module to build in easy way energy models of building zones for simplified dynamic

simulation, thanks to the MODSCO tool;

- Comparison of simulated and actual performance of air handling units using MODSCO module;
- An easy access to a comprehensive and powerful energy dynamic simulation engine for buildings and to access to capabilities of IEQ analysis and report according to international standard, thanks to ESPr module, made available in the BEMServer platform;
- Automatic calibration of energy simulation models according measured data from the BMS and improvements actions assessed thanks to energy dynamic simulation of automatic calibrated models.

The feedback on the modules: maturity, ergonomics and usefulness is summarized in the conclusion table of the deliverable.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this report is to evaluate the impact of the HIT2GAP solutions deployed in the four European pilot sites. The deliverable D5.3 is related with Task 5.3 “Running of the HIT2GAP solution in the pilot sites” and Task 5.4 “Evaluation and impact assessment of the HIT2GAP solution”. As a consequence, for each pilot, it includes a description of the effects brought by HIT2GAP, the testing methodology and the results in terms of energy savings, comfort improvements, time management, energy gap reduction between predicted and measured performances, and others.

The different interfaces of the modules are shown as well as detailed examples of the results obtained during the testing phase and an analysis of the accuracy, usefulness and impact of these results. Where possible, numerous KPIs have been presented and described. Moreover, a description of the refinements implemented in the platform and the modules following the feedbacks received from the pilot sites managers and lessons learnt in terms of operation of the solution are presented in this document. Finally, an analysis of the gap reduction potential for each pilot site is presented.

1.2 Contributions of partners

Bouygues Energies and Services (BES) as the leader of the task 5.3 and responsible of deliverable D5.3 is the main contributor to this document.

The pilot managers (MOS, GIR and R2M/CYL) have also contributed providing their feedback about the modules deployed in their own building.

The modules developers (FISE, API, CYR, ENE, NUIG, UDG, UOS, EGE) have provided the quantitative results in terms of modules outcomes and energy gap reduction.

1.3 Report structure

This deliverable is organized in several chapters and sections listed below:

- Chapter 1 is the initial introduction of the document.
- Chapter 2 is dedicated to the French pilot site, Challenger, managed by BES.
- Chapter 3 is dedicated to the Polish pilot site, the town hall of Wilanów, managed by MOS.
- Chapter 4 is dedicated to the Spanish pilot site called Nanogune managed by GIR.
- Chapter 5 is dedicated to the Irish pilot site, the Alice Perry building, located in the National University of Galway, managed by R2M and CYL.

Each of these 4 chapters are divided in 4 sub-sections.

- Section X.1 resumes the different purposes and expectations expressed by the pilot manager and summarizes the modules implemented on the pilot site.
 - Section X.2 details the scenarios used to evaluate the effect brought by the different HIT2GAP modules on the demonstration site, and a deep analysis of the key performance indicators for each module tested.
 - Section X.3 explains how the HIT2GAP platform allows to evaluate and reduce the energy performance gap for the pilot site.
 - Section X.4 resumes the lessons learnt during the demonstration phase and the solutions found.
- Chapter 6 is dedicated to the refinements made to the platform itself,
 - Chapter 7 is the conclusion of the report and the summary of the module's evaluation.

2 Challenger (France, BES)

Challenger is a recently renovated site consisting of three main buildings: Central building, North Building and South Building with a total surface area of 68000 m². The site has several energy sources: geothermal energy, photovoltaics, solar thermal energy, dry adiabatic and thermal generators. Each building in Challenger has many consuming applications: lighting, ventilation, air conditioning, plug loads included in the regulated perimeter, as well as applications such as lifts that are not included in the regulated perimeter.

Figure 1: Photo of the Challenger building

The energy data, specifically electrical and heat consumption, are collected from the BMS and stored in the database. The BMS is of brand PcVue and the database is of brand SQL.

The BMS collects data from sensors measuring either the overall building consumption or the consumption per application and per zone. For instance, the consumption of lighting, comfort units, ventilation and plug loads can each be measured per zone (half floor level). These data are measured by the sensors every 10 minutes, but they are collected by the BMS every 15 minutes. The total consumption of the buildings and some applications directly measured at the main switchboard (such as lifts consumption) is available every 1 hour.

Moreover, there is a single water loop circulating in the site. The consumption of the loop comprises the consumption of the pumps corresponding to the geothermal sources (for heating and cooling), the dry adiabatic coolers (for cooling) and the secondary distribution pumps.

2.1 Use cases

The following table summarises which modules have been deployed on Challenger building and what were the expectations regarding each module.

Table 1: Objectives of the demonstration and expected impacts for the Challenger building

Module name	App	Partner	Objective of the demonstration / expected impact
Fault Detection and Diagnosis Modules	FDD-PCA	UDG	• Easily detect and locate misbehaviours/faults.
	FDD-ML	FISE	• Easily detect and locate misbehaviours/faults.
Load Forecasting	Load Forecasting	UDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecast power consumption in building or zones of a building. • Anticipate overconsumptions and deviations with

			<p>respect to energy performance contracts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of energy baseline.
User Behaviour Modules	BM-Events	API	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trace wasteful behaviour, evaluate its impact and notify users and facility managers. • Provide information for the Energy Management module. • Allow different building occupants to engage in gaming.
	BM-ML	EGE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimize energy consumption and occupant comfort by generating recommendations for facility managers and occupants including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changing indoor temperatures, - Central control of lighting, - Changing indoor air flow settings, - Changing shading device states, - Changing operation schedules, in particular HVAC
Energy Management/ Energy Performance Application	EM	ENE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving recommendations and prioritization • Tracking of energy waste • Persons & man-months reduction for everyday EnMS staff's activities. • Better Management and effective Decision-making process.
Building Performance Simulation Modules	ESP-r	UOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of reasons for performance gap and recommendations
Renewable Energy Simulator	REnSIM	CYR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of the performance of the PV system • Identification of defaults in the installation and their sources • Prediction of energy production
Visualisation Modules	EM Visualisation	ENE	<p>Graphical user interface for the EM module.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display the appropriate information to the user regarding energy saving actions, wasteful events and follow up of the consumption baseline
	FM Visualisation	FISE	<p>Graphical user interface for the FDD-ML module.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable decision support for the operational management of the building by providing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview as well as detailed information on the energy operation of buildings and building services like heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems, lighting, etc.; • A clear and targeted energy performance information on the basis of outputs from Fault Detection and Diagnostics (FDD) algorithms; • A forecast energy consumption dataset from the building energy simulation models.
	Building Occupants Module	INO	<p>Reach and influence non-technical users in their daily interaction with the building by providing indicators that they can well apprehend.</p>

2.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot

This section details the different scenarios used to evaluate the effect brought by the HIT2GAP solutions on the French demonstration site and a deep analysis of the key performance indicators calculated for each module deployed on the pilot site.

2.2.1 Load forecasting (developed by UDG)

The load forecasting module allows energy managers to forecast the power consumption by usage (lighting, plug load, ventilation etc.) and by building or zone of the building.

The energy manager (EM) needs to follow his energy performance contracts, anticipate and justify potential overconsumptions. By using the forecasting module, the energy manager can visualize the forecasting of energy consumption, identify deviations and overconsumptions. He has an easier and faster tool to evaluate his consumption and whether or not he will be able to respect the targets imposed by the energy performance contracts. Hence, the energy manager can anticipate penalties and act immediately to rectify the problem or justify any overconsumption. This will help him to control the energy budget.

This module is also intended to support performance measure and verification protocols (IPMVP, ISO 50015:2014) by comparing energy consumption after the implementation of corrective actions and energy consumption profile according to the model obtained in the forecasting module.

2.2.1.1 *Testing methodology and implementation*

As the targets imposed by the energy performance contracts are usually defined by usages, different models have been developed for Challenger to forecast:

- The total electricity consumption of the south triangle building
- The ventilation electricity consumption of the south triangle building
- The lighting electricity consumption of the south triangle building
- The VRF units electricity consumption of the south triangle building
- The plug load electricity consumption of the south triangle building
- The water loop electricity consumption

The models were trained with data from 01/01/2018 to the 31/01/2019, and they were tested from the 01/02/2019 to the 20/03/2019.

Data used to create the models included energy consumption data as well as influence factors such as weather data (temperature and humidity), contextual information related to occupation (working and non-working days) and calendar (month, weekday). The data were collected from the HIT2GAP platform, which itself collected data from Challenger BMS.

A requirement for this module is to have clean data. In the presence of data gaps or abnormal measurements, a data treatment module is required before the creation of the forecasting models.

The mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), a measure of prediction accuracy of a forecasting method, was calculated for the testing period. The MAPE was also calculated for working days (WD) and non-working days (NWD).

The results of the forecasting module are shown below.

a) Electrical Consumption of the South Triangle

Test period: 01/02/2019 – 20/03/2019

MAPE = 20% MAPE WD = 11% MAPE NWD = 45%

Figure 2: Results of electrical consumption forecasting

Observation: abnormal temperature measurements at the beginning of March (06-10/03/2019) with temperatures between 40°C and 80°C produces inaccurate forecasting values.

b) Lighting Consumption of the South Triangle

Test period: 01/01/2019 – 20/03/2019

MAPE = 27% MAPE WD = 11% MAPE NWD = 70%

Figure 3: Results of lighting consumption forecasting

c) Ventilation Consumption of the South Triangle

Test period: 01/02/2019 – 20/03/2019

MAPE = 35%

MAPE WD = 26%

MAPE NWD = 53%

Figure 4: Results of ventilation consumption forecasting

d) Plug Load Consumption of the South Triangle

Test period: 01/01/19 - 20/03/19

MAPE = 12%

MAPE WD = 11.8%

MAPE NWD = 12.5%

Figure 5: Results of plug load consumption forecasting

e) Water loop – Cooling consumption

Models with very low accuracy (MAPE > 20 %).

f) VRF Units Consumption (Heating And Air Conditioning) of the South Triangle

No accurate models (MAPE > 20 %).

2.2.1.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

The precision of the models depends on the predicted usage. The model has a good precision when the MAPE < 20%. The models that have a good precision are electrical consumption, plug load and lighting WD. The models that have a bad precision are VRF units, water loop, ventilation and lighting NWD.

This module will help the energy manager to identify deviations and overconsumptions for the usages with a MAPE below 20%. Moreover, deviations from energy performance contracts limits can be anticipated.

In order to increase the accuracy of the models, additional influence factors may be included such as occupancy measurements or solar radiation. Moreover, input data needs to be cleaned to account for abnormal measurements or gaps.

2.2.1.3 Improvements of the module following the feedbacks received

A first test of the module showed that any abnormal data greatly affected the results of the prediction. For this reason, a data treatment module has been used to delete or replace abnormal data.

Another improvement was made by the optimisation of the creation of the models: selection of algorithm and parameters. This facilitates the creation of the models without the need to spend lots of time on the creation and testing of different models.

In addition, careful attention needs to be given for the selection of influence factors. Non relevant or inaccurate influence factors decrease the accuracy of the models.

2.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)

The Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (FDD-PCA) module detects abnormal consumptions of electricity in a building, due to failures or malfunctions deteriorating its energy performance. The abnormal behaviour is detected intelligently using the historical data of the different meters as well as influence variables such as weather and indoor environmental data.

The facility manager (FM) wants to know if the functioning of the building equipment has an abnormal behaviour. The fault detection and diagnosis module generates an alert to inform the FM if the module has detected a problem. The module can be used to detect problems related to cooling, heating, ventilation, lighting or any other existing application within the building. This module enables the FM and his/her team to quickly detect problems and thus, correct them and save energy consumption and money. There should also be fewer complaints of the building occupants since the

defaults are easily located. Since the FM spends less time identifying the source of the problem, the module should allow to diminish the man-months of the staff.

2.2.2.1 Testing methodology

To test this module, the developers created the models with the help of the pilot site managers. Indeed, the models are more precise when they are developed for a specific zone. To do so, the pilot site managers analysed the complaints of the occupants to find the zones of interest in the building. In the case of Challenger, 4 critical zones were identified. The developers then created 5 models for a zone with the sensors that were sent to them in the modelling part of the module. Different models were created with the data of the triangles: lighting, ventilation (winter model), heating and cooling (winter model) and one floor total consumption for the north and south triangles. The execution periodicity of the models is one day meaning that once a day the module analyses automatically the data of the day before.

Figure 6: FDD-PCA monitoring window

The results of these models are presented as two graphs in the monitoring window: the first one is the statistic index T^2 (magnitude fault): it detects when a parameter varies because of another, for example, the heating overconsumes because it is very cold outside. The second graph is the Q (correlation fault): it detects when a parameter varies in an irregular manner, for example, because of a breakdown. When the dot is over the red area it means that it overpassed the threshold and it identifies a deviation of the new observation with respect to the model. After detection, clicking on any of these dots on red area displays the contribution analysis (see figure below).

Faulty vars:

Figure 7: Alerts generated by the FDD-PCA module for a specific day of the demonstration period

This new window allows to analyse the contributions of original variables to the statistics that detected the deviations and the time of occurrence of the misbehaviour.

To investigate the relevance of the alerts, the results of the module have been analysed with the maintenance team on site by comparing the consumption curves, the complaints of the occupants and the alerts of the Building Management System.

The output of the module has been analysed from the 17/02/19 to the 04/03/19.

User scenario:

In the section below are presented examples of the analyses of the relevant alerts from the 17/02/19 to the 04/03/19. Only the alerts with at least 3 consecutive hours of detected faults were considered. Indeed, analysing one alert takes 10 to 15 minutes. As this task is long, the facility manager cannot verify the veracity of all the alerts. However, the visual aid provided by the contribution analysis graph provides a useful tool to identify which faults are most critical and should receive attention first.

a) Example 1 of an alert on air conditioning unit:

The module generated an alert for the facility manager from 13:00 to 16:00 on a specific day for the reversible air conditioning (line 7 in the figure below).

Faulty vars:

Figure 8: Alerts generated by the FDD-PCA module for a specific day of the demonstration period

Further analysis was required in order to identify the reason of the fault. On the consumption curve, the equipment stopped consuming after 13:00 which corresponds to an abnormal behaviour. The FM can now initiate a diagnostic to understand why this equipment stopped. After discussion with the maintenance team, it seems to be a gateway problem.

When looking at the consumption of this equipment a few days before the alert, the facility manager notices that the reversible air conditioning consumes less in the afternoon for one week. He even received a complaint from an occupant during this week explaining that it is too warm in the afternoon since a few days.

Impact:

The alert helps the facility manager identify and locate faulty equipments. The problem had occurred a few days before the alert was actually identified by the module. In fact, calibrating the module to receive just the right alerts: not too much and not little or too late, is the hardest part and needs several trial and errors.

b) Example 2 of an alert on lighting system:

The module generated an alert on the same day, from 1:00 to 3:00 for a lighting sensor (line 3 on figure 8). The facility manager analyses the consumption of this sensor with the help of a visualisation tool to check if the alert is relevant (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Lighting consumption monitored during the 27/02/2019

The lighting consumes too much at 00:00 and 1:00. The alert is only relevant for 1:00. After discussing with the maintenance team, it turns out this consumption is normal and is due to security patrols at night and the alert is less relevant.

2.2.2.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators result

The module helps the facility manager to detect the equipment that have an abnormal consumption curve and at what time it occurred. However, since many alerts need to be calibrated, the FM needs to do further analysis to check if the alerts are relevant or not by checking the consumption curves with the help of another tool. The module helped detect different types of problems; breakdowns of equipment, equipment working when they shouldn't and vice versa, equipment not working when they should, gateway connection problems and others.

The percentage of relevant alerts was evaluated for this module from the 17/02/19 to the 04/03/19:

Number of analyzed alerts: 36
Number of relevant alerts: 9
Percentage of relevant alerts: 25%

The facility managers and technicians spend 45 min – 1 hour per day in the morning checking if the equipment of all the building is faulty. The module will help them reduce the time spent on this task once the module is refined. Indeed, for now there is an average of 3 alerts per day for a zone using this module and each of the alerts takes 10 to 15 minutes to analyze.

As the defaults are detected at an early stage, the module will help improve the thermal comfort conditions of the occupants as well as reduce the number of complaints per week. And this improvement can be considered as very useful for the FM in his day-to-day job.

2.2.2.3 Improvements of the module following the feedbacks received

In order to determine if an alert is relevant or not, the facility manager at first, did not have a tool to check the consumption curves of the involved sensors with the FDD module. The tool alone is not sufficient and the FM/ EM needs an additional tool in order to analyze the results. This is made possible through the BEMServer solution by cross-using several modules to deepen the analysis and support the diagnosis.

The testing of the module allowed us to make the following recommendations in order to improve the usability of the module. The module would gain in usability by showing the two results graphs with different dates on the x-axis and the T2 and Q values on the y-axis to obtain a curve instead of a graph for each day. Secondly, it would be preferable to display the description of the sensor instead of the sensor's number.

When generating a report, we can see the faulty sensors per hour for one day. In order to improve the usability, it would be preferable to have an option to see these information's for a longer period of time (week, month, etc). Indeed, a sensor that is faulty only one or two hours a day may not draw the attention of the facility manager, but if this problem occurs for several days it may indicate that the equipment will soon fail.

The analysis was done on only one zone and for less than a month period. Each alert required 10-15 minutes of analysis, so the interface should be improved in order to be adapted for the facility managers.

2.2.3 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (Machine Learning based) (developed by FISE)

The Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (FDD-ML) module detects failures or malfunctions of equipment leading an abnormal consumption of electricity in the building, deteriorating its energy performance. Its functionalities are very similar to the FDD-PCA module but it uses DBSCAN clustering algorithms and detects defaults on equipment. Both modules can be complementary as the FDD-PCA module detects defaults by zone.

The Facility manager (FM) wants to know if there is a failing equipment in his building. The module is going to generate an alert to inform the FM that the module has detected a problem. The module can detect many problems such as HVAC systems faults which can be user generated (heating

during summer) or equipment generated (maintenance needed). This module enables the FM and his team to quickly detect equipment problems and thus save energy consumption and money. There should also be fewer complaints of the building occupants. Moreover, the team will do less programmed maintenance because the problems will be detected automatically. It should diminish the man-months of the staff.

Figure 10: Screenshot on the current visualization of FDD results in the FM module

2.2.3.1 Testing methodology and implementation

The test of this module consists in checking the detected faults on the equipment and the responsible sensors. To do so, during abnormal operating conditions, we will select a day and will select a sample of data which contains faults related to the building HVAC system according to fault history and we will execute the FDD monitoring mode.

In order to test this module, the pilot site managers sent the equipment and sensors for which they want to detect anomalies. For this reason, 3 models have been developed for the air handling system of the north triangle. The first model detects when the supply air temperature is below 16°C with low outside air temperature. The second model is a DBSCAN based FDD and the third model detects when air supply temperature is above 28°C with high outside air temperature. For configuration and visualisation of FDD results, the display module for facility managers (FM) has been extended with appropriate user interfaces. The results are provided on a special widget.

On the line plot, all the necessary information to identify a faulty operation is available; time, location, duration, fault message etc.

Below is an example of some of the results/ faults that have been identified by the module:

On the visualization module for the facility managers, there are alerts for the 29th, 30th and the 31st of October 2018 (see figure below).

Figure 11: Line plot shown on the FM visualisation module

For three consecutive days there were alerts because the air handling unit was blowing cold air under 10°C when outside it was less than 16°C. This causes occupants thermal discomfort and complaints. With the help of the modules, alerts occur before occupants complain. The facility managers can then set up a corrective action to improve the occupants' comfort. For example, on the 29th of October, the first alert is at 7:00 AM and the first occupant's complaint is at 10:00 AM. The facility manager, with the help of this module could have detected the problem 3 hours before the first occupant's complaint. He could have avoided 4 complaints that day. Moreover, the early detection of this issue also has an impact on energy efficiency which is the other primary objective of the FM while operating the building.

2.2.3.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

At this stage of the project, the DBSCAN method has been applied to one single air handling unit. For this equipment, all the tested alerts from the 01/05/18 to the 31/10/2018 were relevant.

The reduction of the number of complaints during October 2018 was analyzed. On 10 alerts, 6 could have been discovered earlier with the help of the module so there is a reduction of HVAC equipment complaints by 60% that week, assuming that a corrective action is taken immediately. With the help of this module, there could be an improvement of the thermal conditions as the defaults can be detected at an early stage.

2.2.3.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The following feedback and improvements have been identified with the test of the module:

1. The FM module can be fully parameterized by users with administrator rights. Nevertheless, this functionality has not been provided to the site managers yet, because of integration issues in the back end of the module. This leads to a lower usability of the module, which will be considered in future developments.

2. The FDD interface implemented through the FM Display Module needs to be further developed to allow better interpretability. This includes the addition of results from fault identification.
3. The output of the FDD method requires an additional post-processing that accounts for on/off times of the systems, as well as working and off working hours (including holidays).

2.2.4 Behaviour modelling – Semantic approach (developed by EGE)

The Behaviour modelling – Semantic approach (BM) module takes into account building meter readings and the thermal and visual comfort survey the building occupants filled in for each heating and cooling season. It detects if the occupants are in thermal discomfort.

In order to prepare the model, a survey has been sent to the occupants of a selected floor level in Challenger from December 2016 to December 2017. 102 occupants participated to the survey. The survey included questions regarding occupant’s satisfaction, perception and preferences.

In the heating season, the results show that 26% and 27% of the participants assessed the indoor air temperature as “dissatisfactory” and “very dissatisfactory”, respectively (Figure 12). Figure 13 shows that dissatisfaction is caused by the fact that the participants perceived the indoor air temperature as “cold” (33%), “cool” (20%), “slightly cool (16%). Accordingly, 67% of the participants stated that they wanted warmer indoor temperature and only 24% of them stated that they do not need a change in the indoor temperature (Figure 14). The same evaluation was done for the cooling season.

Figure 12: Distribution of indoor temperature satisfaction votes in the heating season

Figure 13: Distribution of thermal sensation votes in the heating season

Figure 14: Distribution of thermal preference votes in the heating season

Once the model has been created, the module sends an alert to the FM to inform him if the module has detected a discomfort and generates some recommendations in order to reduce energy consumption and improve the occupants' comfort. All prediction models are trained using data between January 2018 and October 2018.

The events generated by the module are classified as follows:

Event category - Energy Consumption

The lighting model detects abnormal energy consumption for the lighting.

The prediction model of lighting energy consumption is developed to predict the next 2 hours consumption via linear regression analysis. Occupancy and outdoor illuminance are used as the input parameters for the model. Figure 15 shows the screenshot of the actual and predicted lighting energy consumption plot for one zone.

Figure 15: Screenshot of the actual and predicted lighting energy consumption plot for one zone

Event category – Measures

The DRV External Unit Energy model detects abnormal measured values for the DRV. DRV consumption refers to the total energy consumption consumed by DRV external for heating and cooling. The prediction model of DRV consumption is developed to predict the next 1 hour consumption via quadratic regression analysis. The input parameters of the model are indoor temperature, indoor humidity, indoor new air flow, occupancy, carbon dioxide, outdoor temperature, outdoor humidity and ray-glob. Gradient boosting method is used to train the model and % 90 prediction intervals are used to detect excessive energy consumption. Figures 16 and 17 show the prediction and upper prediction of the consumption of one DRV unit for the first and second quarter of 2018, respectively. Moreover, Figure 18 shows the screenshot of the actual and predicted DRV consumption.

Figure 16: Example prediction interval of DRV model for the first quarter of 2018

Figure 17: Example prediction interval of DRV model for the second quarter of 2018

Figure 18: Screenshot of the actual and predicted DRV consumption plot for the second floor, Zone 21

Event category - Indoor Air Quality

The model detects when the CO₂ level is too high, above 1000 ppm.

2.2.4.1 Testing methodology

As the module is based on indoor & outdoor environmental parameters and works real-time, and as a problem has happened on data collection for Challenger for a couple of months during the testing phase, BES has not been able to receive any messages or alerts from the module and test real-time the impact of the module. The alerts are supposed to be sent to BEMServer as events.

However, 3 reports have been prepared by EGE in JSON format which includes historical events generated by the module from January 2018 to the 10th of May 2019.

The first report contains the alerts of “Unexpected lighting energy consumption”.

The second one contains the alerts of “CO₂ values are too high”.

The third report contains the alerts of “Abnormal measures values”.

For each alert is detailed what model is used and its description, the location, start and end time of the detected problem, the sensor id, and the meter value reading.

Other alerts can be generated regarding indoor comfort conditions:

- Real measurement temperature
 - ISO7730
 - Zone average should be
 - $20 \leq T \leq 24$ (Heating Mode - Winter)
 - $23 \leq T \leq 26$ (Cooling Mode - Summer)
 - Heating/Cooling energy consumption may give an idea about mode
 - Off hours should be detected.
 - Occupancy in last hour may give an idea about off hours.
 - Stable energy consumption may give an idea about off hours.
 - Category: “Description”
 - `comfort_temp_high`: “Temperature too high. Occupant preferred temperature should be 23,5.”
 - `comfort_temp_low`: “Temperature too low. Occupant preferred temperature should be 23,5.”
- Real measurement hygrometry (Relative humidity)
 - Zone average should be
 - $\%30 \leq RH \leq \%70$
 - Category: “Description”
 - `comfort_rh_high`: “relative humidity too high”
 - `comfort_rh_low`: “relative humidity too low”
- Real measurement CO₂ (Indoor air quality)
 - Each sensor should be
 - $CO_2 \leq 1000$
 - Category: “Description”
 - `iaq_co2_high`: “CO₂ too high”
- New air flow (Air velocity)
 - Each sensor should be
 - $0.10 \leq AV \leq 0.16$ m/s (Heating Mode)
 - $0.10 \leq AV \leq 0.19$ m/s (Cooling Mode)
 - Category: “Description”
 - `iaq`: “Bad indoor air quality”

2.2.4.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

Since the alerts in json files are not user friendly, the results have not been tested (see figure below).

Figure 19: json results for alerts on comfort units' energy consumption

Moreover, no alerts were generated regarding indoor environment data. So one might assume that indoor environment was comfortable.

2.2.4.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The meter values readings in the reports have been changed from incremented values into real consumption values at the request of the pilot site managers.

Moreover, the module could be improved by including real time alerts regarding potential discomfortable situations for the occupants, by taking into consideration occupants' preferences, indoor environmental data and weather data.

2.2.5 Behaviour modelling – Event driven approach (developed by API)

The Behaviour modelling – Event driven approach (BME) module takes into account building meter readings and traces wasteful behaviour, evaluates its impact and notifies users and facility managers.

The module evaluates the impact of the events and generate two different notifications: a technical message for the managers (FM & EM) explaining the problem and a more friendly-user one for the building zone users to raise their awareness and make them actors in the improvement of energy efficiency.

For challenger different types of events / notifications are available for the south triangle:

- a) Lighting waste events for off hours (between 00.00 and 05.00)
- b) Plug load waste events for off hours (at night)

c) Weather compensated set-point events

2.2.5.1 *Testing methodology*

Below is an example of alerts received by the users on the Behaviour Module (BM) event interface.

Timecheck	Sensor	Value
06/02/2019 12:00	CONSUMPTION->3RD FLOOR SOUTH TRIANGLE->1st zone:Lighting->Off hours operation->Energy Waste [Wh]	6295
07/02/2019 12:00	CONSUMPTION->GROUND FLOOR SOUTH TRIANGLE->1st zone:HVAC->Off hours operation->Energy Waste [Wh]	28100
07/02/2019 12:00	CONSUMPTION->GROUND FLOOR SOUTH TRIANGLE->2nd zone:HVAC->Off hours operation->Energy Waste [Wh]	76800
07/02/2019 12:00	CONSUMPTION->1ST FLOOR SOUTH TRIANGLE->1st zone:HVAC->Off hours operation->Energy Waste [Wh]	25898

Figure 20: Example of alerts on the BM-event interface (before calibration of the module)

Lighting energy waste events: The off-hours lighting event data in the second semester of 2018 were analyzed, in all 8 zones (Ground/ 1st/ 2nd/ 3rd; 1st and 2nd zone) of the south triangle. It appears that there is some significant consumption between 23.00-00.00. This is shown below in Ground floor/ 1st zone case. Thus, the analysis was carried out for only five hours, from 00.00 – 05.00, to avoid the morning 'cleaner' impact.

The total waste off this event is shown collectively below. To interpret this correctly, one has

- to offset what is considered normal
- to take account some data issues; thus, the calculation period is not always 6 months... and in one case the data was poor.

Table 2: Total lighting energy waste detected by the BM-Event driven module for a six months period (after calibration of the module)

Zone	Event Waste (kWh)
G/1	136
G/2	750
1/1	Not calculated / poor data
1/2	274
2/1	208
2/2	978
3/1	192
3/2	346

Figure 21: Example of lighting event power for one zone for 00.00- 05.00 off hours only

Figure 22: Example of lighting event power for one zone for 00.00- 05.00 off hours only (in Wh)

Plug load energy waste events:

The off-hours plug load event data in the second semester of 2018 were analyzed, in all 8 zones (Ground/ 1st/ 2nd/ 3rd, 1st and 2nd zone) of the south triangle. The baseline consumption was identified and off hours events were calculated with regard to these baselines.

ZONE	Baseline for the event notification	Estimated Impact (% to baseline- normal)
G/1	800 W	5
G/2	800 W	10- 12
1/1	1200 W	12- 15
1/2	800 W	2- 3
2/1	750 W	2- 3
2/1	600 W	7- 8
3/1	600 W	4-5
3/2	800 W	2-3

Figure 23: Total plug load energy waste detected by the BM-Event driven module for a six months period (after calibration of the module)

2.2.5.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

This module helps building managers in identifying energy waste in their building. This could be related to increased consumption of different applications (lighting, ventilation, plug loads, air conditioning) during non-working hours. It could also be unnecessary increased consumption (of heating or cooling applications) during working hours. Using this module, the facility manager can modify equipment set points and identify waste energy behaviours.

The module was only used by the pilot site manager during the demonstration on Challenger building because on this site, everything is automated and hence the occupants do not have any control over HVAC units. On other types of building, the module can be also used to inform the occupants about wasteful events and motivate them to pay closer attention to their actions and their impact on energy consumption.

2.2.5.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

The pilot site manager calibrated the thresholds of the alerts for each usage in order to receive relevant alerts taking into consideration building normal and abnormal functioning.

2.2.6 *Energy management (developed by ENE)*

The Energy Management (EM) module is for organizations that want to keep or acquire the ISO-50001 certification or that want to manage their energy consumption optimally. The module assists the EM and his team in analyzing their total energy consumption as well as their energy action plans. An initial interface allows the user to consult the flow and loss of energy. Moreover, improvement opportunities are collected using other HIT2GAP modules (behaviour modules, fault detection and diagnosis) and shown to the energy managers in a dedicated interface. The improvement opportunities are ranked according to the importance and the impact of the task.

The tool also allows the energy manager to compare and benchmark his energy consumption according to defined baselines, to follow his energy budget and to manage his reports. He is able to stock documents such as monthly energy reports or action status on the dashboard.

Figure 24: Dashboard of the EM module

2.2.6.1 Testing methodology

The following functionalities have been evaluated and tested during the demonstration phase on Challenger building:

- Evaluating energy use (past and present)
- Visualizing energy performance indicators
- Capturing and prioritizing improvement opportunities: user input or input from other HIT2GAP modules
- Assignment of actions to specific users
- Managing reports

The EM module's functions

Matching the ISO 50001 requirements, as depicted below, the performances of the EM visualization module cover two main functions.

- Energy Planning & Monitoring;
- ISO 50001 Management System.

Energy Planning & Monitoring

Energy Performance: Energy Review

The Energy Review function in the HIT2GAP EM visualization module presents the data in the form of a Sankey diagram, linking the energy sources to the energy uses. The energy sources are typically

identified from energy utility bills and/or energy audit reports. The energy uses are typically identified from energy audits and sub-meters.

Energy Performance: EnPI

Energy Performance Indicators (EnPIs) and their corresponding energy baselines are metrics that are defined by the organization to measure energy performance. Types and examples of EnPIs include the following:

- energy consumption (in total or broken down by energy use) (e.g. kWh, GJ);
- simple ratio such as energy consumption per unit of output (e.g. kWh per tonne, kWh per man hour worked)
- statistical model (e.g. linear and nonlinear regression);
- engineering based model (e.g. simulation).

Energy Performance & management charts

The Charts function in the Energy Performance and management area includes dashboards showing personalized default energy performance charts and action management charts for the location selected.

Figure 25: Challenger (France): Action Management Charts

Action Management: IOs & Plans

The identification of improvement opportunities (IOs) is an output from the energy review. There are also Improvement Opportunities triggered from other Modules delivered through the HIT2GAP

platform. Having identified improvement opportunities, these IOs are prioritized based on criteria defined by the organisation (e.g. cost savings, capital cost, payback, complexity, impact on health & safety). The energy manager (and energy team) can review this list and decide what IOs should be included in the actions plans. The organization also establishes, implements and maintains action plans for achieving its objectives and targets (ISO 50001).

With the HIT2GAP EM visualization module, the IOs function displays the list of IOs including their category and their prioritization ranking if assessment has been completed. The Plans function shows what actions have been assigned to various people and the target dates for completing these actions. The user can also see easily what actions are overdue.

Figure 26: Challenger (France): Improvement Opportunities

1. ISO 50001 Management System

This section describes the ISO 50001 Management System or the management aspects of the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module.

The main function implemented is the “Planning” function, which includes six sub-functions: Documents, Audit, Management, Non-Conformities, Charts and Tasks.

ISO 50001 Management System: Doc

Within an ISO 50001 EnMS you are required to establish, implement and maintain information, in paper, electronic or any other medium, to describe the core elements of the EnMS and their interaction and that documents required by the standard are adequately controlled.

Within the HIT2GAP EM module, full document management functionality is available. The “Docs” function in the HIT2GAP EM Visualisation module allows the use to access and view documents related to the EnMS.

ISO 50001 Management System: Audit

An internal audit of an EnMS is an objective, systematic review of all or part of an organization’s EnMS. The purpose of internal audits is to check that everyone is doing what is expected from them in relation to the requirements of your EnMS and specifically to:

- determine if the requirements are being met (if conformance to ISO 50001 is required);
- identify and drive improvements in energy performance and the EnMS.

ISO 50001 Management System: Meetings

The Meetings (“Mtg”) functions within the HIT2GAP Energy Management module, allows users to schedule and plan regular energy team and management review meetings. It allows actions to be created and managed from the outcomes of the meeting.

Planning: NCs

Within the organizations of an EnMS, nonconformities (*NCs) should be corrected to ensure the effectiveness of the EnMS. NCs are usually highlighted as a result of an internal audit but can also be highlighted during routine operations.

Within the energy management module, NCs can be created and managed effectively allowing the energy manager to assign NCs to appropriate staff to identify the cause of the problem and to ensure that corrective and preventive actions are taken to prevent it happening again.

Planning: Charts

The Charts function in the ISO 50001 Management System area includes a dashboard showing four default action management charts for the location selected. Other available charts can be personalized.

Figure 27: Challenger (France): Management System: Charts

Energy Performance Indicators (EnPI's)

The following list shows examples of EnPI's defined for the Challenger Site.

Figure 28: Challenger (France): 2018 EnPI's comparing actual consumption to baseline reference

2.2.6.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

The added value of this module is that it allows to capture and to prioritize improvement opportunities and actions coming from other HIT2GAP modules. This is a first step towards action management that allows the energy manager to have a series of recommendations from tools such as HIT2GAP and a list of improvement opportunities that he can evaluate. The EM visualisation module synthesises the alerts coming from different modules. It also allows the user to define, personalize and visualize the KPIs so that he can follow and evaluate the energy use of his site. The module allows to directly track energy waste and energy deviation with respect to baseline.

2.2.6.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The EM visualization module is a tool that can be used by energy managers to input improvement opportunities and rank them based on defined criteria. During the testing phase, the possibility of automating part of these improvement opportunities was added. Energy actions are directly generated from alerts coming from other modules such as occupant behaviour and fault detection.

2.2.7 ESP-r – Simulation module (developed by UOS)

The ESP-r module provides the means to identify locations within the building where indoor environmental quality may fall below levels prescribed in international standards. The identification of such point and the corresponding level of discomfort supports decision making for facility managers.

The FM can use the module to simulate the thermal distribution, glare and CO₂ concentration in the building and thus identify locations where the indoor environmental quality may fall below levels prescribed in international standards or cause occupants' discomfort. He then knows where a corrective action needs to be implemented. Once the corrective action is implemented, the indoor quality and thermal comfort should improve and the number of complaints of the occupants per week should drop.

For the Challenger building, a high-resolution model is available for one zone of the south triangle.

As part of the simulation module, BuildAX sensors have been implemented in Challenger in one zone of the second floor of the South Triangle in order to collect additional information about indoor environmental conditions and feed the module.

Figure 29: Implementation of the BuildAX sensors in Challenger

A total of 17 sensors have been implemented to measure temperature, humidity and luminosity level at a 10 minutes frequency. The measurements of these sensors are compared to the results of the simulation models corresponding to visual, thermal and air quality comfort in order to assess the performance gap.

2.2.7.1 Testing methodology

This section details the methodology of applying this module: testing scenarios, user scenario, requirements.

Figure 30: Zones naming used in the results

Use scenario:

The scenario concerns a Facility manager (FM) who wants to know whether the building is compliant with all the international comfort standards. In the case where comfort conditions are not met, the facility manager should be able to analyze possible reasons for discrepancies. In order to adapt the outcomes of the models to the needs of the EM and FM, detailed reports for thermal comfort and air quality assessment are generated by the module. Graphs are only produced for locations that violate the standard. The visual comfort reports include rendered images with annotations when the comfort criteria in the standard is violated.

a- Air quality detailed reports:

Examples of the analysis outcomes of an air quality simulation are shown in Figure 31 and Figure 32.

The report shows rank-ordered assessment results for locations that do not comply with standards either in tables or in time series graphs.

Area	Location	Frequency of CO ₂ concentration violating criteria (%)	Time of worst criteria violation (MM/DD HH:MM)
mgr_Z22_ESEx	001	62.3	4/09 18:00
off_Zxx_ESEx	00A	44.4	4/04 13:00
	00B	44.4	4/04 13:00
op2_Z22_ESE1	014	22.2	4/02 16:00
	015	22.2	4/02 16:00
	016	22.2	4/02 16:00
	017	22.2	4/02 16:00
	018	22.2	4/02 16:00
	019	22.2	4/02 16:00
	021	22.2	4/02 16:00
	022	22.2	4/02 16:00
	020	22.2	4/02 16:00
op1_Z22_ESE1	002	20.4	4/10 12:00
	003	20.4	4/10 12:00
	004	20.4	4/10 12:00
	009	20.4	4/10 12:00
	006	20.4	4/10 12:00
	010	20.4	4/10 12:00

Figure 31: Example of rank-ordered assessment results for locations that do not comply with the standard

Figure 32: Time series graph showing examples of comfort parameter values at locations that do not comply with standards (values are not representative)

The module was not calibrated with real CO₂ measurements and hence the values shown are only indicative and do not represent real CO₂ values.

b- Thermal comfort detailed reports:

The analysis outcomes of a thermal comfort simulation are shown in the following figures. Examples of rank-ordered (by operative temperature) assessment results for locations that do not comply with the standard are shown in Figure 33 and Figure 34. The results show the frequency of violation of the comfort criteria as well as the times of the day when these values where most flagrant.

The different comfort metrics assessed are: operative temperature, floor temperature, wall temperatures, head to foot temperature difference and draught. Figures showing each comfort metric at all locations that do not comply with the standard, with comfort criteria, are shown after this.

Area	Location	Operative temperature	Floor temperature	Radiant asymmetry (ceiling)	Radiant asymmetry (wall)	Draught	Vertical air temperature difference	
Frequency of violation of the criteria associated with the metrics above (%)								
mgr_Z22_ESEx	001	71.4	21.4	0.0	28.6	0.0	38.5	
op2_Z22_ESE1	014	57.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
	019	57.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0	
	020	57.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	
	010	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	0.0	
op2_Z22_ESE1	015	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	
	016	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
	017	42.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0	
	018	42.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	
	021	42.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
	022	42.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0	
	op1_Z22_ESE1	003	35.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0
		009	35.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0
002		21.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.2	0.0	
004		21.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	7.7	
006		21.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	
Time of worst violation of the criteria associated with the metrics above (MM-DD HH:MM)								
mgr_Z22_ESEx	001	10-01 14:30	10-01 07:30	n/a	10-01 13:30	n/a	10-01 19:30	
op2_Z22_ESE1	014	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	
	019	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 15:30	n/a	
	020	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 14:30	n/a	

continued on next page

Figure 33: Rank-ordered (by operative temperature) assessment results for locations that do not comply with the standard

continued from previous page

Area	Location	Operative temperature	Floor temperature	Radiant asymmetry (ceiling)	Radiant asymmetry (wall)	Draught	Vertical air temperature difference
Time of worst violation of the criteria associated with the metrics above (MM-DD HH:MM)							
op1_Z22_ESE1	010	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 13:30	n/a
op2_Z22_ESE1	015	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 13:30	n/a
	016	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	017	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 15:30	n/a
	018	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 13:30	n/a
	021	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	022	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 15:30
op1_Z22_ESE1	003	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 15:30	n/a
	009	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 15:30	n/a
	002	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 13:30	n/a
	004	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 15:30	10-01 19:30
	006	10-01 15:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	10-01 13:30	n/a

Figure 34: Rank-ordered (by operative temperature) assessment results for locations that do not comply with the standard

Figure 35: Comfort metric at all locations that do not comply with the standard, versus comfort criteria

Operative temperature is a simplified measure of human thermal comfort derived from air temperature, mean radiant temperature and air velocity.

The results seem unusual to what would one expects, especially that according to the results the temperature is higher than the temperature felt by the occupants. However, this graph shows the results of one specific day and does not represent the whole testing period.

Figure 36: Percentage of discomfort due to floor temperature in one of the offices

Figure 37: Percentage of discomfort due to wall temperatures in one office

Figure 38: Percentage of discomfort due to head-to-foot air temperature difference

Significant temperature differences between foot and head height can create discomfort. It is recommended that the difference does not exceed 3°C.

Figure 39: Draught rating

The Draft Rating is an experimentally derived equation to assess the percentage of dissatisfaction from the indoor air flow or the unwanted movement of cool air near occupants. The assessment requires the indoor air velocity (mean and standard deviation) and temperature.

c- Visual comfort:

The report provides a table with locations that violate the acceptable Unified Glare Rating (UGR) (>21). UGR is a measure of the luminance from specific sources against the background lighting level from the walls and ceiling. It provides a single rating based on a fixed luminance value. The UGR is evaluated for every location listed on the floorplan at each time-step in the simulation. The figures in the report show potential glare sources at the time of worst criteria violation for locations that do not comply with the standard (unit are candelas/m²). The figures can be used by the facilities manager to know at what time of the day is the glare most problematic, and where the sources of glare are coming from. This would then allow them to, for example, lower the blinds at those times of day or to rearrange the office environment/ people to avoid those glare sources.

Figure 40: Example of the glare assessment renderings

2.2.7.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

Once the module is calibrated with real time data, it can be used to identify uncomfortable situations for occupants: glare, operative temperature, CO₂, draught... Many of the results mentioned above are not calibrated. Moreover, the results shown correspond to specific selected days where comfort conditions may have not been met.

The module can be used by a facility manager who wants to understand why the occupants of the building are complaining and how he can overcome this issue. He can use the module to run updated simulations with the modifications he thinks are necessary to improve occupants' comfort.

Some of the actions that can be used may be:

1. Increasing HVAC system air flow rate
 - FM checks the conditions in locations using hand held sensors, and confirm the results shown by the simulations.
 - FM identifies the closest air inlet to the desk, and commissions a model with a high flow rate through this vent.
 - FM invokes an assessment using this new model, and sees that the thermal comfort problem was mitigated.
 - FM implements the change in the building, by modifying the fan speed of the system servicing the area.
2. Individual HVAC unit performance manipulation
 - Same as 1, but changing the temperature set-point of only one indoor unit.
3. Rearranging office planning
 - FM sees that a user in the office consistently complains about cool environment, while another user complains about warm environment.
 - FM confirms these complaints with the outputs from the report.
 - FM proposes swapping the desks.
 - FM monitors the complaints of these two users in their new locations.
4. Rearranging office environment
 - Identify sheltering (cabinets, etc.) that preventing the arrival of fresh cold air at draught locations.
 - Propose changes in furniture.
 - FM implements an assessment using the rearranged environment, and sees that the thermal comfort problem was mitigated.
 - FM implements the change in the building.
5. Change blind position
 - Same process as 1, but the position of the blinds is adjusted in the model to reduce the incoming solar irradiance, and then confirmed with BEM Server.

2.2.7.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

Since the model requires running simulations for every time or location where a discomfort needs to be assessed, the module requires some simulation skills.

The results of the module are generated in reports which require time to obtain and analyze. The module can be improved by adding a simplified interface for restituting the results and sending alerts when comfort conditions are not met.

Another possible improvement of the module would be the assessment of the potential sources of discrepancies and discomfort.

2.2.8 REnSim (Renewable Energy Simulator) (developed by CYR)

The Renewable Energy Simulator (REnSim) module supports the user in the management of the energy coming from renewable sources and its effective integration into the installation. The module improves the overall system performance during its operational cycle by allowing early detection of losses and malfunctions.

Challenger PV installed capacity

The PV generated power is collected via 4 main energy meters, named North triangle, COCKPIT, North West and South West. The configuration of the PV plants per PV system/installation as well as the number of PV panels per PV plant and energy meter are shown below:

Table 3: Configuration of the PV plants

PV plants configuration per energy meter	North triangle PV system	COCKPIT PV system	North West PV system	South West PV system
R+ 1 North West			x	
R+4 North West			x	
R+4 North East			x	
R+1 South West				x
R+4 South West				x
R+4 South East				x
ATRIUM			x (1/2)	x (1/2)
North Triangle TN R+1	x			
North Triangle TN R+4	x			
South Triangle TS R+1	x			
South Triangle TS R+4	x			
Solar Farm		x		
COCKPIT		x		
Technical building		x		
R+1 HEA		x		

Figure 41: Distribution of the PV panels

The table below shows the PV production capacity (in Kilowatt, kW) for every PV system. The **COCKPIT PV system** (including PV panels, wires, inverters, power meters, controllers etc), the **North West PV system** and the **South West PV system** have equal PV production capacity (31%). The **North triangle PV system** has the lowest production capacity (6.7%).

Table 4: PV production capacity for each PV system

	North triangle PV system	COCKPIT PV system	North West PV system	South West PV system	SUM
Photovoltaic capacity (kW)	240.0	1078.2	1083.5	1099.3	3501
Percentage (%)	6.85%	30.80%	30.95%	31.40%	100.00%

2.2.8.1 Testing methodology

In terms of energy production, facility and energy managers are mostly concerned with identifying whether the installed system is performing as predicted. If the system is underperforming, then the FM would like to identify the cause. To assess the performance of PV systems, it is necessary to couple information related to the system's operational status (working properly or not), its actual performance efficiency, the weather (amount of solar radiation actually occurring), and any shading/blockage (debris or snow).

For the needs of the study, four different periods were examined between 1st of July 2018, until the end of February 2019. The Weather data and the actual PV output of each plant/meter are derived directly from HIT2GAP platform.

A major factor that REnSim continuously corrects during simulations is the photovoltaic PV derate factor (fpv), with the aim to increase the accuracy level of the simulation and to reduce the energy gap between simulated values and actual data. This is a scaling factor that REnSim applies to the PV array power output to account for reduced output in real-world operating conditions compared to

the conditions under which the PV panel was rated. Particularly, using the REnSim module the course of the production curve is corrected continuously, therefore the accuracy is increased providing more precise forecasting of the production of each PV plant. In general, the derate factor considers various power reduction factors such as:

- Typical reduction factors: dirt/dust/leaves/pollen/bird droppings on the panels.
- Snow cover.
- Shading.
- Faulty or under-performing inverters; wiring losses; disconnection of wires; damages due to strong winds; other hardware issues; etc.

For example, a derate factor of 0.75 represents that testing yielded power measurements at STC (Standard Test Conditions) is 25% less than the manufacturer’s nameplate rating. An indicative Derate Factor of a PV plant that performs very well and is normally affected by the typical reduction factors, ranges from 70% to 80%. A reduced derate factor (40% to 60%) informs the facility manager that he needs to initiate a diagnostic to verify, isolate and eliminate the causes for reduced derate factor.

The following figures show some screenshots of the REnSim module interface and results of the module.

Figure 42: Examples of PV simulation results

January	24,578.05 kW/h	29,464.26 kW/h	16,008.07 kW/h
February	47,433.32 kW/h	39,438.92 kW/h	50,493.74 kW/h
March	78,626.28 kW/h	77,698.90 kW/h	62,178.97 kW/h
April	119,119.06 kW/h	135,876.95 kW/h	85,656.77 kW/h
May	126,057.46 kW/h	136,602.29 kW/h	173,638.78 kW/h
June	119,889.04 kW/h	165,653.50 kW/h	131,404.56 kW/h
July	165,030.75 kW/h	147,106.57 kW/h	173,034.35 kW/h
August	147,909.98 kW/h	105,960.00 kW/h	138,615.61 kW/h
September	95,764.04 kW/h	91,874.72 kW/h	110,150.12 kW/h
October	66,532.80 kW/h	68,823.67 kW/h	70,076.90 kW/h
November	32,193.86 kW/h	34,310.97 kW/h	28,904.38 kW/h
December	28,481.95 kW/h	18,532.41 kW/h	17,145.58 kW/h
Totals	1,051,616.59kW/h	1,051,343.16kW/h	1,057,307.85kW/h

Figure 43: Examples of monthly simulated PV output

2.2.8.1.1 Analysis of results

Below are some results of the application of the Rensim module on Challenger.

- 250 PV panels out of service were identified in the North and South triangle.
- The shading affects several PV plants, since many PV panels are periodically covered by shadow during a day. The reduction of PV power production, because of shading, is significant and is analysed below.
- The PV derate factors and the performance of the PV systems is calculated for the entire examined periods with a daily resolution.
- When there is no actual data available from the Challenger building, the calculated PV derate factors are lower due to this data loss.

Below is an example of the evaluation of the system.

CASE 1: 01/07/2018-31/08/2018

COCKPIT PV SYSTEM

Figure 44: Evaluation of the COCKPIT PV system

NORTH TRIANGLE PV SYSTEM

Figure 45: Evaluation of the NORTH TRIANGLE PV system

NORTH WEST PV SYSTEM

Figure 46: Evaluation of the NORTH WEST PV system

SOUTH WEST PV SYSTEM

Figure 47: Evaluation of the SOUTH WEST PV system

During 01/07/2018-31/08/2018:

- Cockpit meter performs better than the rest PV systems with a derate factor of 55%.
- North Triangle system is under-performing with derate factor 38%. Approximately the one quarter of its PV production capacity is zero due to the inactivation of 250PV panels.
- North West and South West PV systems have lower than expected derate factors (43% and 37% respectively).

The same evaluation was done for other periods and are presented in Table 6.

2.2.8.1.2 Summary of results

During the last 8 months, the simulations carried out using the REnSIM module show that all PV installations are not performing as expected. In comparison to well-performing PV systems, which are normally affected by the typical power reduction factors (dirt/dust/leaves/pollen/bird droppings on the panels), the average derate factors are lower. Two key aspects that affect the performance of PV systems are shading, during the whole year, and snow cover, that is present during the winter.

The **COCKPIT PV system** is performing better than the other 3 PV photovoltaic installations. In particular, the COCKPIT system has the highest derate factor (54%). Due to shading 12% of COCKPIT's PV production capacity is not active. In addition, the snow cover of the PV panels leads to reduced PV production during the winter period.

The **North West PV system and the South West PV system** are operating in a sub-standard (or insufficient) manner. The PV plants of the **North West PV system** have the lower derate factor. The average derate factor of North West PV system is 38%. The power production of North West PV system is significantly lower than COCKPIT PV system which has the same PV production capacity. Due to shading, 28% of North West PV system is not active. The PV plants of **South West PV system** have average derate factor equal to 36%. The power production of North West PV system is significantly lower than COCKPIT PV system which has the same PV production capacity. Due to shading, 18% of South West PV system is not active.

The **North Triangle PV system** as a complete installation is under-performing due to the fact that 250 PV panels are out of service (due to damaged inverters and wiring disconnections), resulting in a reduction of 26% compared to its maximum PV production capacity. In addition, 15% of its production capacity is inactive due to shading.

Table 5: Comparison between PV production capacity and actual production and associated derate factors

	North triangle system	COCKPIT PV system	North West system	South West PV system	SUM
01/07/2018 - 28/02/2019					
Actual Production (kWh)	59736	431796	292233	289571	1073336
Simulated PV Output with calculated convergent fpv and ap values (kWh)	54146	385310	275364	275287	990107
Derate factors	35%	54%	38%	36%	

2.2.8.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

The module allowed to detect that 250 PV panels were out of service in Challenger PV installation. The exact energy loss due to these panels being out of service cannot be directly computed using the module.

The table below shows the potential production of all Challenger PV plants if the Derate Factor is 75%. This table corresponds to a very well performing PV plant that is only affected by the typical power reduction factors, excluding shading and snow cover. This PV power output reduction is significant for all PV systems. Therefore, the corresponding PV system installations should be further examined in order to isolate and fix all hardware issues that affect the PV power production (i.e. faulty or under-performing inverters, wiring losses, disconnection of wires, damages due to strong winds, etc.).

Table 6: Comparison between the actual and the potential PV Production if the Derate factor is 0.75 (values in kWh and €)

	Studied period: 01/07/2018 - 28/02/2019				
	North triangle system	COCKPIT PV system	North West system	South West PV system	SUM
Actual PV Production (kWh)	59736	431796	292233	289571	1073336
Potential PV Production if the Derate factor is 0.75 (kWh)	130660	584393	602462	605294	1922809
Reduction %	54%	26%	51%	52%	44%
Actual PV Production (€)	€3 656	€26 426	€17 885	€17 722	€65 688
Potential PV Production if the Derate factor is 75% (€)	€7 996	€35 765	€36 871	€37 044	€117 676
Losses (€) (due to shading, snow coverage and underperformance)					€51 988*

* For the financial calculations, the France tariff taken into consideration is €0.0612/kWh.

*These losses represent losses due to shading (shading from the building on itself), snow coverage and underperformance of the installation. However, to assess the actual gains to be expected with the system operating at full performance, one needs to compute further simulation to identify the losses due to underperformance only, since shadow and snow coverage are external factors that cannot be influenced.

2.2.8.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

As the predictions lacked accuracy, CYRIC added a second configuration (V2), that takes into consideration the shadow coverage, in order to assess the derate factors of the PV plants without the influence of shadow. Using the V2 configuration, the simulated values remain almost identical to the v1 ones, while the corresponding derate factors are increased.

The estimated average reduction of PV power production capacity (%), due to shading, is presented in the following table.

Table 7: Estimated average reduction of PV power production capacity (%), due to shading

Reduction of PV power production capacity (%)	North triangle PV system	COCKPIT PV system	North West PV system	South West PV system
	15%	12%	28%	18%

Using a web tool that calculates the shadow of an object when is projected against the sun for any month and any hour, the total losses due to shadow coverage amounts to 18.6%.

The table below shows the respective PV Derate factors when the shading effect is both considered and disregarded. It is understandable that the PV Derate factors are comparatively higher, since less PV panels are producing the same energy.

Table 8: Derate factor alteration when considering the shading effect

	Studied period: 01/07/2018 - 28/02/2019			
	North triangle PV system	COCKPIT PV system	North West PV system	South West PV system
PV Derate factor without considering shading effect	29%	50%	30%	32%
PV Derate factor when considering the shading effect	36%	56%	46%	39%

Moreover, the module could be improved by including a simplified way to directly identify losses in the installation, without having to do several iterations to compute the derate factor.

Also, with further instrumentation of the PV panels, the module should allow to quantify losses due to installation problems. The module as it is today, allows to compute a derate factor that includes losses due to snow and shadow coverage in addition to installation problems. The impact of each of these factors alone should be computed.

2.2.9 Facility management visualisation module (developed by FISE)

The FM module enables to monitor all meters and sensors data of both Triangles and provides an overview of the current performance of the different building services. It enables decision support for the operational management of the building by providing:

- An overview as well as detailed information on the energy operation of buildings and building services like heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems, lighting etc.
- A clear and targeted energy performance information on the basis of outputs from Fault Detection and Diagnostics (FDD) algorithms.

2.2.9.1 Testing methodology

Several dashboards, in the figures below, are available for the Challenger site:

- Energy Dashboard: Provides an overview on the energy consumption of the site
- “Investigate Data” Dashboard: Allows the custom selection of data for plots
- Different dashboards for the single DRV units:
 - Overview dashboards showing their mean COV for heating and cooling mode
 - Operation dashboards showing their operation times by means of carpet plots
 - Signature dashboards showing scatter plots of the DRV unit data to highlight the relation of COP and power consumption for heating and cooling mode

Figure 48: Screenshot of the consumption charts for the Challenger site

Figure 49: Overview of the energy performance (COP) of the different reversible heat pumps in the North Triangle

Figure 50: Detailed performance monitoring of a single reversible heat pump

Figure 51: Screenshot of signature plots for a single reversible heat pump (DRV) of the Challenger

Figure 52: Screenshot of the consumption charts for a single zone of the Challenger site

2.2.9.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

Site specific visualizations have been implemented that allow to visualize operation and performance data of the installed reversible heat pumps (DRV).

Following issues listed in Table 9 have been identified:

Table 9: Issues identified with rule-based FDD and through graphic display of the visualisation FM module

System	Identified problem:	Period:	Recommendation:	Figure:
Blinds	Power meter data indicate power consumption of the blinds at night	08.2018-03.2019	Check blind operation and control logic	Figure A
DRVs	Low COP of DRVs in cooling and heating mode	08.2018-03.2019	Check setup of DRVs	Figure B
AHU RC1	Supply air temperature levels are too low or too high and might cause discomfort	01.2018-03.2019	Check temperature sensor position (might be installed before the heating and cooling coils) Check AHU temperature level setpoints Check AHU control logic	Figure C
AHU RC3	Supply air temperature levels are too low or too high and might cause discomfort	01.2018-12.2019	Check temperature sensor position (might be installed before the heating and cooling coils) Check AHU temperature level setpoints Check AHU control logic	Figure D

Figure A: Power meter data of the blinds in one of the zones

DRV Overview

Group	Mean COP (Cooling Mode)	COP Indicator (Cooling Mode)	Mean COP (Heating Mode)	COP Indicator (Heating Mode)	Dashboard
filter for group					
TN_1F.Z18_DRV.01	0.5	●	2.6	●	TN_1F.Z18_DRV.01
TN_1F.Z19_DRV.02	1.7	●	2.9	●	TN_1F.Z19_DRV.02
TN_2F.Z18_DRV.01	1.0	●	⚠	⚠	TN_2F.Z18_DRV.01
TN_2F.Z19_DRV.02	1.1	●	2.8	●	TN_2F.Z19_DRV.02
TN_3F.Z18_DRV.01	1.6	●	2.0	●	TN_3F.Z18_DRV.01
TN_3F.Z19_DRV.02	0.2	●	3.2	●	TN_3F.Z19_DRV.02
TN_GF.Z18_DRV.01	0.5	●	2.1	●	TN_GF.Z18_DRV.01
TN_GF.Z18_DRV.02	9.0	●	11.0	●	TN_GF.Z18_DRV.02
TN_GF.Z18_DRV.03	9.0	●	⚠	⚠	TN_GF.Z18_DRV.03
TN_GF.Z19_DRV.04	9.0	●	11.0	●	TN_GF.Z19_DRV.04
TN_GF.Z19_DRV.05	9.0	●	⚠	⚠	TN_GF.Z19_DRV.05
TN_GF.Z19_DRV.06	0.4	●	2.7	●	TN_GF.Z19_DRV.06

Figure B: Overview table of the COPs of the DRVs in cooling and heating mode

Figure C: Carpet-plot Air Handling Unit– Supply air pressure (below) and supply air temperature (above)

Figure D: Carpet-plot AHU RC03 – Triangle Nord – Supply air pressure (below) and supply air temperature (above)

2.2.9.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The graphs used: carpet plots and cloud of dots should be better shown, with clear information regarding the data and the information that the graph is supposed to show. It is not easy to understand and analyse the graphs at the first glance.

2.2.10 Occupants' visualisation module (developed by INO)

The Building Occupants module is dedicated to non-technical users in buildings like employees and visitors. It provides visualisations of simplified indicators on building energy performance. The purpose of this module is to reach and influence non-technical users in their daily interaction with the building by providing indicators that they can well apprehend. These indicators are indexed on technical indicators. In HIT2GAP, it is aimed to display this module on different screen formats and types (Smartphone, Desktop computers, Big Screens). For now it is displayed on desktop computers.

The different submodules:

- Room temperature: It allows the occupants to be aware of the current and historical indoor temperature.
- Weather conditions: It informs the occupants of the current and forecasted weather conditions in the building area.
- Energy consumption: It informs the occupants on the current and historical energy consumption with the information on how the building is performing regarding the forecasted energy consumption.
- Action suggestions: It provides tips to the occupants for them to be more responsible and to take actions to reduce the energy consumption.

Figure 53: Screenshots of the occupants' visualisation module

2.2.10.1 Testing methodology

In order to test this module, the following functions have been tested:

- Monitoring of current or historical indoor temperature.
- Monitoring of current or forecasted weather conditions outdoor temperature.
- Monitoring of the current and historical energy consumption with information on how the building is performing regarding the forecasted energy consumption.
- Action suggestions to reduce the energy consumption.

2.2.10.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

User satisfaction and relevance of notifications has been evaluated.

The impact of the module on the awareness of the occupants is evaluated below for the different sub-modules.

Temperature information sub-module: This module is an added-value service. The occupants use this sub-module when they are in thermal discomfort to check the room's temperature. In cases where the occupants manage the heating and cooling of the building, this module will help them avoiding over and under heating.

Action suggestions: As the suggested actions are static the occupants are going to read the tips once or twice. The occupants need the suggestions to be more dynamic and have more interactions with them to feel engaged in the actions.

Energy consumption: This module raises the awareness of the occupants. By changing their behaviour, they can evaluate the effect of their actions on the consumptions of lighting, plugs loads,

HVAC etc... Thresholds can be defined and visualised on the same graph. In Challenger case, lighting and HVAC are automatically controlled by the BMS.

2.2.10.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The module would gain more effectiveness if the tips were in relation with the behaviour of the occupants or alerts from the other modules. For example, if the plug load consumption is too high at night, the recommended action should be: turn off your devices at night. It would give more dynamism to the actions suggested and intrigue the occupants. BEMServer makes interoperability between modules possible and coupling BM module and visualisation modules could thus improve the relevance of this visualisation module and increase the occupants' awareness. In Challenger case, the occupants had little impact on HVAC systems since everything is automated by the BMS.

2.3 Gap evaluation

Most of the modules have been tested on small demonstration zones and for short periods of time (less than a year). For this reason, it is not possible to evaluate accurately the gap reduction on Challenger site. Moreover, some developments need to be made in order for the modules to be easily applied for a building that is the size of Challenger (68 000 m²). Also, for highly automated buildings such as Challenger, one should not expect a huge gap reduction due to data models.

However, the reduction of the gap between energy consumption targets and actual consumption can be reduced with some of these factors:

- Intelligent detection of faulty equipment helps to easily detect when a problem occurs. The easier the message received by the facility manager, the faster he can solve the problem and reduce overconsumptions.
- Forecasting of energy consumption allows the user to anticipate deviation with respect to targets and conduct deeper analysis of energy performance.
- Behaviour modelling events allow the detection of waste energy due to off work hours. So equipment that still run during the night can be easily detected and corrective actions can be taken to reduce energy consumption.
- Simulation of photovoltaic production is used to assess actual energy production as well as losses due to the installation.
- Visualization tools send the right information to the right user so that corrective actions can be easily understood and applied.

2.4 Lessons learnt during the operation

The first lesson learnt is that the quality of data is essential for the accuracy of the models developed. Fault detection and diagnosis, load forecasting, visualisation modules, behaviour modelling... all rely on continuous data availability as well as good quality of data. Missing or abnormal data largely affects the result of these modules.

The second lesson learnt is that even though data analysis and models developed should facilitate fault detection, action management and building control, a lot of work still needs to be done (by data scientists and module developers) to create these models and to tune them to reach good accuracy.

Third, with data modelling, one should not expect (yet) a model that works for all building equipment and zones. Instead, several models need to be developed for different applications and/ or zones.

Fourth, the user interface and the simplicity of understanding a tool is essential. It is not enough to develop a great model, if the user interface is not clear, simple and appealing to the user.

Finally, understanding the use cases and outcomes expected from such models is necessary to be able to select and evaluate such modules.

3 Wilanów Town Hall (Poland)

Wilanów City Town Hall is a new building constructed in 2014 year. The building is divided in two buildings, 3 floors, grand floor, underground garage. Energy sources are district heating network and electricity. City of Warsaw is the building owner of the demonstration site and manages itself its own building and will be the end-user of the tool developed within HIT2GAP.

Figure 54: Wilanow Town Hall building.

3.1 Use cases

The primary requirements and expectations regarding HIT2GAP at Polish pilot site are presented below:

- Forecast power consumption in building or zones of a building in order to get better contracts terms with energy and heat water suppliers;
- Improve prediction for reactive actions, energy baseline;
- Trace wasteful behaviour, evaluate its impact and notify users and facility managers;
- Build a multi-year energy action plan;
- Identify reasons for performance gap and provide recommendations;
- Compare energy consumption in the range of several years;
- Visualise the amount of energy that can be saved.

Table 10: List of modules deployed and tested in the Polish pilot site and main expectations

Module Name	App	Partner	Objective of the demonstration/ expected impact
Fault Detection and Diagnosis Module	FDD-PCA	UDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect misbehaviours/faults.
Load Forecasting	Load Forecasting	UDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecast power consumption in building or zones of a building. • Improve prediction for reactive actions, energy baseline. • Demonstrate the integration of forecasting tools in a platform such as HIT2GAP.
Energy Management/ Energy Performance Application	EM	ENE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a multi-year energy action plan • Identify improvement opportunities possible for each site • Demonstrate action management coupling with the ISO 50001 and potential achievable energy savings. • Targeted improvement: HVAC, lighting, equipment, etc.
Visualisation Modules	EM Visualisation	ENE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphical user interface for the EM module. • The EM visualisation module displays the appropriate information to the user on the “current” status of activities generated and managed generated by the EM module.
	BIM Visualisation	ZUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D visualization of real-time building performance indicators.

3.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot

Adapting the building to the HIT2GAP project consisted in increasing the quantity of measurement points to improve the functionality of the BMS system. The adaptation of the building required installation of heat, cold and electricity meters. Modernizations were carried out at the level of the underground garage, 3rd floor and the building’s roof. Data read by the BMS from all the selected sensors deployed in the Wilanów town hall is collected by a script and saved in a csv file every day, in a file format compatible with Plat.One. The csv files are stored on a FTP from where data is retrieve by Plat.One.

The demonstration area is located on the third floor of the Wilanów Town Hall. Only third floor of the Wilanów Town Hall has been chosen as the demonstration area, because only there the state/condition of the BMS allowed to do it (during the project, it turned out that the building did not have a real/ full BMS consistent with the executive documentation). However, the modernizations despite 3rd floor were carried out at the level of the underground garage and the roof.

Figure 55: Wilanow Town Hall building – demonstration area – third floor.

3.2.1 Load forecasting (developed by UDG)

Motivation of using the forecasting module is to model energy demand of a specific area of the building to assist daily operation and management tasks. In particular the interests of having a daily forecasting for this area of the building are the following:

- To inform energy managers in advance (the day before) about energy demand episodes that could require a specific reaction.
- To evaluate the impact of possible energy conservation measures (ECM) or actions in the area. Thus, baseline is built on historical data gathered previous to these ECM and the model is used to evaluate savings after the implementation of ECM according to Measurement & Verification projects (International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol, IPMVP).

The module operates in two steps:

- creation of the model (modelling);
- exploitation of the model (monitoring).

Modelling:

In order to create the model, data need to be retrieved from the platform. User can select variables (sensors) starting from the existing list of nodes, and define basic operations, period of time and resampling frequency. Data are stored in a csv file.

Process Data

Process Variables Selection

Nodes | Model

Pilot: Wilanow

electricity | 8 | to Fine-grained

Measure_ID	Building	Floor	Zone	Node_description	UnitOfMeasure	Type
BMS31_LEN_RB3_FC_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	A	3	Building A	Electricity Meter - BMS3 1 FanCoils - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS31_LEN_RB3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	A	3	Building A	Electricity Meter - BMS3 1 Sockets - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS31_LEN_RB3_OSW_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	A	3	Building A	Electricity Meter - BMS3 1 Lighting - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS31_LEN_RK3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	A	3	Building A	Electricity Meter - BMS3 1 RK3 Computer sockets - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NAWILZACZ_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	A	n/a	Building A	Electricity Meter - BMS4 1 NW1 Humidifier - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NW1_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	A	n/a	Building A	Electricity Meter - BMS4 1 NW1 - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS03_LEN_AGR_FC_rEnergiaCzynna	A	n/a	Building A	Electricity Meter - FanCoil Chiller - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption
BMS03_LEN_AGR_NW1_rEnergiaCzynna	A	n/a	Building A	Electricity Meter - NW1 Chiller - Energy	kWh	Electricity consumption

Fine-grained Selection

ATTRIBUTES

- BMS31_LEN_RB3_FC_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana
- BMS31_LEN_RB3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana
- BMS31_LEN_RB3_OSW_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana
- BMS31_LEN_RK3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana
- BMS41_LEN_RB4_NAWILZACZ_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana
- BMS41_LEN_RB4_NW1_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana
- BMS03_LEN_AGR_FC_rEnergiaCzynna
- BMS03_LEN_AGR_NW1_rEnergiaCzynna
- BMS41_StacjaPogodowa_rTemperatura

max

mean

min

max

OPERATION

sum

mean

min

max

Prefix: WIL_

start_time: 2018-02-01T00:00Z

end_time: 2018-09-30T00:00Z

Freq: day

Last samples:

from now

yesterday

Mark holidays

Show JSON

Get CSV

CSV filename: WIL_test01

Figure 56: Getting data from the "Nodes" tab.

User can build forecasting models: select the csv file that contains historical data (obtained in the previous step) and fix the settings of the model: attributes selection, forecasted variable, forecasting method and its parameters – advanced settings, horizon, window (in autoregressive models, how many previous consumptions are used for modelling, removing missing values in case of not autoregressive models).

Figure 57: User interface for forecasting modelling.

Forecasting:

Two execution modes have been implemented:

- On demand: user can create a new csv and perform the forecasting for these data. The content of the csv file (variables, basic operations, resampling frequency) must be the same as the one in the csv file used for building the model.
- Periodic execution: forecasting is performed periodically. In case of daily energy forecasting, each day are calculated the forecasted consumptions for the next 3 days.

3.2.1.1 Testing methodology

In order to test the module at Polish Pilot Site, two consumptions of interest have been chosen: electricity consumption and heating consumption of the third floor. The motivation for choosing these consumptions are the following: third floor is the chosen area for H2G implementation and results can be evaluated before the end of the project.

Electricity consumption

The building does not have a dedicated meter for the area of interest. So, electric consumption of the third floor are calculated as addition of 8 partial consumptions of meters in the third floor. In particular, the loads that are measured refer to AHU/HVAC (Fan Coils, Humidifier, Chillers), lighting and loads (computers and appliances) as listed in the following table:

Table 11: List of electrical loads considered in the analysis

Node	Description
BMS31_LEN_RB3_FC_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 FanCoils – Energy
BMS31_LEN_RB3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 Sockets - Energy
BMS31_LEN_RB3_OSW_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 Lighting - Energy
BMS31_LEN_RK3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 RK3 Computer sockets - Energy
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NAWILZACZ_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS4.1 NW1 Humidifier - Energy
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NW1_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS4.1 NW1 - Energy
BMS03_LEN_AGR_FC_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - FanCoil Chiller - Energy
BMS03_LEN_AGR_NW1_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - NW1 Chiller - Energy

These variables are available in the HIT2GAP platform with a sampling frequency of 15 minutes and are added into a single one representative of the 3rd floor electricity consumption. Moreover, these variables are “energy index” type, that is, they are increasing values. Therefore, they need to be pre-processed in order to calculate the energy consumption in a period of time.

Independent variables

Since main consumption in the floor is related to air handling/cooling, lighting and loads (computers and appliances), it is necessary to incorporate in the model some variable that indirectly report information about these consumptions. In particular, the following are the available variables that can be considered for modelling:

- Wilanów Town Hall weather station: Outside temperature (sampling frequency = 15 min).
- External weather service: Outside temperature. For this variable, the weather service provides forecasted values with a 3-hour frequency.
- Holidays: attribute that identifies the day as a working/non-working day.
- Day of the week.
- Month.

The demo proposed for testing the forecasting module in the Wilanów Town Hall aimed to forecast the electricity consumption of the third floor once a day. Since no specific ECM are reported during the period when data is available, the demo has focused on testing the functionality of the module of providing daily forecasting in a continuous mode (every day the module is executed to forecast the day after) and make it available for decisions. Due to seasonal variations of demand, the model will be representative of a specific time period and the validity will be limited to a period of time with the same season and similar weather conditions.

Modelling: Scenario and data

A forecasting model has been created with the following historical data:

Table 12: Historical data considered in the analysis

Variable	Description
BMS31_LEN_RB3_FC_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 FanCoils – Energy
BMS31_LEN_RB3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 Sockets - Energy
BMS31_LEN_RB3_OSW_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 Lighting - Energy
BMS31_LEN_RK3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 RK3 Computer sockets - Energy
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NAWILZACZ_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS4.1 NW1 Humidifier - Energy
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NW1_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS4.1 NW1 - Energy

BMS03_LEN_AGR_FC_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - FanCoil Chiller - Energy
BMS03_LEN_AGR_NW1_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - NW1 Chiller - Energy
BMS41_StacjaPogodowa_rTemperatura	Outside temperature (weather station)
Holidays	Working/non-working day
Week of the day	-
Month	-

Period of historic data: For training forecasting models, data gathered from February to September 2018 was used. The reason for that is the best data quality of the selected variables.

Basic operations:

Electricity consumptions: operations max and increment are performed to calculate the consumption in a period of time (max energy consumption period (i) – max energy consumption period (i-1); period can be one day, for example).

Outside temperature: operation mean is performed to calculate the mean temperature in a period (for example, one day). And the model used is an Artificial Neural Network without autoregressive term (no previous consumptions are included in the model) and removing the timestamps with missing values.

The model has been trained to forecast the next sample and an iterative invocation of the algorithm has been used to forecast a horizon of 3 samples, that is, the electricity consumption of the 3 next days. The quality of the trained model is:

MAPE = 7 %

CC = 0,9563

Forecasting horizon: 3 days

Validity / forecasting accuracy:

Historical data from February to September 2018 was used to train the model. Then, the model was tested to forecast consumptions during the following 2 months - October and November 2018.

Results:

Forecasting of consumption was performed as follows:

- Days 1-16 October: these results were obtained on demand.
- Days 17 October – 12/11: these results were obtained running the module automatically (once a day).

Next table shows the accuracy of the forecasting:

Table 13: Accuracy of the forecasted values

TS	Holidays	Consumption (real)	Consumption (forecasting)	Error (%)
2018-10-01T00:00:00Z	0	522.33	537.63	-2.93
2018-10-02T00:00:00Z	0	557.9	540.07	3.20
2018-10-03T00:00:00Z	0	570.93	537.19	5.91

2018-10-04T00:00:00Z	0	545.48	542.09	0.62
2018-10-05T00:00:00Z	0	592.2	533.12	9.98
2018-10-06T00:00:00Z	1	343.82	373.27	-9.57
2018-10-07T00:00:00Z	1	333.98	402.13	-20.41
2018-10-08T00:00:00Z	0	474.44	526.9	-11.06
2018-10-09T00:00:00Z	0	658.67	527.9	19.85
2018-10-10T00:00:00Z	0	542.46	553.4	-2.02
2018-10-11T00:00:00Z	0	567.01	573.23	-1.10
2018-10-12T00:00:00Z	0	548.99	585.9	-6.72
2018-10-13T00:00:00Z	1	365.72	395.28	-8.08
2018-10-14T00:00:00Z	1	339.18	387.16	-14.15
2018-10-15T00:00:00Z	0	547.11	540.45	1.22
2018-10-16T00:00:00Z	0	553.83	551.25	0.47
2018-10-17T00:00:00Z	0	536.86	551.86	-2.79
2018-10-18T00:00:00Z	0	530.45	561.03	-5.76
2018-10-19T00:00:00Z	0	529.48	541.66	-2.30
2018-10-20T00:00:00Z	1	292.87	337.72	-15.31
2018-10-21T00:00:00Z	1	312.12	332.62	-6.57
2018-10-22T00:00:00Z	0	524.88	504.26	3.93
2018-10-23T00:00:00Z	0	546.19	508.56	6.89
2018-10-24T00:00:00Z	0	548.49	510.1	7.00
2018-10-25T00:00:00Z	0	532.98	517.89	2.83
2018-10-26T00:00:00Z	0	531.26	527.23	0.76
2018-10-27T00:00:00Z	1	282.81	341.2	-20.65
2018-10-28T00:00:00Z	1	289.81	325.55	-12.33
2018-10-29T00:00:00Z	0	567.72	515.99	10.03
2018-10-30T00:00:00Z	0	551.36	591.82	-6.84
2018-10-31T00:00:00Z	0	531.52	546.31	-2.71

2018-11-01T00:00:00Z	1	435.48	377.41	15.39
2018-11-02T00:00:00Z	0	529.30	584.98	-9.52
2018-11-03T00:00:00Z	1	305.47	355.36	-14.04
2018-11-04T00:00:00Z	1	301.88	370.29	-18.47
2018-11-05T00:00:00Z	0	573.75	553.48	3.66
2018-11-06T00:00:00Z	0	545.10	547.22	-0.39
2018-11-07T00:00:00Z	0	563.05	547.43	2.85
2018-11-08T00:00:00Z	0	561.95	540.59	3.95
2018-11-09T00:00:00Z	0	538.86	538.92	-0.01
2018-11-10T00:00:00Z	1	299.29	341.32	-12.31
2018-11-11T00:00:00Z	1	292.32	342.74	-14.71
2018-11-12T00:00:00Z	0	429.08	524.31	-18.16

Figure 58: Comparison between the real consumptions and forecasted values

The model was retrained using data until January 2019 and results from April to June 2019 have a MAPE of 9.7%, being the MAPE for working and non-working days quite similar:

Figure 59: Load Forecasting Module Interface – Wilanów Town Hall.

The upper graph shows the values of energy consumption predictions: prediction (C) and the real consumptions (C – blue curve). The lower graph shows the values of the variables used to predict the consumption. In general, the performance of the module to forecast electrical consumptions is similar to the other pilot sites, with MAPE below 10%. However, forecasting models for daily heating consumptions (as the presented in the next subsection) have higher values of MAPE.

Heating consumption

The model was built to forecast space heating energy consumption for third floor in Wilanow Town Hall.

Modelling: Scenario and data

Although this consumption is the addition of three meters:

Table 14: Three electric meters considered

Node	Description
BMS31_HM_P3_LAZIENKA_CIEPLO_rEnergia	Heat Meter - Third floor - Space Heating - Energy
BMS31_HM_P3_FANCOIL_1_CIEPLO_rEnergia	Heat Meter - Room 333/1 - Space Heating - Energy
BMS31_HM_P3_FANCOIL_2_CIEPLO_rEnergia	Heat Meter - Room 333/2 - Space Heating - Energy

Only the BMS31_HM_P3_LAZIENKA_CIEPLO_rEnergia was considered for building the forecasting model. The reason is the other two measurements introduce a high error in the prediction. So, the forecasting model only provides the forecasting of consumption

BMS31_HM_P3_LAZIENKA_CIEPLO_rEnergia, that is almost the entire 3rd floor space heating consumption. It forecasts the daily consumption for the next three days.

Period of historic data: The model was trained using historic data gathered from October 2018 to January 2019. Unfortunately, due to the problems with heat meters at the polish pilot site, there is no historic data referring to whole heating season. The model for heating energy consumption was created, however more precise accuracy test will be possible to perform, only during upcoming heating season due to the fact that training set of data will be complete (based on whole winter season).

The model has been trained to forecast the next sample and an iterative invocation of the algorithm has been used to forecast a horizon of 3 samples, that is, the heating consumption of the 3 next days. The quality of the trained model is:

MAPE = 20%

Figure 60: Load Forecasting Module Interface – Wilanów Town Hall.

Validity / forecasting accuracy: Initially, a training data set with data gathered from January to March 2019 was used to test the forecasting model, resulting in a MAPE of around 16%. However, the discrepancy between real and forecasted heating consumptions have become bigger, which would lead to a retraining of the model after assessing if some change in the system (or how the system is exploited) has occurred.

3.2.1.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

As the demonstration area of the demo site covers only third floor, the evaluation of the module's impact on the building's performance is very limited. According to the feedback received from the Wilanow Facility Manager, the module can be used in order to detect any abnormal behaviour, for example overconsumption etc. This can be done by comparison the predictions with the real, measured values. Any deviation can be a signal for the deeper analysis.

3.2.1.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

It is often the case that buildings have more than one energy meter and the total consumption is a sum of several partial meters. Then, the module has been improved to allow the possibility of adding several variables in order to get the full overview on the energy consumption in the building.

3.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)

The Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (FDD-PCA) module detects failures or malfunctions creating an overconsumption of electricity in the building, deteriorating its energy performance.

Scenario: In this scenario the facility manager (FM) wants to know if there is an over-consumption in his building. The module is going to generate an alert for the FM to inform him that the module has detected a problem. The module can be used to detect problems related to cooling, heating, ventilation, lighting or any other existing application within the building. This module will enable the FM and his team to quickly detect problems and thus save energy consumption and money. There should also be less complaints of the building occupants. Moreover, the team will do less programmed maintenance because the problems will be detected automatically. It should diminish the man-months of the staff.

3.2.2.1 *Testing methodology*

In order to test the module at the Polish Pilot Site two models have been created by the module developer in cooperation with the pilot site manager. The key aspect was to choose the right scope for the module implementation and the suitable period of time with the possibly best data quality in order to test the module. The first model involved 86 variables presented below. Most variables relate to the comfort in the rooms such as: temperatures, humidity, CO₂ rate. Testing area covers entire third floor of the Wilanów Town Hall. However, the number of variables turned out to be too large which cause the excess number of alerts - the precision of the module is better when the area/ scope is narrower. This was the reason for the creation the second model and to focus on narrower scope of interest.

Modelling: Scenario and data – First model

The first FDD model was built using gathered data from 01/01/2019 to 20/05/2019. List of 86 variables involved in the model is presented below:

Table 15: List of 86 variables considered.

Variable	Description
BMS03_Ciepnomierz_CT_BUD_A_rStanLicznika	Heat Meter - Building A - Air heating in AHU - Energy
BMS03_Ciepnomierz_CT_rStanLicznika	Heat Meter - Building complex - Air heating in AHU - Energy
BMS03_LEN_AGR_FC_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - FanCoil Chiller - Energy
BMS03_LEN_AGR_NW1_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - NW1 Chiller - Energy
BMS31_KKW_03_02_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 302 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_02_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 302 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_02_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 302 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_03_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 303 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_03_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 303 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_04_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 304 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_04_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 304 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_05_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 305 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_05_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 305 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_05_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 305 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_06_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 306 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_06_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 306 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_06_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 306 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_07_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 307 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_07_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 307 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_07_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 307 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_12_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 312 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_12_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 312 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_12_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 312 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_14_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 314 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_14_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 314 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_14_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 314 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_17_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 317 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_17_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 317 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_17_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 317 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_18_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 318 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_18_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 318 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_18_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 318 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_19_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 319 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_19_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 319 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_20_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 320 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_20_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 320 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_21_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 321 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_21_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 321 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_21_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 321 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_22_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 322 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_22_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 322 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_22_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 322 - Heating setpoint temperature

BMS31_KKW_03_23_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 323 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_23_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 323 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_23_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 323 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_24_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 324 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_24_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 324 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_24_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 324 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_25_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 325 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_25_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 325 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_26_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 326 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_26_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 326 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_26_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 326 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_27_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 327 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_27_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 327 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_27_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 327 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_28_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 328 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_29_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 329 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_29_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 329 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_29_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 329 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_30_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 330 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_30_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 330 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_30_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 330 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_31_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 331 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_31_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 331 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_31_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 331 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_32_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 332 - Current temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_32_rTemperaturaChlodzenia	Room 332 - Cooling setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_32_rTemperaturaGrzania	Room 332 - Heating setpoint temperature
BMS31_KKW_03_K2_rTemperaturaAktualna	Corridor K2 - Current temperature
BMS31_LEN_RB3_FC_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 FanCoils - Energy
NW1_rTemperaturaWyciagu	NW1 - Exhaust Air temperature
BMS31_LEN_RB3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 Sockets - Energy
BMS31_LEN_RB3_OSW_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 Lighting - Energy
BMS31_LEN_RK3_GN_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS3.1 RK3 Computer sockets - Energy
BMS41_LEN_RB4_NW1_rEnergiaCzynnaPobierana	Electricity Meter - BMS4.1 NW1 - Energy
BMS41_StacjaPogodowa_rTemperatura	Weather Station - Outside temperature
BMSSK308_Klimat_SK_308_RTC_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 308 - Current temperature
BMSSK308_Klimat_SK_308_RTC_rTemperaturaZadanaLokalnie	Room 308 - Local setpoint temperature
BMSSK308_rH_308_rPomiar	Room 308 - Air humidity - Measurement
BMSSK310_CO2_310_rPomiar	Room 310 - CO2 concentration in air - Measurement
BMSSK310_CO2_311_rPomiar	Room 311 - CO2 concentration in air - Measurement
BMSSK310_Klimat_SK_310_RTC_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 310 - Current temperature
BMSSK310_Klimat_SK_311_RTC_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 311 - Current temperature
BMSSK310_rH_310_rPomiar	Room 310 - Air humidity - Measurement
NW1_rTemperaturaNawiewuZadana	NW1 - Supply Air setpoint temperature

The results are presented in two graphs that represent simple statistic indexes T^2 (magnitude fault) and Q (correlation fault). These indexes are used to detect abnormal behaviours, represented as a dot over the red areas. Thus, the red areas represent that one of the thresholds (or both) is overpassed, identifying a deviation of the new observation with respect to the model.

On the graphs below, we can see that the magnitude fault is overpassed for two days (15/02/2019 and 20/05/2019) while the correlation fault does not overpass.

The following figure shows that two faulty days were present in the model: 15/02/2019 and 20/05/2019:

Figure 61: FDD-PCA Module Interface – Wilanów Town Hall.

After clicking on any of the dot over chart's red area, module displays new window that allows to analyse the contributions of original variables to the statistics that detected the deviations. When the real value (red) exceeds statistic value (green) fault is detected. On the chart below, many of faulty variables can be observed.

Figure 62: Faulty day in the model: 20/05/2019 (T2).

Figure 63: Alerts generated by the FDD-PCA module for a specific day of the demonstration period (20/05/2019).

Observation: The above results were not satisfactory because of the excess of the faults and lack correlation to the building's behaviour – model was not precise. In order to improve the quality of the model, the scope of the interest has been narrowed. This reduction aimed to consider variables that are physically highly related, being a priori easier to understand the information provided by the FDD model. The focus is on AHU NW1 and the conference rooms served by this AHU (308,310,311).

Modelling: Scenario and data – Second model

The second FDD model was built using gathered data from 23/01/2018 to 27/06/2019. List of 31 variables involved in the model is presented below:

Table 16: List of 31 variables considered.

Variable	Description
NW1_rTemperaturaNawiewu	NW1 - Supply Air temperature
NW1_rTemperaturaNawiewuZadana	NW1 - Supply Air setpoint temperature
NW1_rTemperaturaWyciagu	NW1 - Exhaust Air temperature
BMS41_HM_DACH_CIEPLO_rEnergia	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air heating in AHU - Energy
BMS41_HM_DACH_CHLOD_rEnergia	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air cooling in AHU - Energy
BMS41_HM_DACH_CIEPLO_rPrzeplyw	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air heating in AHU - Flow
BMS41_HM_DACH_CHLOD_rPrzeplyw	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air cooling in AHU - Flow
BMS41_HM_DACH_CIEPLO_rTemperaturaPrzeplywu	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air heating in AHU - Flow temperature
BMS41_HM_DACH_CHLOD_rTemperaturaPrzeplywu	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air cooling in AHU - Flow temperature
BMS41_HM_DACH_CIEPLO_rTemperaturaPowrotu	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air heating in AHU - Return temperature
BMS41_HM_DACH_CHLOD_rTemperaturaPowrotu	Heat Meter - NW1 - Air cooling in AHU - Return temperature
BMS03_LEN_AGR_NW1_rEnergiaCzynna	Electricity Meter - NW1 Chiller - Energy
BMS31_Kontaktron_308_1_xKontakt	Room 308 - Window open_closed 1/4
BMS31_Kontaktron_308_2_xKontakt	Room 308 - Window open_closed 2/4
BMS31_Kontaktron_308_3_xKontakt	Room 308 - Window open_closed 3/4
BMS31_Kontaktron_308_4_xKontakt	Room 308 - Window open_closed 4/4
BMSSK308_CO2_308_rPomiar	Room 308 - CO2 concentration in air - Measurement
BMSSK310_CO2_310_rPomiar	Room 310 - CO2 concentration in air - Measurement
BMSSK310_CO2_311_rPomiar	Room 311 - CO2 concentration in air - Measurement
BMSSK308_rH_308_rPomiar	Room 308 - Air humidity - Measurement
BMSSK310_rH_310_rPomiar	Room 310 - Air humidity - Measurement
BMSSK310_rH_311_rPomiar	Room 311 - Air humidity - Measurement
BMSSK308_Klimat_SK_308_RTC_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 308 - Current temperature
BMSSK308_Klimat_SK_308_RTC_rTemperaturaZadanaLokalnie	Room 308 - Local setpoint temperature
BMSSK310_Klimat_SK_310_RTC_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 310 - Current temperature
BMSSK310_Klimat_SK_310_RTC_rTemperaturaZadanaLokalnie	Room 310 - Local setpoint temperature
BMSSK310_Klimat_SK_311_RTC_rTemperaturaAktualna	Room 311 - Current temperature
BMSSK310_Klimat_SK_311_RTC_rTemperaturaZadanaLokalnie	Room 311 - Local setpoint temperature
6695624_current_cloudiness	Current cloudiness
6695624_current_humidity	Current humidity
6695624_current_temperature	Current temperature

A manual pre-processing for data was necessary in order to change some “0” values to NaN. This reprocessing had the purpose to not learning “0” values as normal values of some variables, as they are really NaN values. The model is able to detect “0” as abnormal values. A clear example of variable with NaN values presenting “0” value for example variable: *BMSSK308_CO2_308_rPomiar* - this variable captures CO₂ values. CO₂ values under 300ppm are clear outliers regarding variable values distribution:

Figure 64: Variable: BMSSK308_CO2_308_rPomiar – data distribution.

Finally, the model was created using all the available days without NaN values. The model was created with 106 days (77 working days and 29 non-working days).

On the graphs below, we can see that the magnitude fault overpassed for one day (04/07/2019).

Figure 65: FDD-PCA Module Interface – Wilanów Town Hall.

Figure 66: Faulty day in the model: 04/07/2019.

Faulty vars:

Figure 67: Alerts generated by the FDD-PCA module for a specific day of the demonstration period (04/07/2019).

Observation: The model generated the alert for the facility manager on a specific day and informed about the abnormal behaviour of the cooling installation. Further analysis of the faulty variables has showed that the alert was correct because it was caused by the chiller failure. The facility manager confirmed that indeed problem has occurred – the chiller stopped working due to the serious problem with compressor as well as the circulation pumps.

3.2.2.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

The module enables the facility managers to detect any abnormal behaviour in the building and inform about deviations by reporting an alert. This can be a signal to a deeper investigation of the problems, and gives possibility to react in the fastest possible way. Module can be run for the various types of installation such as ventilation (AHUs), lighting, heating systems etc. It only requires the creation of appropriate models by an expert. Module tests on the polish pilot site have shown that module is more accurate when the smaller scope of interest is considered. Too many variables cause the excess of alerts. When the area of interest has been narrowed the module is more precise - which caused in a correct identification of the malfunction of the chiller that serves AHU NW1.

3.2.2.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The following improvements have been required and delivered:

- Reports and results explanations

3.2.3 Energy management (developed by ENE)

The Energy management (EM) module is for organizations that want to keep or acquire the ISO-50001 certification or that want to manage their energy consumption optimally. The module is helping the EM and his team to capture and prioritize improvement opportunities. The software shows on their screen a list of improvement opportunities with a ranking according to the importance and the impact of the task. It has made the decisions of the EM team easier to take. The module is also helping the EM manage his team. Indeed, it automatically assigns actions with target dates and reminders to the energy team members so they can prioritize and assign to individuals within the team. It is also helping the EM to manage reports. The EM is able to stock documents such as monthly energy reports or action status on the dashboard.

3.2.3.1 Testing methodology

The EM module's performance

Matching the ISO 50001 requirements, as depicted below, the performances of the EM visualization module cover two main functions.

- Energy Planning & Monitoring;
- ISO 50001 Management System.

Figure 68: Operative menu

Energy Planning & Monitoring

Energy planning is the “Plan” part of the PDCA cycle of an ISO 50001 EnMS. Energy planning provides the foundation for developing an EnMS that is based on an understanding of an organization’s energy performance.

This is the step where the organization’s analysis of its energy data, along with other energy information is used to make informed decisions on actions to continually improve energy performance.

Within the HIT2GAP Energy Management visualization module, the “Energy Planning and Monitoring” section is divided into 2 main areas:

- A. Energy Performance, with 3 sub-functions: Energy Review, EnPI’s, Charts.
- B. Action Management, with 4 sub-functions: IOs, Plans, O&Ts, Charts.

Energy Performance: Energy Review

The energy review is the analytical part of the energy planning process. This function analyses both the energy sources and the identified significant energy uses within the building or location. The Energy Review function in the HIT2GAP EM visualization module presents the data in the form of a Sankey diagram, linking the energy sources to the energy uses. The energy sources are typically identified from energy utility bills and/or energy audit reports. The energy uses are typically identified from energy audits and sub-meters.

Figure below shows the Sankey diagram for the energy consumption data:

Figure 69. Wilanow (Poland): energy consumption Sankey diagram

On the left side of the Sankey diagram we can see Wilanow Town Hall data from the bills. The right side of the diagram represents the real values coming from the meters. The reason for the discrepancies between the energy sources and energy uses is due to the fact that data from the bills relates to the entire building and data from the meters relates only to the third floor (with few exceptions). The diagram enables the facility manager to investigate and to identify areas with significant energy consumption.

Energy Performance: EnPI

Energy Performance Indicators (EnPIs) and their corresponding energy baselines are metrics that are defined by the organization to measure energy performance. Types and examples of EnPIs include the following:

- energy consumption (in total or broken down by energy use) (e.g. kWh, GJ);
- simple ratio such as energy consumption per unit of output (e.g. kWh per tonne, kWh per man hour worked)
- statistical model (e.g. linear and nonlinear regression);
- engineering based model (e.g. simulation).

The EnPI function in the HIT2GAP EM visualization module allows the user to see a list of EnPIs configured for the location selected. The view displays the data for the previous month, as depicted in the figure below:

Figure 70. Wilanow (Poland): Defined EnPI functions

An EnPI can be at a facility, system, process or equipment level and should have an appropriate baseline at the same level for comparative purposes.

The user, clicking on a description text, is able to see the progress of the EnPI versus the established baselines over the previous months, as shown in figure on the right side.

EnPI: Electricity 2018 vs 2015 (Baseline) (kWh/m²) - 2018

Figure 71. Wilanow (Poland): EnPI Total Electricity per Area

Energy Performance: Charts

As depicted in the following figures, the Charts function in the Energy Performance area includes a dashboard showing four default energy performance charts for the selected location. Other available charts can be selected by clicking on the "Change Chart" button.

Figure 72. Wilanów (Poland): Energy Performance Charts

Action Management: IOs

The identification of improvement opportunities (IOs) is an output from the energy review. There are also Improvement Opportunities triggered from other Modules delivered through the HIT2GAP platform. Having identified improvement opportunities, these IOs are prioritized based on criteria defined by the organisation (e.g. cost savings, capital cost, payback, complexity, impact on health & safety). The energy manager (and energy team) can review this list and decide what IOs should be included in the actions plans (see Plans function next).

With the HIT2GAP EM visualization module, the Improvement Opportunities (IOs) function displays the list of IOs including their category and their prioritization ranking if assessment has been completed.

Basically, IOs are visualized according to three basic categories:

- a. those that are still open (ongoing);
- b. those that need to be assessed before the successful completion;
- c. those that are considered into the Action Plan and contribute to the yearly budget.

Figure below shows the IOs information for each category:

Figure 73. Wilanow (Poland): Improvement Opportunities

Action Management: Plans

The organization establishes, implements and maintains action plans for achieving its objectives and targets. (ISO 50001).

The Plans function within the Action Management areas of the HIT2GAP EM visualization module shows what actions have been assigned to various people and the target dates for completing these actions. The user can also see easily what actions are overdue.

Figure 74. Wilanow (Poland): Action Plans

Action Management: O&Ts

ISO 50001 requires that objectives and targets including timeframes are defined to improve the energy performance of the organisation. The user can view overall targets set for the whole site, the targets set for different energy uses and targets and potential savings from different IOs.

Figure 75. Wilanow (Poland): Objectives and Targets

While the bottom of the screen shows detailed information on the breakdown of electrical and thermal targets for individual energy uses and the potential energy savings (electrical and thermal) from identified IOs that have been included in the action plans.

This detailed view also summarises whether the overall target can be met based on the identified IOs or if further IOs need to be identified and actions included in the plans.

Action Management: Charts

The Charts function in the Action Management area includes a dashboard showing four default action management charts for the location selected. Other available charts can be selected by clicking on the “Change Chart” button.

Figure 76. Wilanow (Poland): Action Management Charts

ISO 50001 Management System

An EnMS is a framework by which an organization establishes processes to achieve control and improvement of energy performance – a systematic approach to energy management. Think of an EnMS as the umbrella under which those processes relate and interact.

An EnMS is often viewed as having two aspects: “Management” and “Technical”. In the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module, the “Energy Planning & Monitoring” area, described in the previous sections, are the technical aspects of the energy management system.

This section describes the ISO 50001 Management System or the management aspects of the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module.

The main function implemented is the “Planning” function, which includes six sub-functions: Doc, Audit, Mtg, NCs, Charts and Tasks.

ISO 50001 Management System: Doc

Within an ISO 50001 EnMS you are required to establish, implement and maintain information, in paper, electronic or any other medium, to describe the core elements of the EnMS and their interaction and that documents required by the standard are adequately controlled.

Within the HIT2GAP EM module, full document management functionality is available. The “Docs” function in the HIT2GAP EM Visualisation module allows the use to access and view documents related to the EnMS.

Figure 77. Wilanów (Poland): Docs

Filters allow the user to find documents easily by different types, categories and sub-categories.

ISO 50001 Management System: Audit

An internal audit of an EnMS is an objective, systematic review of all or part of an organization’s EnMS. The purpose of internal audits is to check that everyone is doing what is expected of them in relation to the requirements of your EnMS and specifically to:

- determine if the requirements are being met (if conformance to ISO 50001 is required);
- identify and drive improvements in energy performance and the EnMS.

The Audit function within the ISO 50001 Management System allows the user to view the full audit schedule at the top of the screen and more detailed view at the bottom of the screen including the start dates and end dates.

ISO 50001 Management System: Meetings

The Meetings (“Mtg”) functions within the HIT2GAP Energy Management module, allows users to schedule and plan regular energy team and management review meetings. It allows actions to be created and managed from the outcomes of the meeting.

Within the HIT2GAP EM visualization module, the user can view the meetings and its outcomes.

Planning: NCs

Within the organizations of an EnMS, nonconformities (*NCs) should be corrected to ensure the effectiveness of the EnMS. NCs are usually highlighted as a result of an internal audit but can also be highlighted during routine operations.

Within the energy management module, NCs can be created and managed effectively allowing the energy manager to assign NCs to appropriate staff to identify the cause of the problem and to ensure that corrective and preventive actions are taken to prevent it happening again.

The NCs function in the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module allows users to see the list of open and closed NCs including completion dates and who has been assigned.

Planning: Charts

The Charts function in the ISO 50001 Management System area includes a dashboard showing four default action management charts for the location selected. Other available charts can be selected by clicking on the “Change Chart” button.

Figure 78. Wilanów (Poland): Management System: Charts

3.2.3.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

The module has been tested for its functionality. Because the module is mostly for visualisation purposes, it helped to visualize the performance of the building among several years. The demonstration area for the polish pilot site is limited to the third floor, however the module enabled also aggregation bill data for entire building and compare its performance by using charts, EnPIs as shown below on the screenshots:

Energy Performance Indicators (EnPI's)

The following list of EnPI's (Figure 79) are configured for the Wilanow Site (All are defined for a baseline year of 2015).

1. Electricity Consumption (kWh) per building area (m2)
2. Total Energy Consumption (kWh) per building area (m2)
3. Heating Consumption (kWh) per building area (m2)

Figure 79. Wilanow (Poland): EnPI's

Figure 80. Wilanow (Poland): 2018 EnPI's

Figure 81. Wilanow (Poland): 2018 EnPI's

Energy Analysis (Sankey)

The Sankey diagram for each year is generated based on bill data manually entered to build the left side and metered data mapped against energy uses to build the right side. The energy consumption data is read directly on a nightly schedule from the HIT2GAP platform.

Figure 82. Wilanow (Poland): 2015-2018 Energy Flow Diagram's (Sankey's).

Objectives & Targets/Improvement Opportunities Implemented

The screenshots below show the year on year targeting of energy savings for each energy use identified for the site, what improvement opportunities were identified to meet those targets and the savings actually made.

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022		
		kWh		Objective	Total(kWh)		Electrical(kWh)		Thermal(kWh)	
					Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date
Overall Objective: Reduce total energy by 5%					87500	0	50000	0	37500	0
Energy Use Total & Targets		218913			70200		47500		22700	
Total Savings (Potential & To-Date) from Actions					33000	0	33000	0	0	0
▼	CT- air handling units and CWU-water heating - Wilanów Town Hall	144501		Reduce Electricity usage by 5%			13500	0.00	0	0.00
Total							0	0	0	0
▼	Fan heaters and convection heaters. - Wilanów Town Hall	51251		Cut thermal usage by 5%			0	0.00	22700	0.00
Total							0	0	0	0
▼	HVAC - Wilanów Town Hall	19773		Reduce Electricity Consumption by 5%			34000	0	0	0
20/11/2017 - New room units							33000	-	-	-
Total							33000	0	0	0
▼	Office Equipment - Wilanów Town Hall	2655		-			0	0.00	0	0.00
Total							0	0	0	0
▼	Lighting - Wilanów Town Hall	733		-			0	0.00	0	0.00
Total							0	0	0	0

Figure 83. Wilanow (Poland): 2019 Objectives & Targets

Energy Savings

The charts below show a month by month comparison of energy consumption for a) the current year vs last year and b) last year vs the previous year.

Figure 84. Wilanow (Poland): Energy Consumption Charts.

3.2.3.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

The possibility of automatic addition of improvement opportunities, based on alerts coming from other modules, was added.

3.2.4 BIM visualisation module (developed by ZUT)

Zutec Dimensions is a 3D model viewer. For HIT2GAP it was used to display sensor data from a building overlaid in the model. As there is a delay between the sensors and that data being available on BEMServer (the Wilanów data read by the BMS is collected by a script and saved in a .csv file everyday (once a day), pushed to Plat.One and finally transferred to the Core Platform) it can show only simulated live data that is 2 weeks old as an example if there was fresh data available. Alternatively, it can also display historic data which is the use case for the Wilanów town hall building. The datapoints can be created at any point in space or they can be attached to rooms or components in the model. They are categorised into groups as needed. These groups of datapoints can be enabled and disabled in 3D space in the model. Alternatively, all datapoints are listed in the main UI. From here all values can be read and clicking on a datapoint in the UI brings user to its position in the model to quickly locate it in the building.

Figure 85. BIM Visualisation interface.

Figure 86. Visualisation of the parameters for an individual room selected.

3.2.4.1 Testing methodology

In order to test the module, data visualised on the model has been compared to the values stored in the BMS. After checking the values display on the module it turned out that data match to the appropriate values generating from the sensors (stored in the BMS). The next step in order to test the module, was to interview the Facility Manager from the Wilanów building as he will be the end user of the BIM Visualisation Module. Before answering the questions, BIM Module's features and abilities were demonstrated to FM. Below the results of the survey are presented:

I Relevance of Alerts / Notifications

Definition:

Alert 1: For sensors measuring room TEMPERATURES: if value is lower than 20 °C or higher than 26 °C, show it in RED

Alert 2: For sensors measuring rooms CO₂ CONCENTRATIONS: if values are above 1000 ppm, colour them in RED

Alert 3: For sensors measuring room RELATIVE HUMIDITY: if values are lower than 25% or higher than 60%, colour them in RED

Q1: In terms of being useful and providing usable information, how do you rate Alert 1?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Strong
- Very Strong

FM Comments: The alert particularly important during the winter season.

Q2: In terms of being useful and providing usable information, how do you rate Alert 2?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Strong
- Very Strong

FM Comments: Alert particularly important for the conference rooms.

Q3: In terms of being useful and providing usable information, how do you rate Alert 3?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Strong
- Very Strong

FM Comments: -

Q4: In terms of being useful and providing usable information, how do you rate the presented historical data?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Strong
- Very Strong

FM Comments: If module enables to visualise historical data the rate is Average. The historical / archive data are very helpful for example in order to negotiate with tenant on their claims related to the provided services. Based on historical data the tool can be useful in order to investigate or to detect any malfunctions in HVAC systems. If the module, apart from visualizing historical data, also offers on-line data (both functionalities) then the rate is Very Strong.

Q5: Do you have the possibility of remote viewing the comfort parameters in any room (temperature, humidity, CO₂, etc.) and data from heat / cold/ electricity meters? How?

Yes, theoretically BMS system installed in the Town Hall Building allows similar functions – data visualisation on 2D layouts but only for basics parameters. Moreover the visualisation of the data is not user friendly – data presented on the layouts are illegible.

Q6: Do you have an opportunity to check / review data for any period from the past? Is this information useful for you? For what purpose?

Yes, the standard BMS system offers trends functionality (save historical data). The historical/ archival data are very helpful for example in order to negotiate with tenant on their claims related to the provided services. Based on historical data the tool can be useful in order to investigate or to detect any malfunctions in HVAC systems.

Q7: After learning about the functionality of the BIM Viz module, do you see any use for this solution in your daily work? What?

If only the module is running on the live data together with the historical data the module can be very useful. It gives the possibility of monitoring the systems in buildings and to react quickly if some malfunctions are observed.

Q8: What additional functionalities do you think can be added to the module?

1. *Visualisation of real time data.*
2. *The ability to control systems from the module level (not only visualisation).*

II Ergonomics / User-Interface

Q1: In terms of visualizing the information/data trends, how do you rate the functionality/performance of the module in comparison with other conventional methods (such as retrieving information from a CSV file)?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Strong
- Very Strong

FM Comments: Advantages of data visualisation on 3D model are: information readability, intuitiveness, speed of data access.

Q2: In terms of being User-friendly and intuitive, how do you rate the UI of the module?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Strong
- Very Strong

FM Comments: The reason for the rate Average is the interface only in English language. This can be a problem for non-english speakers.

III Investment Return

Q1: In your opinion, how much time can be saved by using the module as part of the BMS and monitoring system?

- None
- Less than 25%
- Between 25% to 50%
- Between 50% to 75%
- More than 75%

3.2.4.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

According to the feedback received from the Facility Manager from the polish demo site, module offers wide range of useful functionalities. Currently the module has been running only using the archival data so the impact evaluation is very limited. According to the FM, possibility of reviewing sensor data from the past can be very useful, for instance in order to investigate or to detect malfunctions in HVAC systems, however the module can bring the greatest benefit only when working on real time data.

3.2.4.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

Initially, historic data could not be displayed. However, as real time data was not available through BEMServer for Wilanów it was suggested to display historic data. Any date and time at 15 minute intervals can be selected and all datapoints are updated to show this point in time. If there is no data available for that time a message 'No Data' is displayed. Being able to flick through the data on the model may help diagnose any faults that occurred in the buildings systems.

3.3 Gap evaluation

Due to the fact that the Polish demo site concerned only the third floor of the Wilanów Town Hall, the assessment of the energy performance gap reduction is very limited, and cannot be estimated in order to provide accurate and relevant information. The baseline situation for the Polish pilot site, that could be determined, concerned the whole building while the demonstration area includes only the third floor. A change in the energy efficiency of only one floor has a negligible effect on improving the energy performance for the entire building. Moreover, most of the modules have worked on a very limited scope of interest and during the very short period of time (the testing phase due to various reasons was shortened and lasted less than a year).

However, the implementation of the modules at Wilanów Town Hall, even on such a limited demo area, has shown that the energy performance can be improved successfully by:

- Detecting malfunctions or deviations in the operation of the HVAC systems. The fast information about problems allows to take quick action and thus minimize the adverse effects of failures.
- Visualisation of any installation parameters in a very intuitive way, on a 3D model. According to the feedback from the facility manager, the visualisation tool is essential and crucial in his daily work in order to monitor the building's performance. Visualisation tools allow to save time on inspection of the installations and enable detecting any abnormal behaviour.
- Forecasting the energy consumption (in particular, in relation to the whole building). The forecasts enable detecting any deviations such as overconsumption etc. by comparison of the predictions with the real values.

3.4 Lessons learnt during the operation

The first lesson learnt is that the quality of data from the sensors is very important. Incomplete data causes incorrect operation of the modules.

Another lesson learnt is that, the connection and data collection from the building through the middleware platform has proved to be quite problematic. In the case of problems with data, it was necessary to determine on which side the problem occurred: whether on the Plat.One, BEMServer or the pilot building itself.

The third lesson learnt is that, the real time data are more valuable, in particular for the module such as BIM Visualisation in order to monitor the parameters in the real time.

Next lesson learnt is that, the choosing the right scope for running the modules is crucial. Some of the modules such as FDD – PCA operate more precisely when the area of interest is narrow (number of HVAC system, etc.).

The fifth lesson learnt is that, some of the modules require an expert assistance in order to create the “reference models” and results analysis (for example: Load Forecasting and FDD-PCA).

And finally, the English language on most interfaces can be a problem for the efficient use of applications by users in non-English countries.

4 Nanogune (Spain, GIR)

Nanogune building is a public research center located in San Sebastian (SPAIN). The building has 7319 m² distributed over six floors. Nanogune was inaugurated in January 2009, and it houses offices, 15 ultra-sensitive laboratories and a cleanroom of nearly 300 m² where the air purity is under strict supervision.

Figure 87: Nanogune building.

Building's primary energy sources are gas and grid electricity. There are two gas boilers that provide heat to the facilities and an air/water chiller with heat recovery for cooling. The BMS of the building controls the lighting and HVAC system.

4.1 Use cases

In Nanogune, three different types of users are involved: energy managers, facility managers and occupants. GIROA-VEOLIA is the energy manager who is in charge of analysing historical energy data (energy consumption and production) and improving energy efficiency of the building. The facility manager is in charge of the building infrastructure and its correct functioning. The facility manager and GIROA-VEOLIA, as energy manager, are the end-users of the modules developed in HIT2GAP. Finally, building occupants refer to researchers and workers that make use of the facilities.

For GIROA-VEOLIA, as **energy manager**, the main goal for the implementation of the modules in Nanogune is a better measurement and visualization of the control variables in order to have a highest knowledge about the building behaviour and understanding of the existing gap. In order to achieve the objective, the following use cases can be expected:

- Identification of the critical variables that describe the energy building behaviour.
- Accurate consumption predictions that will provide a better capability of making previsions, reducing the excess costs and transforming them into saving.
- Analysis of the evolution of the made decisions, in such way that reduction in energy consumption thanks to the actions performed could be proved.
- An accessible platform where the different partners could check the state of the variables, providing complete transparency to the facility manager

For energy managers, the knowledge acquired using the innovative tools developed in HIT2GAP could be applied in the future to other buildings in which the monitoring of the facilities is not so developed.

For the **facility manager** the modules should offer a more efficient control in the failure detection and improvements in the corrective and planned maintenances operations. Moreover, the modules should support the facility manager in management actions and offer a decision-making assistance.

Building occupants are also involved in the building efficiency improvement project and should learn how to make a more responsible use of energy. In addition, the platform should empower the occupants by offering the possibility of adjusting the comfort of the building by means of the feedback they provide.

In order to meet the expectations and purposes of all users, the modules that have been implemented in Nanogune are the following:

- Load Forecasting. This module provides energy demand forecasting, intended to support energy budget control, demand response and performance measure and verification protocols.
- Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis and System Oriented. These modules enable the early detection of system and component malfunctions that deteriorate the energy performance of buildings and provide information facilitating the application of corrective actions.
- Energy Management. This module offers a systematic approach to Energy Management in compliance with the ISO 50001 international standard.
- Gap Reasoner. The module is based on uncertainty analysis (UA) and sensitivity analysis (SA) of building performance simulation. The module runs simulation models with a set of uncertain input parameters and delivers statistically distributed simulation with the objective to provide a more reliable simulation result.

On the following table, objective of the demonstration and expected impacts are presented for each module:

Table 17: Objectives of the demonstration and expected impacts for Nanogune building

Module	Partner	Objective of the demonstration / expected impact
Fault Detection and Diagnosis Modules (FDD-PCA)	UDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect misbehaviours or faults. • Reduce response time to faults.
Load Forecasting	UDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecast power consumption in building or zones of a building. • Improve prediction for reactive actions, • Establishment of energy baseline.
User Behaviour Modules (BM-ML)	EGE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing energy consumption whilst increasing occupant comfort by generating recommendations including: • Proactive recommendations for facility managers about indoor temperature settings, air flow, lighting system, HVAC operation schedules, etc.
Energy Management (EnMS)	ENE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Between 2%-5% energy saving due to a systematic approach based on the ISO 50001 standard without any capital cost • Further energy savings due to low-cost actions. • Increase people awareness • Persons & man-months reduction for everyday EnMS staff's activities. • Better Management and effective Decision-making process.
Gap Reasoner	FISE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of reasons for an energy performance gap.

EM Visualisation	ENE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display the appropriate information to the user on the “current” status of activities generated and managed generated by the EM module.
FM Visualisation	FISE	<p>Graphical user interface for the Gap Reasoner module. Enable decision support for the operational management of the building by providing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview as well as detailed information on the energy operation of buildings and building services like e.g. heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems, lighting etc.; • A forecast energy consumption dataset from the building energy simulation models.

4.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot

For the evaluation of the effect brought by the HIT2GAP solution on Nanogune pilot site, the modules have been tested in different scenarios. In order to analyse its effectiveness Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined.

Table 18: Test scenarios and KPIs for Nanogune building

Module	Test scenario	KPIs
Fault Detection and Diagnosis Modules (FDD-PCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building general electricity consumption 	Quantity of detected faults/misbehaviours
Load Forecasting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building general electricity consumption • Building gas consumption • Chiller electrical consumption 	Forecast deviation from real data
User Behaviour Modules (BM-ML)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First floor Nano building. Analyze the consumption of HVAC, lightning and force, occupancy data and occupants' surveys. 	Occupants comfort First floor energy consumption
Energy Management (EM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Fifth Floor Heating/Cooling •Roof Heating/Cooling •Basement Laboratories •Basement Clean Room •Second Floor •Ground Floor •Basement Parking •First Floor •Ground Floor Laboratories •First Floor Laboratories •Boilers 	Energy costs Energy uses consumption Energy savings generated for each energy use
Gap Reasoner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building general electricity consumption 	Real consumption vs. theoretical consumption
EM Visualisation	Graphical user interface for the Energy Management module.	
FM Visualisation	Graphical user interface for the Gap Reasoner module.	

4.2.1 Load Forecasting (developed by UDG)

The load forecasting module allows energy managers to forecast the power consumption by usage (lighting, plug load, ventilation etc.) and by building or zone of the building.

GIROA-VEOLIA as energy manager needs to prepare and follow his energy performance contracts. Through the forecasting of the module the contracts can be evaluated and overconsumptions can be anticipated and justified. This module helps controlling the energy budget.

In Nanogune, the Load Forecasting module has been implemented to obtain the load prediction for the three main energy consumptions of the building.

4.2.1.1 Testing methodology

From all the energy meters installed in Nanogune building, three meters were selected to be tested in this module for their relevance. This testing scenarios were defined together with the facility manager. The three selected energy consumptions were:

General Electricity

This model forecasts the overall electricity consumption of the building. It uses daily data from the general electricity meter.

In first place, in order to develop suitable forecasting models, the module has been used in modelling mode. The module calculates the consumption predictions for these scenarios through models based on a recurrent profile built on historical data. Historical data from the selected meter has been given as input to the module, that provided automatically the forecasting model. Historical data from past periods of duration from 1 to 3 months have been used (22/05/2018 – 31/03/2019). The dataset also contained weather info, which starts on 22/5/2018.

For the training the following results were obtained:

- MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) = 4,7%
- CC (Continuity Count) = 88%
- RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) = 555

After that, the model has been launched in the simulation-forecasting mode. So, the model is being running daily in order to generate results for forecasting windows of 3 days in the future.

In order to analyze the validity of the forecast the results are compared with real consumption data to detect deviations. The following results were obtained for different periods for working and non-working days:

Testing with data from period 22/05/2018 – 31/03/2019:

MAPE (working) = 2,9%; MAPE (non working) = 8,5%

Data testing from 01/04/2019 – 21/04/2019:

MAPE (working) = 1,2%; MAPE (non working) = 5%

Data testing from 01/04/2019 – 07/05/2019:

MAPE (working) = 1,4%; MAPE (non working) = 3,7%

Data testing from 01/07/2019 – 30/07/2019:

Figure 88: Forecasting results for general electricity from 01/07/2019 to 30/07/2019

In this period, 22, 23, 24 and 29 July real consumption got from the BEMServer is too low, which leads to MAPE values too high. However, this result improves if data from 1st to 21th July are considered. In this case MAPE is approximately 6%:

Figure 89: Forecasting results for general electricity from 01/07/2019 to 21/07/2019

General Gas

This model forecasts the total gas consumption of the building, demanded by the two boilers that cover the heating and hot water demand. It uses daily data from the gas meter.

In first place, in order to develop suitable forecasting models, the module has been used in modelling mode. Historical data from the selected meter has been given as input to the module that provided automatically the forecasting model. Historical data from past periods of duration from 1 to 3 months have been used (22/05/2018 – 31/03/2019). The dataset also contained weather info, which starts on 22/5/2018.

For the training the following results were obtained:

- MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) = 2,3%
- CC (Continuity Count) = 37%
- RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) = 2,8

After that, the model has been launched in the simulation-forecasting mode. So, the model is being running daily in order to generate results for forecasting windows of 3 days in the future.

In order to analyze the validity of the forecast the results are compared with real consumption data to detect deviations. The following results were obtained for different periods for working and non-working days:

Testing with data form period 22/05/2018 – 31/03/2019:

MAPE (working) = 2,2%; MAPE (non working) = 2,6%

Data testing from 01/04/2019 – 21/04/2019:

MAPE (working) = 1,6%; MAPE (non working) = 1,5%

Data testing from 01/04/2019 – 07/05/2019:

MAPE (working) = 1,8%; MAPE (non working) = 1,4%

Data testing results from 01/07/2019 – 30/07/2019:

Figure 90: Forecasting results for general gas from 01/07/2019 to 30/07/2019

Chiller

This model forecasts the thermal energy produced by the chiller that supplies all cooling uses of the building. It is essential to analyze the consumption of the chiller since it composes the 9% of the electricity load of Nanogune. This module uses data from the heat meter installed in the chiller. This meter measures the daily cool demand of the building.

In first place, in order to develop a suitable forecasting model, the module has been used in modelling mode. The module calculates the consumption predictions for these scenarios through models based on a recurrent profile built on historical data. Historical data from the selected meter have been given as input to the module, that provided automatically the forecasting model. Historical data from past periods of duration from 5 months have been used (01/01/2018 – 31/05/2019). The dataset also contained weather info.

After that, the model has been launched in the simulation-forecasting mode. So, the model has been tested for forecasting windows of 3 days in the future.

In order to analyze the validity of the forecast the results are compared with real consumption data to detect deviations. The following results were obtained for different periods for working and non-working days:

Testing with the same data training (period 01/01/2019 – 31/05/2019):

MAPE (WD) = 7%; MAPE (NWD) = 8%

Figure 91: Forecasting results for chiller from 01/01/2019 to 31/05/2019

After that, data was tested for the period 01/06/2019 - 31/07/2019:

MAPE (WD) = 9.5%; MAPE (NWD) = 63%

Figure 92: Forecasting results for chiller from 01/06/2019 to 31/07/2019

The MAPE for working days is a 9%. However, for non-working days it has an elevated error. This is due to that during two non-working days the values were lower than usual, and in another non-working day the consumption was very high (of the order of a working day).

4.2.1.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

The precision of the models depends on the predicted usage. The model has a good precision when the MAPE < 20%. The results from the load forecasting module show a good level of accuracy in the forecasted values for most of the cases. When the performance of the building is regular the forecasting has been accurate. However, when the consumption is not within the commons, the module doesn't give so accurate results.

This module enables facility managers to go from a corrective control of the energy consumption to a predictive one. For example, they would be able to plan maintenance work in the hours with less demand expected. Moreover, this module can help the facility manager to identify deviations and overconsumptions for the usage that are regular and have MAPE under 20%. This way, they would be able to anticipate deviations from the energy contracts.

4.2.1.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

Due to some communication issues Nanogune data was not available in BEMServer. In order to solve this, the module offers the possibility of uploading data statically to create the models and test them.

4.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)

The Fault Detection and Diagnosis - Principal Component Analysis (FDD-PCA) module detects failures or malfunctions creating an overconsumption of electricity in the building, deteriorating its energy performance.

The module can be used to detect problems related to cooling, heating, ventilation, lighting or any other existing application within the building. This module will enable the FM and his team to quickly detect problems and thus save energy consumption and money. There should also be less complaints of the building occupants. Moreover, the team will do less programmed maintenance because the problems will be detected automatically. It should diminish the man-months of the staff.

4.2.2.1 *Testing methodology*

In order to test the module FDD-PCA, the cooling network of the building was selected. The cooling demand composes the 9% of Nanogune's energy demand. This network is critical because it is usually a target of the complaints of the users. In addition, it would be replicable to the heating network.

For creating the model, a set of sensors installed in the cold circuit was used, as listed in the following table:

Table 19: Variables used for the model of FDD-PCA module

Variable	Description
NAN_TermF_Enfriadora_Heat_Energy_kWh	Energy delivered by the chiller
NAN_TermF_Refrigeracion_Procesos_Heat_Energy_kWh	Energy consumed by the Clean Room for process cooling
NAN_TermF_Fancoils_PB_y_1_Torre_Heat_Energy_kWh	Energy consumed by HVAC of ground and first floor of Torre building
NAN_TermF_Climatizadoras_AP_Heat_Energy_kWh	Energy consumed by the HVAC of the Clean Room
NAN_TermF_Fancoils_2_3_y_4_Torre_Heat_Energy_kWh	Energy consumed by HVAC of second, third and fourth floor of Torre building
NAN_TermF_Fancoils_1_Nano_Heat_Energy_kWh	Energy consumed by HVAC of first floor of Nano building
OWM_3110044_current_temperature	Outside temperature
OWM_3110044_current_humidity	Outside humidity
OWM_3110044_current_cloudiness	Outside cloudiness

The developers created the model with these variables. The data used has a time-step of 1 hour. The execution periodicity of the models is once a day and the module analyses automatically the data of the day before.

Figure 93: FDD results and interface

The results are presented in two graphs. The one above is the statistic index magnitude fault (T²). It detects when parameters magnitudes are abnormal but inside the restrictions of the model, for example when the cooling overconsumes because it is very hot outside. The second graph is the correlation fault (Q). It detects when a parameter varies in an irregular manner. For example, when usually two variables increase at the same time, the system detects when one of them increases and the other remains constant or decrease. When the dot is on the red area it means that there has been a deviation of a parameter with respect to the model.

In the model created, it can be observed that magnitude fault doesn't pass the threshold. However, the correlation fault does overpass the threshold. After detecting these faults, clicking on any of these dots on red area the contribution analysis is displayed. Below the analysis for 23rd July is displayed:

Figure 94: FDD contribution analysis results

For each variable, hourly values are plotted. These indexes can be used to detect abnormal behaviours. If the real value (in red) exceeds the limit value (in green) calculated by the model, a fault has been detected. In this example, we can observe that the anomalous values detected correspond with anomalous values in temperature and humidity, being this correlation fault greater than usual. So, in this case it didn't mean there was a fault, but an anomalous value produced by extreme weather conditions, since 23rd July was the hottest day of the month.

4.2.2.1 *Depth analysis of the key performance indicators results*

In the model created, it can be observed that magnitude fault doesn't pass the threshold throughout the month. However, the correlation fault does overpass the threshold in 8 days out of 31. After discussing the days where the correlation fault was high with Nanogune maintenance team, it was concluded that this performance is within the common on hot days.

This module helps the facility manager to detect abnormal consumptions with hourly precision. The module enables the facility manager to shorten the response time to different types of problems; machinery failure, communication and gateway problems, equipment working out of schedule... In addition, as the module helps to solve the problems faster, it will have a positive impact in the comfort of the building occupants.

However, since the module detects the faults but it doesn't give information about the possible causes, the facility manager must verify if it did indeed correspond to an anomalous event or it was a problem that needs to be solved.

4.2.2.2 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

Due to some communication issues Nanogune data was not available in BEMServer. In order to solve this, the module offers the possibility of uploading data statically to create the models and test them.

4.2.3 Behaviour modelling – Semantic approach (developed by EGE)

The semantic BM provides recommendations to improve energy efficiency and user comfort through utilizing real-time energy data and ambient information. The tool combines different control strategies into a unified coordinated framework that establishes an optimal balance between global control and individual comfort needs.

The module has two main features. The first one is detecting abnormal energy consumption via continuous monitoring. Abnormal energy consumption is detected by using machine learning techniques. The module utilizes measurements obtained from various indoor and outdoor sensors such as temperature, humidity, illuminance, air flow, CO₂, etc. The second feature is generating alerts and recommendations for avoiding occupant discomfort states. The module utilizes responses of questionnaires to identify occupant comfort levels and integrates this information to the recommendation rules.

In order to prepare and generate the model, it was necessary the participation of employees of Nanogune. For that purpose, GIR made the recruitment of volunteers to provide their feedback of the comfort parameters and environmental conditions of their workplace and thus correlate with the data collected by the sensors. To this end, paper surveys were prepared, which volunteers should fill in and send out manually every day. This system generated annoyance in the volunteers and the system of acquisition of surveys was changed with the objective of minimizing the work done by the volunteers and thus trying to attract more volunteers. For this, a web form was implemented, and the volunteers started to use it to provide their feedback, changing also the frequency of reporting to once a week. All the data provided by the volunteers were collected and stored in TEK servers. The BEMServer gathers the questionnaire data directly from TEK servers in order to make it available to the modules.

In addition to the surveys, different kind of elements were implemented and deployed for this module in Nanogune building.

TEK worked in the MM-WSN, which is an extension of TIBUCON sensor/actuators functionalities to adjust to pilot sites requirements. This wireless solution provides measurements of indoor temperature, humidity, luminosity and presence. All the information collected is sent to PLAT.ONE through MQTT.

A first deployment of 10 MM-WSN were carried out in order to test the performance the wireless connectivity range as well as the remote connection to PLAT.ONE. According to the results of the tests performed for 6 months, the functionality and configuration of the MM-WSN devices were reviewed and some functional corrections had to be implemented.

After these improvements, a total of 29 MM-WSN sensors were deployed in a second installation in order to collect indoor environmental and presence information that feed the module. The following figure shows the location of each sensor in Nanogune premises:

Figure 95: MM-WSN sensors deployed in Nanogune

The deployed network was continuously supervised in order to check its correct implementation as well as the availability of the collected data in PLAT.ONE. During this performance monitoring, a problem related to the battery efficiency management was detected. For this reason, some modifications in the MM-WSN sensors' firmware were carried on.

The 29 MM-WSN sensors were updated with this new firmware release and started again to collect indoor information.

On the other hand, EUR deployed an alternative solution to monitor occupancy, especially suited for large open office areas, based on indoor positioning. The technology is based on Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) and Wi-Fi communications. Although it could provide the accurate location of individuals inside the buildings on a specific floor (2D location) and trace their trajectory, it was used only for people counting in pre-defined areas. This information may be used for the comfort analysis of a specific zone, for instance, or for the purpose of identifying faults.

A total of 12 beacons were deployed in a collective office (271 m²) containing over 40 workplaces in an open space. The area was divided into 2 monitoring zones regarding the people counting.

Figure 96: Beacons and zones distribution of the indoor positioning system deployed in Nanogune

The system is composed by an app that has to be deployed in the users' smartphone, a configuration tool that helps in the deployment and set-up process, a back-end service that collects the data coming from the app and send them to PLAT.ONE and an occupancy module that calculates periodically (every minute) the number of people in each zone. The data is transmitted automatically from PLAT.ONE to HIT2GAP core platform (BEMServer). The module for occupancy calculation requests the data from the BEMServer and store the result in the BEMServer as well. The maintenance staff checks weekly that the system is working properly.

To minimize privacy concerns, the position is only transmitted when the user is inside the monitored area and relative coordinates related to the building shape are used (instead of global coordinates). Furthermore, areas such as the kitchenette/coffee area were excluded from the monitoring. The position is linked to the user with an id and the binding with the real user is not stored in HIT2GAP.

The main challenge was to engage people to participate. Only 9 volunteers were willing to participate and only after a face-to-face meeting explaining all the details and answering all their questions. In order to use effectively the indoor positioning system as occupancy calculator most of the users of the collective office should be participating. Another observed effect was that the users stopped using the app after a period. The reason for that was that they disconnected the app when they leave the building, and after a period they forgot to re-connect it again when they entered the building the next day. For long period campaigns, reminders should be provided periodically. In any case, the reason for disconnecting the app was energy demand. This reason can be minimized by improving the app and sending it to sleep mode when the user is not in the building. The system could run more efficiently if the app were deployed in the smartwatches instead of smartphones avoiding false positive caused by people leaving their smart phones on their desks. However, the penetration of this type of devices is not high enough yet.

4.2.3.1 *Testing methodology*

Data requirement of semantic BM are as follows:

- Energy consumption data
- Occupancy number and /or occupancy presence
- Weather condition data
- Indoor environmental data (temperature, relative humidity etc.)
- Occupancy comfort feedback

Above measurements are used to construct energy models as well as identifying user preferred neutral operative temperature which are required to generate recommendations and alerts for optimized energy consumption and increased occupant comfort. However, the following issues prevented to demonstrate the semantic BM at Nanogune pilot site:

1. Energy models are constructed based on occupancy information as well as weather and indoor environmental condition data. Occupancy sensor data was not available in a continuous way due to the various re-deployments of the MM-WSN sensors that have needed to be done, whereas indoor environmental data was not extractable for temperature, humidity, light level, etc. Additionally, weather data was not included in the database. Therefore, energy models which require these datasets could not be constructed.

2. Real-time energy consumption data through the platform was not available until June 2019 so Nanogune facility managers sent historical hourly electricity data between 05/04/2018 and 01/02/2019. Historical hourly thermal energy consumption data was available between 19/04/2018 and 05/04/2019. However, the module uses machine learning techniques and updates the models according to the real-time data. Therefore, static energy models were not adequate to run the model.
3. The questionnaires were sent weekly and there were 9 volunteers to respond the questionnaire. However, 7 of them responded and the fact that there was insufficient data, comfort analysis could not be conducted, and preferred neutral operative temperature could not be calculated.

4.2.4 Energy management (developed by ENE)

The Energy management (EM) module is for organizations that want to keep or acquire the ISO-50001 certification or that want to manage their energy consumption optimally.

The module is helping the EM and his team to capture and prioritize improvement opportunities. The software shows on their screen a list of improvement opportunities with a ranking according to the importance and the impact of the task. It has made the decisions of the EM team easier to take. The module is also helping the EM manage his team. Indeed, it automatically assigns actions with target dates and reminders to the energy team members so they can prioritize and assign to individuals within the team.

It is also helping the EM to manage reports. The EM is able to stock documents such as monthly energy reports or action status on the dashboard.

4.2.4.1 Testing methodology

The EM module's performance

Matching the ISO 50001 requirements, as depicted in the figure below, the performances of the EM visualization module cover two main functions.

- Energy Planning & Monitoring;
- ISO 50001 Management System.

Figure 97: operative menu

Energy Planning & Monitoring

Energy planning is the “Plan” part of the PDCA cycle of an ISO 50001 EnMS. Energy planning provides the foundation for developing an EnMS that is based on an understanding of an organization’s energy performance.

This is the step where the organization’s analysis of its energy data, along with other energy information is used to make informed decisions on actions to continually improve energy performance.

Within the HIT2GAP Energy Management visualization module, the “Energy Planning and Monitoring” section is divided into 2 main areas:

- Energy Performance, with 3 sub-functions: Energy Review, EnPI’s, Charts.
- Action Management, with 4 sub-functions: IOs, Plans, O&Ts, Charts.

Energy Performance: Energy Review

The energy review is the analytical part of the energy planning process. This function analyses both the energy sources and the identified significant energy uses within the building or location.

The Energy Review function in the HIT2GAP EM visualization module presents the data in the form of a Sankey diagram, linking the energy sources to the energy uses. The energy sources are typically identified from energy utility bills and/or energy audit reports. The energy uses are typically identified from energy audits and sub-meters.

Figure 98 shows the Sankey diagram for the energy consumption data.

Figure 98: Nanogune (Spain): energy consumption Sankey diagram

Energy Performance: EnPI

Energy Performance Indicators (EnPIs) and their corresponding energy baselines are metrics that are defined by the organization to measure energy performance. Types and examples of EnPIs include the following:

- energy consumption (in total or broken down by energy use) (e.g. kWh, GJ);
- simple ratio such as energy consumption per unit of output (e.g. kWh per tonne, kWh per man hour worked)
- statistical model (e.g. linear and nonlinear regression);
- engineering based model (e.g. simulation).

The EnPI function in the HIT2GAP EM visualization module allows the user to see a list of EnPIs configured for the location selected. The view displays the data for the previous month, as depicted in the below.

Figure 99: Nanogune (Spain): Defined EnPI functions

An EnPI can be at a facility, system, process or equipment level and should have an appropriate baseline at the same level for comparative purposes.

The user, clicking on a description text, is able to see the progress of the EnPI versus the established baselines over the previous months, as shown in the figure on the right side.

EnPI: Electricity 2018 vs 2015 (Baseline) (kWh/m²) - 2018

Figure 100: Nanogune (Spain): EnPI Total Electricity per Area

Energy Performance: Charts

As depicted in the following figure, the Charts function in the Energy Performance area includes a dashboard showing four default energy performance charts for the selected location. Other available charts can be selected by clicking on the “Change Chart” button.

Figure 101: Nanogune (Spain): Energy Performance Charts

Action Management: IOs

The identification of improvement opportunities (IOs) is an output from the energy review. There are also Improvement Opportunities triggered from other Modules delivered through the HIT2GAP platform. Having identified improvement opportunities, these IOs are prioritized based on criteria defined by the organisation (e.g. cost savings, capital cost, payback, complexity, impact on health & safety). The energy manager (and energy team) can review this list and decide what IOs should be included in the actions plans (see Plans function next).

With the HIT2GAP EM visualization module, the Improvement Opportunities (IOs) function displays the list of IOs including their category and their prioritization ranking if assessment has been completed.

Basically, IOs are visualized according to three basic categories:

- those that are still open (ongoing);
- those that need to be assessed before the successful completion;
- those that are considered into the Action Plan and contribute to the yearly budget.

Action Management: Plans

The organization establishes, implements and maintains action plans for achieving its objectives and targets. (ISO 50001).

The Plans function within the Action Management areas of the HIT2GAP EM visualization module shows what actions have been assigned to various people and the target dates for completing these actions. The user can also see easily what actions are overdue.

Figure 102: Nanogune (Spain): Action Plans

Action Management: O&Ts

ISO 50001 requires that objectives and targets including timeframes are defined to improve the energy performance of the organisation. The user can view overall targets set for the whole site, the targets set for different energy uses and targets and potential savings from different IOs.

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	kWh		Objective	Total(kWh)	Electrical(kWh)	Thermal(kWh)	
				Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date
Overall Objective: Reduce total energy by 2%				90000	899511	70000	79097
Energy Use Total & Targets	1370286			99250		93250	6000
Total Savings (Potential & To-Date) from Actions				1117738	899511	204097	79097
▶Boilers - CIC Nanogune	354160		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			0	0
▶Ground Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	285023		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	0.00
▶First Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	284104		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			750	0.00
▶Second Floor - CIC Nanogune	169560		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			12000	0.00
▶First Floor - CIC Nanogune	125101		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1600	74097
▶Basement Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	64831		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			18000	5000
▶Roof Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	39119		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			13000	0.00
▶Basement Clean Room - CIC Nanogune	19871		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			15000	0.00
▶Ground Floor - CIC Nanogune	14600		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	0.00
▶Fifth Floor Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	10607		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			26000	0
▶Basement Parking - CIC Nanogune	3310		Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1700	0.00

Figure 103: Nanogune (Spain): Objectives and Targets

While the bottom of the screen shows detailed information on the breakdown of electrical and thermal targets for individual energy uses and the potential energy savings (electrical and thermal) from identified IOs that have been included in the action plans.

This detailed view also summarises whether the overall target can be met based on the identified IOs or if further IOs need to be identified and actions included in the plans.

Action Management: Charts

The Charts function in the Action Management area includes a dashboard showing four default action management charts for the location selected. Other available charts can be selected by clicking on the “Change Chart” button.

Figure 104. Nanogune (Spain): Action Management Charts

ISO 50001 Management System

An EnMS is a framework by which an organization establishes processes to achieve control and improvement of energy performance – a systematic approach to energy management. Think of an EnMS as the umbrella under which those processes relate and interact.

An EnMS is often viewed as having two aspects: “Management” and “Technical”. In the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module, the “Energy Planning & Monitoring” area, described in the previous sections, are the technical aspects of the energy management system.

This section describes the ISO 50001 Management System or the management aspects of the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module.

The main function implemented is the “Planning” function, which includes six sub-functions: Doc, Audit, Mtg, NCs, Charts and Tasks.

ISO 50001 Management System: Doc

Within an ISO 50001 EnMS you are required to establish, implement and maintain information, in paper, electronic or any other medium, to describe the core elements of the EnMS and their interaction and that documents required by the standard are adequately controlled.

Within the HIT2GAP EM module, full document management functionality is available. The “Docs” function in the HIT2GAP EM Visualisation module allows the use to access and view documents related to the EnMS (see Figure 105).

Figure 105: Nanogune (Spain): Docs

Filters allow the user to find documents easily by different types, categories and sub-categories.

ISO 50001 Management System: Audit

An internal audit of an EnMS is an objective, systematic review of all or part of an organization's EnMS. The purpose of internal audits is to check that everyone is doing what is expected of them in relation to the requirements of your EnMS and specifically to:

- determine if the requirements are being met (if conformance to ISO 50001 is required);
- identify and drive improvements in energy performance and the EnMS.

The Audit function within the ISO 50001 Management System allows the user to view the full audit schedule at the top of the screen and more detailed view at the bottom of the screen including the start dates and end dates (see figure below).

Figure 106: Nanogune (Spain): Audits

ISO 50001 Management System: Meetings

The Meetings (“Mtg”) functions within the HIT2GAP Energy Management module, allows users to schedule and plan regular energy team and management review meetings. It allows actions to be created and managed from the outcomes of the meeting.

Within the HIT2GAP EM visualization module, the user can view the meetings and the outcome.

Figure 107: Nanogune (Spain): Meetings

Planning: NCs

Within the organizations of an EnMS, nonconformities (*NCs) should be corrected to ensure the effectiveness of the EnMS. NCs are usually highlighted as a result of an internal audit but can also be highlighted during routine operations.

Within the energy management module, NCs can be created and managed effectively allowing the energy manager to assign NCs to appropriate staff to identify the cause of the problem and to ensure that corrective and preventive actions are taken to prevent it happening again.

The NCs function in the HIT2GAP EM Visualization module allows users to see the list of open and closed NCs including completion dates and who has been assigned.

Figure 108: Nanogune (Spain): Non Conformities

Planning: Charts

The Charts function in the ISO 50001 Management System area includes a dashboard showing four default action management charts for the location selected. Other available charts can be selected by clicking on the “Change Chart” button.

Figure 109: Nanogune (Spain): Management System: Charts

4.2.4.2 Depth analysis of the key performance indicators results

Energy Performance Indicators (EnPI's)

The following list of EnPI's (Figure 110) are configured for the Nanogune Site (All are defined for a baseline year of 2016).

1. Electricity Consumption (kWh) per building area (m²)
2. Energy Consumption (kWh) per building area (m²)
3. Natural Gas Consumption (kWh) per building area (m²)

Figure 110: Nanogune (Spain): EnPI's

Figure 111: Nanogune (Spain): 2019 EnPI's

Figure 112: Nanogune (Spain): 2018 EnPI's

Figure 113: Nanogune (Spain): 2017 EnPI's

Energy Analysis (Sankey)

The Sankey diagram for each year is generated based on bill data manually entered to build the left side and metered data mapped against energy uses to build the right side. The energy consumption data is read directly on a nightly schedule from the HIT2GAP platform.

Figure 114: Nanogune (Spain): 2015-2018 Energy Flow Diagram's (Sankey's)

Objectives & Targets/Improvement Opportunities Implemented

The screenshots below show the year on year targeting of energy savings for each energy use identified for the site, what improvement opportunities were identified to meet those targets and the savings actually made.

	kWh	Objective	Total(kWh)		Electrical(kWh)		Thermal(kWh)	
			Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date
Overall Objective: Reduce total energy by 2%			90000	899511	70000	79097	20000	820414
Energy Use Total & Targets	1370286		99250		93250		6000	
Total Savings (Potential & To-Date) from Actions			1117738	899511	204097	79097	913641	820414
▼Boilers - CIC Nanogune	354160	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			0	0	6000	348609
■ 31/05/2019 - Installation of electric heaters					0	0	348609	348609
Total					0	0	348609	348609
▼Ground Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	285023	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼First Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	284104	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			750	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Second Floor - CIC Nanogune	169560	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			12000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼First Floor - CIC Nanogune	125101	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1600	74097	0	0
■ 24/05/2019 - Replacement of the BMS					125000	0	-	-
■ 31/05/2019 - Variable flow in HVAC first floor					74097	74097	-	-
Total					199097	74097	0	0
▼Basement Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	64831	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			18000	5000	0	0
■ 31/05/2019 - Installation of a heat exchanger for recovering heat from laboratories (basement)					5000	5000	-	-
Total					5000	5000	0	0
▼Roof Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	39119	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			13000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Basement Clean Room - CIC Nanogune	19871	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			15000	0.00	0	0.00

Figure 115: Nanogune (Spain): 2019 Objectives & Targets

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	kWh	Objective	Total(kWh)		Electrical(kWh)		Thermal(kWh)	
			Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date
Total	3738349					93250	237291	10000 9645
▼Fifth Floor Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	789366	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			26000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Roof Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	743483	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			13000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Basement Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	597340	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			18000	74097	0	0
■ 31/05/2018 - Variable flow in HVAC Basement 2					74097	74097	-	-
Total					74097	74097	0	0
▼Basement Clean Room - CIC Nanogune	481184	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			15000	74097	0	0
■ 31/05/2018 - Variable flow in HVAC Basement 1					74097	74097	-	-
Total					74097	74097	0	0
▼Second Floor - CIC Nanogune	472996	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			12000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Boilers - CIC Nanogune	293910	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			0	0	10000	9645
■ 31/05/2018 - Adjustment of the operating cascade of the boilers					9645	0	9645	9645
Total					9645	0	9645	9645
▼Ground Floor - CIC Nanogune	181722	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	74097	0	0
■ 31/05/2018 - Variable flow in HVAC ground floor					74097	74097	-	-
Total					74097	74097	0	0
▼Basement Parking - CIC Nanogune	75670	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1700	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Ground Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	43015	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼First Floor - CIC Nanogune	32473	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1600	10000	0	0
■ 24/05/2019 - Replacement of the BMS					125000	0	-	-
■ 19/04/2018 - Installation of a new energy manager system (EKIOM)					10000	10000	-	-

Figure 116: Nanogune (Spain): 2018 Objectives & Targets

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	kWh	Objective	Total(kWh)		Electrical(kWh)		Thermal(kWh)	
			Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date
Total	3977367					93250	149659	10000 35523
▼Fifth Floor Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	975470	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			26000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Basement Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	766187	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			18000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Roof Heating/Cooling - CIC Nanogune	616781	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			13000	44338	0	34523
■ 31/05/2017 - HVAC schedule reduction					44338	44338	34523	34523
Total					44338	44338	34523	34523
▼Second Floor - CIC Nanogune	576995	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			12000	59277	0	0
■ 31/05/2017 - Variable flow in HVAC gas room					59277	59277	-	-
Total					59277	59277	0	0
▼Basement Clean Room - CIC Nanogune	576364	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			15000	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Ground Floor - CIC Nanogune	244009	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	23022	0	0
■ 31/01/2017 - Replacement of the old lighting by LED illumination (Copy)					23022	23022	-	-
Total					23022	23022	0	0
▼Basement Parking - CIC Nanogune	83399	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1700	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Ground Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	54773	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2600	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼First Floor - CIC Nanogune	47891	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1600	23022	0	0
■ 31/01/2017 - Replacement of the old lighting by LED illumination					23022	23022	-	-
Total					23022	23022	0	0
▼First Floor Laboratories - CIC Nanogune	35498	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			750	0.00	0	0.00
Total					0	0	0	0
▼Boilers - CIC Nanogune	0	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			0	0	10000	10000

Figure 117: Nanogune (Spain): 2017 Objectives & Targets

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022			
		kWh	Objective			Total(kWh)		Electrical(kWh)		Thermal(kWh)	
				Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date	Target	To-Date		
Total			1429502			17750	17437	10000		0	
▼	Boilers - CIC Nanogune	529711	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			0	0.00	10000		0.00	
Total						0	0	0		0	
▼	Force consumption - CIC Nanogune	262399	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			5000	9500	0		0	
■	29/07/2016 - Installation of 2 meters					7500	7500	-		-	
■	30/09/2016 - Installation of 14 new electricity meters					2000	2000	-		-	
Total						9500	9500	0		0	
▼	Fifth Floor - CIC Nanogune	225382	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			4500	0.00	0		0.00	
Total						0	0	0		0	
▼	Cooling system - CIC Nanogune	187453	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			3750	7937	0		0	
■	31/05/2016 - Implementation of an energy saving programme based on the regulation of AHUs and distribution pumps.					7937	7937	-		-	
Total						7937	7937	0		0	
▼	Basement Usage - CIC Nanogune	140039	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			2800	0.00	0		0.00	
Total						0	0	0		0	
▼	Laboratories on first and main floor - CIC Nanogune	48930	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			1000	0.00	0		0.00	
Total						0	0	0		0	
▼	Lighting - CIC Nanogune	20727	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			400	0.00	0		0.00	
Total						0	0	0		0	
▼	Air consumption - CIC Nanogune	14861	Match overall target of 2% Saving per annum			300	0.00	0		0.00	
Total						0	0	0		0	

Figure 118: Nanogune (Spain): 2016 Objectives & Targets

Energy Savings

The charts below show a month by month comparison of energy consumption for a) the current year vs last year and b) last year vs the previous year.

Figure 119: Nanogune (Spain): Energy Consumption Charts

The table below gives an indication of the energy saved from year to year and how much of that energy saving came from improvement opportunities directly identified during the HIT2GAP project.

Table 20: Nanogune (Spain): Energy Savings from IO's vs Total Energy Saved

Savings from Improvement Opportunities identified					
	Natural Gas (kWh)	Electricity (kWh)	Total (kWh)	Actual Saving (kWh)	% from identified IO's
2019					
2018	9645	237291	246936	721807	34.20%
2017	35523	149659	185182	255254	72.50%
2016	0	17437	17437	409435	4.30%

4.2.5 Gap Reasoner (developed by FISE)

The GapReasoner module is based on building performance simulation (BPS) with uncertainty analysis (UA) and sensitivity analysis (SA). Making use of UA methods gives the user a more reliable simulation result, as input uncertainties are taken into account.

Additionally, the module provides methods for sensitivity analysis, which allows for determining the impact of varying input parameters on the output variation. More precisely, it is estimated whether, for example, the room temperature set value or the g-value of the windows is more influential for the energy consumption of a given building.

The module uses UA to provide results from building energy consumption simulation with additional upper and lower bands from uncertainties. Where a gap between simulated and measured energy consumption is found, SA is used to formulate messages to the user, which can help identifying reasons for an energy performance gap.

4.2.5.1 *Testing methodology*

The underlying building simulation model has been created by the module provider according to building and system documentations of the addressed site. The module is configured by the module provider, e.g. by selecting a set of parameters which are likely to influence the building energy consumption.

Following aspects of the module are tested:

1. Comparison of measured and simulated building energy consumption with uncertainties
2. Listing of time ranges, which show a high gap between simulation and measurement
3. Listing of most influential parameters on the simulation results for the selected time ranges, indicating possible reasons for the gap.

4.2.5.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

The used simulation model needs to be calibrated in order to get feasible results for a building site. Because of issues with the data gathering procedure for the nanoGUNE site, the needed data could not be processed to be regarded in this report. Nonetheless, an energy performance simulation for the site has been performed based on the data available on the platform and the results could be uploaded to the Facility Management Visualization module (see below). While these results are not fully in line with the measurement data, the general trends are already reflected. The major discrepancy in February 2019 can be explained with a data gap in January 2019. As noted before, using the calibration mechanisms of the module should further improve this. Initial comparisons of the simulation with measurement data showed a discrepancy of two orders of magnitude as well as a lack of similar monthly patterns. This revealed a wrong configuration of the data gathering procedures used for the site. While this is not the major use case of the module, it already shows the benefit of such comparisons between measurement and simulation data.

Figure 120: Nanogune (Spain): Comparison of Simulated (blue) and Measured (black) Energy Consumption in the FM Visualization

Figure 121: Nanogune (Spain): Measured Energy Consumption of Air Based Systems in the FM Visualizations

4.2.5.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

Possible improvements of the module: Up to now the user interface is solely based on the FM Visualization module. While initial implementations for configuring the simulation module exist, these are not ready for use yet. Also, since the simulation model has to be provided by a simulation environment, these models tend to be complex and hard to understand. The underlying assumptions on nominal values etc. should best be made available to the end user and possibly in an editable fashion.

4.3 Gap evaluation

In the beginning of the project, the gap between the estimated in the design phase and the actual energy consumption of Nanogune was assessed. In the design phase, energy consumption of the building was estimated through CE3X program. The following table summarises the initial state of the gap in Nanogune:

Table 21: Gap evaluation 2015

	BASELINE CE3X	2015
Total Electricity (kWh*y)	756.445	3.973.000
Total Gas (kWh*y)	963.260	1.770.275
Total Electricity (kWh/m2*y)	129	543
Total Gas (kWh/m2*y)	164	242
Total Base Year Energy (kWh/m2*y)	293	785
Area of Building (m ²)	5862	7319
Electric GAP (%)	320,9	
Gas GAP (%)	47,6	

The baseline was calculated using the habitable area and not the whole surface of the building, that is to say 5862 m² instead of 7319 m². Therefore, in order to evaluate the energy performance gap, the energy per square meter per year has been calculated for the designed values and the real measured values.

It must be considered that, for estimating the energy consumption of a building, the CE3X program does not take into account computers, data centre servers, laboratory equipment... Furthermore, for energy consumption simulations of CE3X only consider five working days with twelve hours per day. However, this does not match reality since researchers have 24/7 access to the facilities.

This energy gap has been significantly reduced during the period of the project. The following table shows the savings in energy consumption made over the duration of the project:

Table 22: Energy consumption and savings obtained during 2015-2018

	Natural Gas (kWh)	Electricity (kWh)	Total (kWh)	Actual Saving (kWh)
2018	855483	3501296	4356779	
	-36%	-6.40%	-14.20%	721807
2017	1337348	3741238	5078586	
	-2.70%	-5.50%	-4.80%	255254
2016	1374707	3959133	5333840	
	-22%	-0.30%	-7.10%	409435
2015	1770275	3973000	5743275	

It has been verified that actions performed jointly with the facility manager had a positive impact in the reduction of the energy gap. This way, the targets set by the facility manager were fulfilled during the project.

The following table summarises the final state of the gap in Nanogune after HIT2GAP project:

Table 23: Gap evaluation 2018

	BASELINE CE3X	2018
Total Electricity (kWh*y)	756.445	3.501.296
Total Gas (kWh*y)	963.260	855.483
Total Electricity (kWh/m2*y)	129	478
Total Gas (kWh/m2*y)	164	117
Total Base Year Energy (kWh/m2*y)	293	595
Area of Building (m ²)	5862	7319
Electric GAP (%)	270,5	
Gas GAP (%)	-28,3	

In Nanogune, there has been a reduction of 16% in the electric GAP and 159% in the gas GAP, thus achieving the objectives set at the beginning of the project.

Nevertheless, it must be remembered that the goal is not directly to consume less but to consume efficiently. A solution like BEMServer offers the necessary tools to the facility manager for achieving an efficient consumption and having a full control of the facilities; by visualizing disaggregated energy uses, forecasting the consumption, detecting faults automatically, calculating optimal comfort parameter, etc.

4.4 Lessons learnt during the operation

An energy management software needs data to work and communication is essential to be able to collect data. In Nanogune, in order to communicate the installation, all the meters had to be configured to communicate with a new server. This process has been complicated and represents a considerable investment.

The good thing about BEMServer is that it can provide adapted solution for each situation. An alternative solution could be to extract data manually from the heat meters and uploaded it to BEMServer manually. Another solution could be to reduce the number of meters. However, during the operation it has been proven that the more disaggregated data, the better the analysis of the installation will be.

Finally, it must be mentioned the difficulties encountered in attracting participants. Out of 50 users of the area of study only 9 agreed to participate. It could be convenient to offer some kind of benefit to users to attract them.

5 National University of Galway (Ireland)

The National University of Galway (NUIG) pilot is conducted in three representative spaces of the Alice Perry Engineering Building (Figure 122). The building features exposed construction techniques and an array of ecological building methods making it an excellent testbed for HIT2GAP. It is a recipient of several awards (architecture, innovation) and like many university buildings includes spaces for offices, lecture halls, conference rooms, research laboratories, common open areas. In this sense, it is a suitable and replicable example for offices, educational and other public buildings. Partner CYLON provided the hardware used in the building's BMS system (during the building's initial construction phase), facilitating interoperability and data access. Overall, the four story 14250m² structure has 400 rooms and accommodates 1100 students and 110 staff.

Figure 122. NUIG Alice Perry Engineering Building

5.1 Use cases

The selected rooms/areas for the NUIG pilot are shown in Figure 123 and Figure 124 and are:

Rooms n. 2053 and 3053 - post grad areas

- Two large open spaces offices for researchers
- Automatic openable windows
- Solar shading blinds integrated into double skin façade

Rooms n. 2016 and 2017 - computer labs

- Two rooms for lectures equipped with computers
- Automatic openable windows, chilled beams, high internal heat gains

Room n. G047 - lecture theatre 3

- Lecture theatre for didactic activities and public events
- Dedicated mechanical ventilation systems with floor diffusers beneath each seat

These areas were selected because they are interesting, representative of many other spaces in the building and on campus and their size and complexity were manageable within the scope of the project.

Figure 123. Photos of the NUIG Pilot spaces (left to right: open space study area, computer lab and lecture theatre)

Figure 124. NUIG Pilot selected rooms on plan layout.

HIT2GAP Testing Scenarios

In conjunction with the core platform, the following modules have been tested in the pilot site:

- Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis
- Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (Machine Learning based)
- Load Forecasting Module
- ModSCO – Simulation module
- ESP-r Simulation Module
- BIM visualisation module

Table 24: List of modules deployed and tested in the Polish pilot site and main expectations

Module Name	App	Partner	Objective of the demonstration/ expected impact
Fault Detection and Diagnosis Modules	FDD-PCA	UDG	• Detect misbehaviours/faults.
	FDD-ML	FISE	• Detect misbehaviours/faults.
Load Forecasting	Load Forecasting	UDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecast power consumption in building or zones of a building. • Improve prediction for reactive actions, energy baseline. • Demonstrate the integration of forecasting tools in a platform such as HIT2GAP.
Building Performance Simulation Modules	ESP-r	UOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of reasons for performance gap and recommendations. • Energy and comfort assessment of improvement measures. • Giving easy access to a detailed dynamic energy simulation models of the building.
	ModSCO	NUIG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of reasons for performance gap and recommendations. • Energy and comfort assessment of improvement measures. • Making available a tool to perform dynamic energy simulation in fast way.
Visualisation Modules	BIM Visualisation	ZUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D visualization of real-time building performance indicators.

In developing the testing campaign for these HIT2GAP solutions, the following points were considered

- Representative rooms and systems, which can be significative for the whole building and of other possible cases
- Overall energy demand, considering some main uses
- Comfort and energy performance aspects
- Capabilities for visualization of data, features and components
- Opportunities for facility management and maintenance

Stakeholders Involved

The pilot involved the following stakeholders:

- Build Owner/End User: NUIG represented by staff and students who own and use the building
- Facility manager: A facility management company named Kingfisher who owns and operates the building
- Engineering Company / ESCO: Partner R2M who is acting in collaboration with partner Cylon as pilot manager
- BMS Provider: Partner Cylon who provided hardware for the Alice Perry building and is continually innovating and upgrading its products and services.
- Researchers/Students: Persons directly involved and interested in the pilot and scientific outcomes

Approach and Methodology

Overall, the NUIG pilot was selected because it is a modern building with advanced and efficiency plants, systems and construction techniques, it was equipped with a BMS, and the researchers involved work directly in building simulation and energy efficiency. Noteworthy, the BMS provider (Cylon) was engaged directly in the project hence there could be no problems with data or interoperability. Clearly, this pilot would run itself. Partner R2M became engaged as co-pilot manager to have the opportunity to directly work with (hands on) the H2G solution in order to assess the feasibility of launching it into its sustainability consulting services typically centered around buildings sustainability certifications (LEED) and where data must now be reported back to USGBC monthly.

Despite the team around this pilot, it initially suffered delays related to setup and configuration. The problem was that despite the fact that the BMS was CYLON, it was not clear what sensors belonged to what measurement points in the BMS. The exact history is not reported here but in a general way and applicable to many (or most) buildings, a construction company builds the building, they use subcontractors, and then once commissioned, end users or facility managers operate the building. During these processes and over time, different naming conventions may be applied to the same sets of sensors. People implementing their own routines or carrying out their own interests may make partial "fixes" and the institutional knowledge of what is where becomes lost. In total, the Alice Perry BMS has some 2600 measurement points. At first, establishing the baseline of who had what knowledge, which set of documentation was current from various available sets, and how to select and make accurate/useable for H2G purpose a specific set of rooms and their corresponding sensors was a significant blocking point.

To overcome this, R2M, CYLON and NUIG performed a detailed review and analysis of the variables measured and logged by the BMS. We reviewed all the available data, considering the documentations from the design stage and with checks thanks to queries in the source database and thanks to checks in field about energy meters names and location, rooms and systems components and loops. This effort spanned 1-2 months and in general we had access to persons with institutional knowledge (which may not be the case for a structure with a longer operational history). We started from the whole set of variables available from the BMS for a total of more than 1900 variables from the several datapoints. We then selected 364 variables suitable for the HIT2GAP tests and analysis.

From this process, we completed a clear and comprehensive list of names for all the measured variables, the considered rooms and spaces, the systems branches and components. We then defined unique names for the selected rooms with clear correspondence to the names currently used in the building. Subsequently, we used the same names also for the tested modules and particularly for the Zutec BIM-visualization module. The final names we defined associated with the 364 measurements each associate with one of following in their string names:

- 2016 Computer Lab
- 2017 Computer Lab
- 2053 Post Grad Area
- 3053 Post Grad Area
- G047 Lecture Theatre 3
- 2052 Seminar Room
- 3052 Boardroom.

These represents a wide set of variables which have been pushed onto the core-platform and used for modules implementation and the other analysis useful for the project. Moreover, these actions provide a relevant opportunity to exploit the large number of variables made available by the BMS

(for 3rd party applications such as H2G). This is valid specifically for the pilot site but also in general for any situation like this, where a large building is equipped by a comprehensive BMS.

Once identified, selected and named, a data pushing procedure was necessary to make historical information available into the HIT2GAP/BEMServer platform. This process and related information exchanges have been guided thanks to a specific template provided by NBK. For this pilot, we implemented and tested a direct connection between the database, gathering data from the BMS, and the HIT2GAP core platform. This pushing procedure to upload the selected measured variables has been managed directly by CYLON, from the BMS and source database side, and by NBK, from the core-platform / BEMServer side.

The source database gathers measured data from the BMS and from a third-party smaller system, based on wi-fi: it's called BuildAX and it has been installed by the ESRU-UOS team in the HIT2GAP framework. The BuildAX system consists in a datalogger which gathered data via a wi-fi communication from several small sensors installed in the selected rooms. These sensors measure temperature, relative humidity, light level (illuminance) and other variables. They represent a cheap system to perform indoor environmental monitoring campaign. With the deployment of the BuildAX sensors, we gathered information useful for the ESP-r energy simulation module and we also tested the integration of wireless third-party sensors like the BuildAX ones.

In the following figure, we can see the connection scheme between the BMS components (bottom part of the figure) and the BuildAX system (upper left) on field to the core-platform of the BEMServer, via the source database (gathering data) from the systems and via the proper pushing API (action as simple informatic bridge from the database to the core-platform).

Figure 125. Scheme of the solution deployed to connect the components in field in the BMS and BuildAX sensor, to the source database and to the HIT2GAP core platform - BEMServer.

In addition, some settings have been performed from the informatic point of view. Settings have been applied from the core-platform side and from the source database side, in order to make regularly available all the selected data in the selected historical periods (generally since 1/1/2017). This also allowed us to optimize our procedures and the time required to send datasets.

These preliminary actions were performed by the team in charge of the core-platform management (NBK) and by the team in charge of the source database directly linked with the BMS (CYLON) with the coordination of the pilot-site manager (R2M) - about information exchange and communication between the two teams. These actions and roles could be representing of a typical deployment of the BEMServer (core-platform) and related modules to further buildings with BMS installed. We saw that some time is needed for the first pushing of historical data related to long periods (e.g. 1 or 2 years in the past). The required time depends on different aspects (web connection, database features, etc.). In our case, this required about 2 days for each of the 3 data groups in which we divided all the selected data. Actions were performed from ICT point of view at the database and at the core platform side in order to optimize the pushing procedure.

This initialization process has been required only once. Afterwards, double checks of data values and availability have been performed by comparison with values from direct queries in the source database and from the software tool Active Energy Manager by Cylon. These checks showed that the initial data pushing procedure was successfully completed and continues working well in its routine data pushing procedure with all the selected variables being regularly available (updated) on the core-platform. This process is automatic without any required actions.

Updates and periodical checks have been performed about data available and access to the module on the core platform. These showed satisfactory feedbacks and behaviours.

An additional module has been implemented in the core platform as plugin for the data visualization. It allows to visualize all the available data, creating graphs in easy and fast way. This functionality is very useful for all the pilot site.

5.2 Running of HIT2GAP in the pilot

This section details the different scenarios used to evaluate the effect brought by the HIT2GAP solutions on the Irish demonstration site.

5.2.1 Load Forecasting (developed by UDG)

The load forecasting module allows energy managers or other users to forecast the power consumption by usage (lighting, plug load, ventilation etc.) and by building or zone of the building using various time windows. Particularly for the pilot site in Galway, it has been used to perform forecasting of daily values of the energy demand related to three different meters, which are relevant for the building and in general as exemplary application of the module.

Forecasts have been provided for 1 to 3 following days.

5.2.1.1 Testing methodology

We reviewed all the installed energy meters which provide measurements to the source database and to the BEMServer. Many energy meters are installed in the buildings and they cover different energy uses (e.g. space heating, space cooling, domestic hot water preparation, electrical appliances, etc.) and different energy carriers (like gas and electricity). Mainly, meters related to the whole buildings and whole systems are available, while sub-meters or meters for specific systems components are not available (e.g. for coils of single air handling units). Regardless, a relevant and wide set of energy meters were available to test the Load Forecasting Module.

Three meters were selected for their relevance, data availability and completeness, and seasonality (cooling, heating, and domestic hot water needs covered). We considered the daily measured values. The three selected meters were:

RADIATORS OF WEST ZONES OF THE BUILDING - THERMAL ENERGY METER

code: `_West_Rads_Energy_`

This meter measures thermal energy for heating provided to the radiators of the west zones of the building. Figure 126 depicts a screenshot taken by the BMS interface (as an example) representing thermal power [kW] delivered to the west zone radiators in March 2019. We could recognize a typical daily trend for the heating season.

Figure 126. Example of thermal power values measured by the meters related to the west zone radiators - March-2019.

CHILLER ELECTRICAL METER - code: `_EM_008_Chiller_Elec_`

This meter measures the daily electrical energy demand [kWh/day] for the installed chiller, that produces cool for all cooling uses in the building. Figure 127 depicts a graph taken by the BMS interface representing daily energy consumption of the electrical chiller installed boilers in the period from April 2017 to February 2019.

Figure 127. Example of daily values measured by the meters for the electrical chiller - period Apr-2017 / Feb-2019.

GAS BOILERS METER - code: *_MR_GM_001_Gas_Boilers_*

This meter provides the gas demand per day [m³/day] for the two gas boilers installed. It covers demand for heating and hot water uses. In parallel, a third boiler (biomass) and a combined heat and power unit work, probably covering the base heating demand.

Figure 128 presents a graph taken by the BMS interface representing daily energy consumption of gas for the 2 installed boilers in the period from April 2017 to February 2019.

Figure 128. Example of daily values measured by the gas meters for the two installed boilers - period Apr-2017 / Feb-2019.

With support of UDG, first the Load Forecasting Module has been used in modelling mode, in order to develop suitable forecasting models for each considered meter. Historical data from the same meters have been given as input to the module, that provided automatically the forecasting models. They were saved in the module and they can be exported and downloaded, using the module interface.

Historical data from past periods of duration from 1 to 3 or more months have been used. Since we selected to have a forecast of daily values, data from the past have to be provided daily aggregated so the daily value summations have been considered for the test of the module.

Then the models have been launched using the module in the simulation-forecasting mode. So, daily value results have been generated for forecasting windows of 1 or 3 days in the future. Results can be visualized directly in the module interface and related files can be downloaded and exported. Actions considered in the test scenario for this module have been completed with positive results and feedbacks.

RADIATORS OF WEST ZONES OF THE BUILDING - THERMAL ENERGY METER

A forecasting model has been built using data from 2/1/2019 to 1/4/2019. This period corresponds to part of the heating season in Galway, so the related equipment is working.

Features of the forecasting model include:

ANN, forecasted variable: daily consumption for the three following days, autoregressive model (windowing = 3), independent variables: holidays, outside temperature and humidity, weekday. MAPE = 9%.

Using the same training set of data for testing the model, the mean absolute percentage error between the forecasted consumption and the real consumption MAPE = 12% is obtained. This is lower than the 20% considered as maximum limit for the tests. Figure 129 shows the real and forecasted consumptions for the period 2/1/2019 - 1/4/2019.

Figure 129. Daily forecasted and real values for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, 2/1/19-1/4/19.

Another test performed to forecast consumption during April 2019 shows the next results. The performance of the forecasting model for April 2019 is worse mainly due to the fact that the weather is becoming warmer (from May 1st the consumption is reduced to almost 0).

Figure 130. Daily forecasted and real values for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, April 2019

A third test was performed to forecast consumption for a previous period, from 19/11/2018 to 23/12/2019. The performance of the forecasting model is better (MAPE = 0,7%) due to the fact that the weather conditions are similar to the existing ones for which the model was created.

Figure 131. Daily forecasted and real values for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, 19/11/18-23/12/19.

CHILLER ELECTRICAL METER

Available data: 01/01/2017 – Up to present date. However, weather data is available from 17/4/2018, so only electricity meter data gathered from this date can be used. The forecasting model is built considering that the equipment is working, then the time period for modelling is 29/5/2018 – 11/7/2018.

Features of the forecasting model:

ANN, forecasted variable: daily consumption for the three following days, autoregressive model (windowing = 1), independent variables: holidays, outside temperature, weekday.

Figure 132. Daily forecasted and real values for chiller electrical meter, 29/5/18-11/7/18.

The accuracy of the forecasting model is very low for non-working days (few observations, one of the occurs June 24th, when the system was off). For working days, MAPE is around 16%.

GAS BOILERS METER

Available data: 01/01/2017 - Up to present date. However, weather data is available from 17/4/2018, so only gas meter data gathered from this date can be used.

Period time for modelling: 28/9/2018 – 30/4/2019.

In the considered test, the forecast model has been developed mainly in function of the outdoor air temperature. We have to consider that in the modelling period for the forecasts about the gas meter for boilers, the daily gas demand is not well correlated to the daily average value of the outdoor air temperature, as we can see in the graph here below. Probably this is due to the fact that the boilers are not only used for pure space heating (which is generally well correlated to the outdoor air temperature) but also for other uses like heat for coils in air handling unit (for example this could depend also on the dehumidification needs and on the moist air transformations in air handling units), domestic hot water, heat for other process in the building (for example for processes in research laboratories).

As a result of modelling, in this case forecasting models have very low accuracy.

Figure 133. Daily gas consumption for boilers (grey line) vs. outdoor air temperature (black dashed), 28/9/18-30/4/19.

5.2.1.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

The results from the load forecasting module show a good level of accuracy in the forecasted trends shape and in values. We can see this particularly when suitable periods are considered for models development and for forecasting.

The forecasts can be useful for facility managers and energy managers in order to support their decisions for avoiding to overcome energy and/or power demand they can put by the contracts with utility companies or by other needs related to technical features of systems and components.

So, basing on forecasts facility managers could decide to pay attention to the operation of the related components and they could decide to limit peak power or time of operation.

Forecasts could be useful also to plan certain maintenance interventions, in specific days when the forecasts indicate low energy demand and so lower issue in case of interventions to change or repair come components.

Forecasts could be also useful to improve the management of load (energy demand in the building) and the generation from renewables system installed, in order to maximize the match between them.

- Forecasting future consumption can help FM to avoid violating the threshold energy peak of the building which can be highly beneficial financially because the price of energy is different for different energy consumption level. The module gives the opportunity to FMs to keep the building at low-tariff energy region where they can also benefit from bonus provided by energy suppliers for low-energy consumers. This could be valid for each energy carrier used in the building.
- By using the Module, FMs have the opportunity to predict the peak demand period. As an illustration, the Figure 134 compares both real and forecasted energy consumptions for EnC_West_Rads_Energy_D14_134 datalog during 2/1/2019 to 1/4/2019 period. As it can be seen, there is peak demand on certain days of Feb 2019 which could be predicted by Load Forecasting module. The Figure 136 shows another sampling from the same datalog implemented for April 2019. As it can be seen, the demand peaks between the 1st to 14th of April could be predicted which were closely matched the real data. In order to further verify the results, both trends have been validated by Cylon Active Energy platform (Figure 135 and Figure 137).

Figure 134. Daily forecasted and real values for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, 2/1/19-1/4/19.

Figure 135. Daily measured values from the BMS for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, Jan-Mar '19.

Figure 136. Daily forecasted and real values for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, Apr '19.

Figure 137. Daily measured values from the BMS for thermal energy delivered to the west zones radiators, Apr '19.

Comparing the forecasted and real data for EnC_West_Rads_Energy_D14_134 datalog: during 2/1/2019 to 1/4/2019 period where the data was validated by Cylon Active Energy and also for April 2019 which was also validated by Cylon Active Energy

- By using the Module, FMs have the opportunity to be prepared to partially or completely switch off/on some equipment and facilities of the building to manage the energy level during the peak demand period
- In the case of using renewable resources in the building, FM can use the forecasted energy data to design an optimised/economical renewable energy system (PV, wind turbine, etc) for building.
- By forecasting the load and energy demand, FMs would have also the knowledge to decide and apply repair/maintenance to their systems during the best time/period when the energy demand is very low (e.g. at NUIG, FMs are running repairs during summer when the least number of people are in the site and the energy demand is very low)
- Since the focused building at NUIG is relatively big (and its BMS features might be extended even to other buildings at NUIG, in part already equipped with BMSs) its consumed energy can have an impact on the grid energy level. Therefore, apart from the local (microscopic impact), load forecasting has also positive macroscopic impacts on energy systems. All scenarios of load forecasting (including short, medium and long terms) can help utility companies (as well as electrical generating and distributing companies) to enhance their efficiency, revenue, management and operational methods in supplying the required energy uninterruptedly and economically with high reliability meeting the demand.
- Load forecasting also enables them to plan and have understanding of future load demand and consumption to avoid under generation or over generation.

- It minimizes the risks and helps the company to plan and make suitable decisions regarding to future generation and transmission investment. It also helps to determine the required fuel resources to generate energy.
- Load forecasting also helps in planning the size, location and type of the future power plants in the regions with high/growing demands to generate the energy close the load and reduce energy transmission losses/costs.
- Short Term load forecasting (less than a week) can deal with energy objective such as Economic Load Dispatch, Load Scheduling, System Security Assessment and Reliability Studies
- Medium Term load forecasting (1 to 10 weeks) can be used for Determining Peak Load, Commissioning and Development of Power System Infrastructure.
- Going over the building / district level, the following points should be considered:
 - Load forecasting allows to create an energy consumption baseline to assess the impact of implemented energy saving measures
 - In a larger context the Load Forecasting module can support forecasting analysis giving results from the scale of single buildings or of groups of buildings
 - Purchasing, managing daily load demand, producing, transmitting and distributing energy require all short, medium and long term load forecasting methods.
 - For managing and maintaining the power sources short term load forecasting is required.
 - Financial and marketing aspects of energy require medium and long term load forecasting.

5.2.1.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

The module has been provided with a complete structure, where all the functionalities were made available.

Some bugs related to access to the module from the core platform BEMServer were solved. The access is regular and easy.

Also basing on a deep exchange of questions and feedbacks between pilot site managers and the module developers, user guide documentation has been developed and completed, making it comprehensive and clear.

5.2.2 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (developed by UDG)

The Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis (FDD-PCA) module detects abnormal consumptions of electricity in a building, due to failures or malfunctions deteriorating its energy performance. The abnormal behavior is detected intelligently using the historical data of the different meters as well as influence variables such as weather and indoor environmental data.

5.2.2.1 *Testing methodology*

In order to test and reach useful results from the FDD-PCA module we selected parts of systems and buildings suitable to be interesting and replicable use cases for the module. For this, we focused on the air handling unit AHU101 and the related served room G047 - Lecture Theatre 3. They represent an interesting and replicable example specifically for the other AHUs installed in the pilot site building and in general for other buildings with AHUs.

The selected AHU101 is a typical air handling unit with supply and return fans, with coils for pre-heating, cooling / dehumidification and post-heating coils supplied by hot and cold water, with heat recovery device. Figure 138 and Figure 139 depict the schemes, components and sensors in the AHU101 and in the served room G047.

The same AHU and room have been selected for the application of other modules as FDD-ML, ModSCO, Zutec BIM visualization module. In this way, comparisons can be developed and comprehensive tests and adoption of the BEMServer modules were able to be considered and demonstrated.

Figure 138. Scheme of the AHU with components, sensors installed and the main variables for controls.

Figure 139. Scheme of the AHU with components, sensors installed and the main variables for controls.

After studying the user guide and with the support of the UDG team, a suitable model has been developed for the selected air handling unit and room. For this purpose, the FDD-PCA module in modelling mode was utilized and allowed us to develop the model we are using for test and application activities.

As input for the model development, a set of measured data from sensors installed in the AHU101 and in the served room G047 has been used. Measured values of the following variables for a period of 1 year (from April 2018 to April 2019) have been considered. Although a good set of data was available, in general shorter periods could be used to develop the module.

The time-step of the analysis is one hour (60 minutes) and the variables, listed here below, are used in the model and analysis:

1. 'AHU101_Ctrls_117_Lecture_Theatre_3_Av_Humidity_D28_482'
2. 'AHU101_Ctrls_AHU101_Calc_Supply_Setpt_D22_470'
3. 'AHU101_Ctrls_AHU101_SAF_VSD_Speed_D17_473'
4. 'AHU101_Ctrls_CO_147_1_Lecture_Theatre_3_CO2_D10_462'
5. 'AHU101_Ctrls_CO_147_2_Lecture_Theatre_3_CO2_D7_466'
6. 'AHU101_Ctrls_GF_East_Rads_Energy_Acc_Total_D2_483'
7. 'AHU101_Ctrls_HE_101_1_Return_Duct_Humidity_D13_458'
8. 'AHU101_Ctrls_HE_147_1_Lecture_Theatre_3_Humidity_D12_456'
9. 'AHU101_Ctrls_HE_147_2_Lecture_Theatre_3_Humidity_D9_464'
10. 'AHU101_Ctrls_Lecture_Theatre_3_Avg_CO2_D26_481'
11. 'AHU101_Ctrls_Lecture_Theatre_3_Avg_Temp_D19_477'
12. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TCV_101_3_Frost_Coil_HVAlve_D14_471'
13. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_101_1_Frost_Coil_Temp_D3_463'
14. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_101_2_Supply_Duct_Temp_D4_472'
15. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_101_3_Cooling_Off_Coil_Temp_D5_478'

16. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_101_4_Return_Duct_Temp_D20_474'
17. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_102_2_Cooling_Off_Coil_Temp_D6_459'
18. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_147_1_Lecture_Theatre_3_Temp_D11_469'
19. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_147_2_Lecture_Theatre_3_Temp_D8_465'
20. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_2_GFC4_1_Riser_3_Flow_Temp_D27_457'
21. 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_2_GFC4_2_Riser_3_Return_Temp_D30_460'

These variables represent typical datapoints for an AHU and the related served room. We also considered as input also information about working and not-working days in the considered periods.

The module received the input data automatically from the core-platform BEMServer, for model development and for the fault detection operation.

Features of the statistical model developed include:

- Days included in the model: 344
- 22 variables (including holidays)
- 26 Principal Components (Kaiser method)

Using these measurement points and features, the FDD-PCA module developed the related statistical model suitable to be used for the faults detection of the considered system, during the test and application actions.

Figure 140 and Figure 141 show two examples of visualizations and graphs from the FDD-PCA module in modelling mode.

Figure 140. Example of interface of the FDD-PCA module in modelling mode.

Figure 141. Example of a visualization option for the variables correlation in the FDD-PCA module in modelling mode.

The module interface allows to download files of the developed models, of results, and of input data. We used these functionalities both for results checks and visualization both for tests procedures. After the model development, the FDD-PCA module was launched in monitoring mode, so the test and use phase was opened and faults could be recognized and detected as abnormal behaviour of the considered variables. We consider and analysed results related to the different periods. We checked and deepened the results also thanks to idea exchanges with the facility managers and also with parallel data analysis directly from the source-database, using the Active Energy Manager software by Cylon. In general, the FDD-PCA module allowed us to detected real faults, which has been confirmed by the facility manager's knowledge of the installed systems and typical faults or by the data comparison with Active Energy Manager by Cylon. So, the innovative and automatic way to monitor and recognize faults using the H2G platform has been confirmed by more traditional methods, like data trends analysis. The automatic method, made available by the FDD-PCA module, of course allows for a continuous monitoring of possible faults and abnormal behaviour of the considered system.

Figure 142. Example of interface of the FDD-PCA module in monitoring mode.

We performed a first test in order to pre-check the related models under development. In this phase, we applied the FDD-PCA module in some days (working days and holidays) in January, February and March 2019. The module worked properly, and the developed model gave good results. We used these first tests to have feedbacks in order to check and improve the model and to get familiarity with the module.

Figure 143, Figure 144, and Figure 145 depict examples of graphs presenting the results for the day 1/2/2019. In each graph, all the considered variables are listed and considered in the order written listed in the beginning of this chapter. The method detects not only variations normality (e.g. larger values over 3 sigma), but also variations in the correlation among variables. For example, when normality means that two variables increase, the system detects when one of them increases and the other remains constant or decrease for example.

In Figure 143 significant magnitude faults (red bars) occurred after the cooling coil where abnormal values were detected for the air temperature sensors, measuring the following variable:
 - 'AHU101_Ctrls_TE_102_2_Cooling_Off_Coil_Temp_D6_459'.

The graph in Figure 144 shows red bars for correlation faults related to the following variables:
 - 'AHU101_Ctrls_AHU101_SAF_VSD_Speed_D17_473'
 - 'AHU101_Ctrls_CO_147_1_Lecture_Theatre_3_CO2_D10_462'
 - 'AHU101_Ctrls_HE_147_2_Lecture_Theatre_3_Humidity_D9_464'
 They respectively represent the speed of the supply air fan, the CO2 concentration and air relative humidity measured in two different point in the room.

Facility managers verified these conditions, which for that days represented only temporary abnormal values due to no typical changes in occupancy and non-typical changes in the AHU operation, but not to broken devices or constant faults.

Figure 143. Example of results visualization in the FDD-PCA module, where red bars corresponds to faults (magnitude faults T2) occurred during the day 1/2/2019.

Figure 144. Example of results visualization in the FDD-PCA module, where red bars corresponds to faults (correlation faults Q) occurred during the day 1/2/2019.

Figure 145. Example of results visualization in the FDD-PCA module, day 1/2/2019, where, for each of the considered variables, green line represents typical / correct values and trends (minimum, median, maximum), red lines represent the actual trend.

Here below several performed test rounds are listed.

Results of tests about period 6-10/5/2019: comparison with Active Energy Manager software by Cylon, for explanations and verification

Results of tests about period 6-29/5/2019: comparison with Active Energy Manager software by Cylon, for explanations and verification

Checks and comments with real data BMS and ActiveEnergy: ideas exchanges with the FMs

Test procedures "T1_" artificial faults changing values in input data file

Test procedures "T2_" artificial faults acting on field

About T2_, we proposed some actions representing artificial faults on field to be performed by the facility managers in Galway. Actions are under completion in the field.

About T1_, several modifications have been provoked to the Reference data. In particular modifications have been applied to two dates that were considered correct in the previous test: 10/05/2017 and 12/05/2017.

Analysis in all the tests follows the same procedure:

- 1.) Projection of data to the reference model
- 2.) Fault identification: Evaluation of T2 and SPE Charts
- 3.) Fault isolation: for dates with T2 and/or SPE out of control the Contribution charts are displayed. This reveals the variables causing the threshold trespassing in each chart (T2 and SPE). A summary of variables and instants is displayed (Report).

All tests gave successful results with reliable and precise faults detection in the different conditions.

5.2.2.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

The BEMServer platform allows to give access to the module for Faults Detection and Diagnosis (FDD-PCA) and to give as input to it the measured data from the BMS on field. So Measured data from the BMS can be automatically analysed in order to detected faults.

The deployed tests have shown that the module can detect successfully faults both in magnitude values both in correlation between the representing variables. The deployment of the BEMServer with FDD-PCA module makes it possible automatically, so the users should not analyse manually a large amount of datapoints, and for a large number of system components (e.g. AHUs, heating and cooling loops, etc. ...).

The module capabilities have been demonstrated in the performed tests, in which faults have been recognized properly in different conditions: current operation of the system, artificial faults generated on fields for test purposes, artificial faults included in the input data by properly changing the measured data in order to performed test. All tests showed successfully results, demonstrating that relevant faults can be detected automatically, such as

- Fans working out of proper time periods
- Not working sensors and actuators, like valves
- Indoor comfort and air quality issues (values out from the comfort ranges)
- Abnormal energy demand for heating, cooling, and electrical uses

Thanks to this, the following positive impacts have been reached in the system selected in the NUIG building and they can be potentially extended to the similar system replicated in the buildings:

- Electrical energy savings (avoiding useless fan operation)
- Proper control of system (detecting faults in sensors and in actuators)
- Indoor comfort improvements
- Thermal energy savings (avoiding useless operation of systems components)

Since the short time available after the completion of the module development, the FDD-PCA module have been tested on the selected air handling unit AHU101 and the served room Lecture Theatre 3 (Room G047). The BMS doesn't include energy meters dedicated to each air handling unit, so we performed a calculation to quantify the potential energy saving that can be provided by the FDD-PCA module for an AHU or all the AHU.

To do this, we extended the performed tests and we estimated potential savings, considered different scenario of faults corresponding to the tested ones. In general, we calculated that, avoiding these kinds of faults, the estimated potential saving of 25-65 % in the electrical energy demand for fans in AHUs similar to this and for the thermal energy for the coils. Details about this analysis were reported in chapter 5.3.

5.2.2.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The following improvements have been required and delivered:

- User guides updates
- Reports and results explanations

5.2.3 Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (Machine Learning based) (developed by FISE)

The Fault Detection and Diagnosis – System Oriented (FDD-ML) module detects failures or malfunctions of equipment leading an abnormal consumption of electricity in the building, deteriorating its energy performance. Its functionalities are very similar to the FDD-PCA module but it uses DBSCAN clustering algorithms and detects defaults on equipment. Both modules can be complementary as the FDD-PCA module detects defaults by zone.

5.2.3.1 Testing methodology

A set of models has been generated for the site. These have also been used in conjunction with the FM Display Module to visualize the results.

Below are some results of the developments. Because of large gaps in the used input data, the results could not be filtered for appropriate time ranges, which results in suboptimal detection results. Nonetheless the routines could already identify states of unusual operation of air handling unit AHU101. Figure 146 shows the table of faults and a plot of the associated sensor data in the FDD dashboard of the FM Visualization module. The selected time range shows a detected anomaly in the AHUs operation. According to the data both fans are out of operation, still the valve of the heating coil is nearly fully opened. This is also reflected by an elevated supply duct temperature. Figure 147 shows the results from the fault identification also accessible through the FM Visualization in the

same time region. The algorithm correctly identifies the heating valve position as a possible cause for the anomaly.

Figure 146. Screenshot of an FDD related dashboard populated with data from the module.

Figure 147. Results from fault identification (no fan operation).

As can be seen in Figure 148 anomalies have been identified also for summer operation of the AHU101. The algorithm identifies the operation of the pre-heater as a possible cause. The time period where the fault has been identified actually does not require frost coil operation as outside air temperatures are above 10 °C.

Figure 148. Results from fault identification (pre-heater operation).

Figure 149. Screenshot of a dashboard used to investigate the system data on the site.

5.2.3.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

The FDD-ML module have been tested in progressive stages of development. Different models have been deployed in order to reach higher levels of detail and completeness. Within the models, an increasing number of measured variables have been considered in the different versions.

Basing on machine learning techniques, the module represents a high potential tool for the fault detection. It is now at level of development of prototype, which can be used by the developers, thanks to the connection with the BEMServer. The FDD-ML module has already given good results in term of faults detection, for a system characterized by a good number of variables (measuring datapoints of the selected AHU and served room) and in different operation way (heating and cooling ones).

Due to the time schedules, the module was tested for periods of some days or weeks and this doesn't allow to extensively quantify an impact. The use of module can be scaled and extend on more systems.

Potentially the impact from this module could be similar to the once related to the FDD-PCA, for the energy savings for a typical AHU.

5.2.3.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

Different stages of improvements for the module have been released during the projects and for the test phase. Its stability and functionalities have been improved and completed. The module reached a good prototype level of development.

Further developments would lead to a user-friendly interface, now not available.

During the project, the connection between the module and the related visualization module has been completed. This allows useful functionalities of visualization, as shown in the graphs and screenshots here presented. Both the detected faults both the variables trends can be visualized in the same tool, providing an easy way to compare them and to verify to which values and effects the detected faults are related.

5.2.4 ModSCO – Simulation module (developed by NUIG)

The ModSCO simulation module exposes Reduced Order Models (ROM) to a non-expert engineer user using a web user interface. The general purpose of the tool is to provide an easy way of generating simplified models of a building and energy systems so they can be used for baseline energy projections and to analyse and recreate different control strategies comparing them together or against real measured data.

The current release of the ModSCO tool is available online at www.modsco.ie. The tool interface has been also integrated into the i-framed menu of the HIT2GAP portal. The tool is ready to create and run simulations, store simulation results and visualize different result sets with easy to navigate graphs for monthly, daily and hourly granularity.

Figure 150. Modsc0 landing page

The figure above shows the landing page of ModSCO. The main ROM link in the top menu bar gives the user access to the ROM administration application. An initial view shown in Figure 151 links the main areas tested in the Alice Perry Engineering Building at NUIG: ENG_2016_2017 (Computer Labs), ENG_G047 (Lecture Theatre) and ENG_2053_3053 (Postgrads Area). The user can select the room where ROM models have been developed or create a new model.

Figure 151. ModSCO index view

After choosing the area, the next view in Figure 152 shows the administration panel of all different models for the area chosen were a given user can: (1) view the model Parameters, (2) Use the Parameter as Template to modify them and create a new model, (3) Delete the set, (4) Simulate the set and (5) view the model Results. From this view, the user can also access a graph comparison of energy consumption for all the sets for daily and hourly values (see Figure 153 in next pages). These graphs have proved to be a very useful tool to visualize differences in energy consumption so the models can be quickly analysed and differences very easy to spot for a non-expert user.

Figure 152. ModSCO set index view

Figure 153. Comparative graph daily values for all sets

5.2.4.1 Testing methodology

The models described have been used using the same three rooms of the Alice Perry Engineering Building of the National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG) as case studies. The first room was the Post Grads Areas 2053 and 3053 located on the second and third floor and served by AHU 103, the second room was the Lecture Theatre G47 placed on the ground floor and conditioned by the AHU 101A and finally the third has been the Computer Labs 2016 and 2017 situated on the second floor served by the AHU105. For each of the areas described, the following actions were performed:

1. Relevant **information was collected** that reflects the main variables for the rooms. A survey has been done for all the three rooms to collect construction data, thermal and electric energy consumption of AHUs and thermal system for years 2015 and 2016. These data can be divided into (1) static information such as geometry, materials, construction arrangements, HVAC power etc., and (2) variables collected from the BMS sensor connected with HIT2GAP. The later were used to construct schedule-based inputs and other calculations.
2. An **initial model** was created using the form view provided in the tool. Different parameters were filled in order to produce a set. Figure 154 shows the ModSCO view to create a new model set. The user inputs the parameters in a form where a brief explanation is given. Some of the parameters need to be calculated using excel calculation tool that can be downloaded from the callout car on top of the page. These sheets are shown in Figure 156 and Figure 157. In these excel files abstract parameters such as Rea, Rie, Rm, Ce and Cm. These are calculated from physical information about the building. The user needs to download the excel file provided and fill the different worksheets which are connected. The input values are to fill these tables are: (1) single materials (2) surface areas (3) Construction Envelope arrangements (4) Global solar factor and (5) internal gains. Once all the worksheets are filled, the final table shows the calculated parameters values that need to be input in the ModSCO input data set. Heat gains regarding people and plug loads are also generated using the excel schedule tool provided. The following step in the creation of the ROM model is to represent the usage patterns of the building. The user needs to download the schedule generator and input schedules for the following: (1) Internal gains (whole year calendar), (2) Internal gains daily profiles with $\frac{1}{2}$ hour accuracy, (3) HVAC calendar (whole year HVAC schedules), (4) HVAC daily profiles with $\frac{1}{2}$ hour accuracy and (5) HVAC season calendar (cold-hot season). Once the calendar tool is filled up. The last worksheet will generate the

raw input needed to run the model. The user uploads the schedules and ModSCO makes them available as a choice field in a dropdown menu.

ModSCO: Rom H2G_test [Login](#)

Calculate Rea, Rie, and Rim

The values for Rea, Rie, Rim, Ce and Cm need to be calculated using the below excel spreadsheet and data gathered for the available buildings.

[Download INPUT excel](#)

Generate Schedules

Schedules for Occupancy, Season, Operation Schedule need to be generated using the schedule generator

[Download Schedules](#)
[Upload Schedules](#)
[Refresh Input](#)

Input Data Set

[Save](#)

Parameter NAME	Parameter VALUE	Parameter DESCRIPTION
Belongs to room:	<input type="text"/>	
Comment:	<input type="text"/>	
MaxPlugLoad:	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Maximum internal gain due to equipment - (W)
MaxLightingLoad:	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Maximum internal gain due to lighting - (W)
MaxOccupancyLoad:	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Maximum internal gain due to people (Max. no. of people x Activity level) - (W)
OccupancySchedule:	<input type="text"/>	Occupancy schedule affecting internal loads - (file)
RoomVolume:	<input type="text" value="15"/>	Room volume - (m3)
Rea:	<input type="text"/>	Thermal resistance between the ambient to the external envelope - (K/W)
Rie:	<input type="text"/>	Thermal resistance between the internal air and the external air - (K/W)
Rim:	<input type="text"/>	Thermal resistance value for internal partitions or slabs - (K/W)

Figure 154. Form view to create a new parameter set. This form expands to 27 parameter inputs

3. **HVAC monthly consumption calculation** was estimated from real BMS data following a dedicated procedure developed at NUIG. This comprises different calculations to reconstruct the Air Handling Unit Electrical and Thermal consumption from existing available data, as the single AHU are never submetered. The AHU unit electrical fan consumption was aggregated from AHU Variable Speed Drive BMS data and given the rated power. The AHU thermal consumption was estimated using ISO 13970:2008 and thermodynamics laws having into account temperature of air outside and temperature of air delivered to the room.
4. **A simplified calibration process** was performed. Final results were chosen that fit the values according ASHRAE 14 guidelines for monthly values of $\pm 5\%$ for the Normalized Mean Bias Error (NMBE) and 15% Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Square Error (CV-RMSE). A semi-automated calibration routine was performed using a python script where the parameters changed during the calibration procedure for the Computer Lab. The parameters chosen to perform the calibration job were based on previous literature¹, these are: (1)

¹ (Giretti, A. et al.. Reduced-order modelling for energy performance contracting. Energy and Buildings 2018. Elsevier., 167, pp. 216–230.).

“efficiencyCold”, (2) “efficiencyWarm”, (3) ThermostatRange[°C] and (4) LRate(kg/s).

For all the three rooms the results have satisfied the ASHRAE guideline 14 calibration criteria. In particular, the Post Grad Area provided a NMBE = 0.39% and a CV-RMSE = 9.80%, the Lecture Theatre a NMBE = 0.09% and a CV-RMSE = 8.81%, and finally the Computer Lab a NMBE = 0.32% and a CV-RMSE = 7.08%. For the Computer Lab the methodology was then further validated with the followed 2016 year data by changing weather file, occupancy schedules, AHU setpoints, and AHU heating and cooling switch. The results obtained are similarly positive and satisfy all calibration criteria with a NMBE = 1.42%, CV-RMSE = 11.10%. Figure below shows the set results view of ModSCO where values for NMBE and CV-RMSE are automatically calculated and corresponds to an intermediate step during the calibration process. The different simulations could be launched using the ModSCO web interface. At the current state of development and provided the elementary server capacity and database capabilities, a “concurrency=1” value was setup in the celery worker that performs the simulation works and process the data. This means different simulation are queued one by one.

- In the computer lab ModSCO tool was also used to test the impact of a control scenario based on temperature setpoint. For 2015, the setpoint temperature of the Computer Lab was fixed to 22 °C. A control scenario by using 20°C for the winter season and 24°C for the summer season has been tested. This implementation results with a yearly electric **energy saving of 2100 kWh**.

Figure 155. Results graph view showing measured Vs. simulated energy consumption, NMBE and CV-RMSE

5.2.4.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

ModSCO is an application that provides engineers an easy interface to produce Reduced Order Models (ROM) underpinned by MODELICA ® language without the hassle of learning complicated simulation software. Energy managers can use the models generated by ModSCO for a variety of energy related applications such as baselining, assessment of energy savings or verification. ModSCO is integrated with BEMServer so it can retrieve relevant static data and performance variables like energy consumption from different rooms or buildings. ModSCO is also capable of connecting with other BEMServer services like CALIBRO, FDD-PCA or ENERIT Energy Management module to provided added value services using your models.

The following are some of the benefits ModSCO Reduced Order Models concept brings to the BEMServer platform:

- ROM models allows the user to simulate scheduled changes and assess impact on energy consumption. It helps to the evaluation and assessment of possible interventions and their impacts on comfort and energy performances;
- The ROM tested were able to run in 90 seconds a whole year simulation, which overall is the main intent of the web-application process. This computation time opens the possibility to use this type of models in other applications where quick feedback is necessary. Scalability as a web service is also key point on providing a simulation as a service product.
- ROM models convey the combined and dynamic effects of thermal inertia, internal loads and weather variables, which is one of the advantages of using Building Performance Simulation;
- The ROM models use a number of simplification conventions (e.g.: simplified North/South/East/West building envelope geometry) that avoid excessively detailing of geometric data, while keeping the influence of orientation and envelope characteristics within the model
- ROM can be used to help understand possible conflicts between expected HVAC performance (start – stop) and scheduled occupancy. This can be traced down depending on available occupancy data or occupancy proxies (e.g.: CO₂ readings) coming from BEMServer.

5.2.4.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

Here below improvements to the ModSCO tool, thanks to its implementation in the NUIG pilot site, are listed.

- The form in the create new set view should be improved in order to guide the user. It should include indications about the thresholds, upper and lower values etc. Tips can be introduced in key terms where user hovers over and a brief explanation or link is provided.
- A new functionality should be introduced in the comparative graphs where a user selects a set as baseline and other set as the energy saving measure. Impact evaluation should be calculated between both sets either in graphical form and aggregated metrics.
- Customization for specific use remains as core consulting activity for revenue creation. The

ROM model developed can be further customized in order to suit specific needs. For instance, if a manufacturer likes to include a detailed model of a heat pump or a heat exchanger this can be achieved upon fee, as it needs changes to the core ROM.

- Migration to NoSQL or MySQL database that provides with a more robust concurrent access to write data.
- Improvement of the simulation / results availability interaction buttons using Django signals. Menu notifications could also be implemented.

5.2.5 BIM visualisation module (developed by ZUT)

The Zutec BIM visualization module is a 3D model viewer which allows users to view their project/building in a 3D environment on their mobile device and desktop. What is different and cutting edge about this tool "Dimensions" is that it can incorporate and show measurement points (in real or near real time). This makes a dramatic communication mechanism and a dedicated Zutec video was made to feature the NUIG and Poland demo sites (launched on twitter, youtube, Zutec and HIT2GAP pages). <https://twitter.com/ZUTECGROUP/status/1147071470545358848>

Figure 158. Zutec Dimensions applied and improved at NUIG.

5.2.5.1 Testing methodology

In the framework of the HIT2GAP tests at the pilot-site in Galway, a powerful BIM visualization software tool by ZUTEC have been applied, tested and improved in functionalities, thanks to the feedbacks from field tests at NUIG. ZUTEC provided access for the software and related app, to the team involved in the project. As such, R2M and NUIG staff have been able to implement and test the tool.

First, R2M with the support of CYLON, performed comprehensive checks on the completion of measured data made available from the BMS database to the ZUTEC tool. Then, ZUTEC and CYLON completed the informatic procedure to provide all the selected data from the BMS to the BIM visualization tool. Using the ZUTEC interface, users can easily add desired data-points to the visualized BIM model of the building and the systems. Then, the measurement datapoints and datasets were paired to different BIM models that R2M and NUIG staff developed and providing updates at different level of details. Then selected sensors boxes (e.g. CO2 concentration, temperature, and relative humidity sensors boxes) in the selected rooms were included in the BIM model. We started from the architectural BIM model, improved at different stage of details, where thanks to ZUTEC tool we visualized measured values from the BMS, linking them to rooms in the BIM model. After this, we enriched the BIM model also with components of mechanical system, for selected part of the building, selected as relevant example. The end result, the ZUTEC BIM visualization model has been tested on a comprehensive BIM model, with architectural and MEP components.

Thanks to this, measured real-time values from the BMS can now be visualized graphically linked to the related sensor boxes or components (e.g. air handling unit) and displaying coherent and correct names for sensors boxes, systems components (e.g. air handling unit), rooms, etc. One benefit of this work is that staff involved in the testing procedures can have useful and clear references using this Zutec module. In the figures that follow, various screenshots from the ZUTEC tool are shown. Visualization functionalities have been added to the other powerful capabilities of the ZUTEC tool, like repository of data, information and communication stream related to the components representing in the BIM model, warnings and alerts functionalities, easy and fast sending services of screenshots.

Figure 159. Near real time CO2 measurement information.

Figure 160. Screenshot sending test

Figure 161. Example of real-time visualization data from CO2 concentration sensors, 21/5/2019 - CEST time zone.

In the ZUTEC tool, for the NUIG pilot, measured data from the BMS are visualized at real-time directly from the BMS interface. We performed several tests about this: for example, we saw here above series of screenshots representing the same point of view in the model taken at different time (in this case at short intervals of some minutes). We can see proper changes in the values. R2M and CYLON also performed test in order to check that the visualized data are corrected in value and time according the source which is the BMS database. With this aim, visualized values in the ZUTEC tool have been compared with the data from the BMS thanks to the Active Energy Manager interface of the BMS. The tests demonstrate correctness of values and time. Here below some examples are presented, where in the screenshots from the ZUTEC tool the Italian summer time appears (since visualized in a desktop at the R2M’s offices in Italy), while in the screenshots from the BMS interface the same time appears for the time zone of Ireland and in standard/winter time (since as common, the BMS interface always uses standard time), so 2 hours of difference appears.

Figure 162. Comparison between visualized values in the ZUTEC tool and in the source BMS interface at the same time.

Figure 163. Comparison between visualized values in the ZUTEC tool and in the source BMS interface at the same time (see also Figure 164).

Figure 164. Comparison between visualized values in the ZUTEC tool and in the source BMS interface at the same time.
 D5.3 – Effects brought by the HIT2GAP solution in all four pilot sites and overall evaluation of the HIT2GAP solution
 179/220

After this round of tests, a further new functionality has been implemented in the ZUTEC visualization tool: it consists of visualizing measured data in different colours, according thresholds and limits set. For example, if comfort limits for indoor temperatures are overcome the related values became red. So, users can detect issues at real-time. This allows to check location and magnitude of discomfort zones or faulty situations, at first look on many different rooms and floors.

During the deployment in the Hi2Gap project, these new functionalities and typical functionalities of the ZUTEC tool have been applied to the NUIG pilot site. Real time visualization of the measured data by the BMS and colours according the comfort / acceptance conditions have been tested together with the ZUTEC functionalities consisting in assets list (visualization of BIM object in form of table where various information, files, attachments, communication flows, etc. can be seen in clearly structured framework, allowing filtering) and in snag list (a activities list linked to the BIM object, allowing communication flows, warnings, reminds, etc.). This has been demonstrated a completed deployment of the ZUTEC tool, with the integration of the BIM environment with the BMS capabilities.

Figure 165. Example of snag list implemented in the ZUTEC tool, with the direct link with the BIM visualization.

5.2.5.2 Impact analysis and key performance indicators results

Thanks to the ZUTEC tool and its developments happened in the HIT2GAP project, it's now possible to visualize real-time data, measured by the BMS, in a BIM environment, so the following aspects are integrated

- the BIM environment, characterized by a three-dimensional visualization of building and systems components, coupled together with detailed information fields, in a comprehensive database, which represent the strength of the building information modelling innovation;
- the dynamic visualization of values measured, signals exchanged, and possible warnings sensed by a variety of datapoints installed in buildings and systems
- the management of asset list e snag list about the building and installed systems components.

This has been deployed and tested in a wide and complex example represented by the NUIG pilot site. The ZUTEC tool, with the new functionalities related to the dynamic connection with the BMS, has been tested both for the architectural both for the systems (MEP) part of the BIM model.

Successful results have been reached, with interest and positive feedback from the facility managers and R2M technical staff involved in the deployment and use of the ZUTEC tool in the pilot site.

The ZUTEC tool is now able to integrate and give a unique access to the following relevant functionalities:

- users can avoid to open several different tools and applications and they can use one tool;
- users can visualize the values of measured variables of many different building zones and systems in easier and faster way, with one look to the BIM model;
- clear and explicit information on the location of sensors and related sensed values is given: so users can avoid to lose information about it or to wrong the selection of the right components: unfortunately this often happens particularly in large buildings with comprehensive and wide BMSs; thanks to the ZUTEC tool this aspect has been improved in the pilot site;
- relevant information (technical documentation, proper naming, etc.) is made accessible in easy and integrated way in one tool

These functionalities bring to a consistent saving of time and to improved chances of control and verifications about the BMS and related information stream.

5.2.5.3 Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received

The ZUTEC tool developments have provided stable and reliable connection with the real time data measured by the installed BMS. The communication flow and the visualized values have been deployed and verified, with improvements and upgrades during the project duration.

The function for visualizing measured values with different colours according settable threshold has been integrated and made available. This allows the users to quickly detect undesired comfort conditions and other operational issues. Positive feedbacks have been arisen by the building facility managers during the meetings occurred.

The tests performed on the ZUTEC tool concerned all of its functionalities (visualization in the BIM environment, direct connection with the BMS, asset list and snag list, information and documents integrated in the BIM model, etc.). Successful results have been reached and an interesting upgrade of a fully mature tool has been demonstrated.

5.2.6 ESP-r – Simulation module (developed by UOS)

The ESP-r module provides the means to identify locations within the building where indoor environmental quality may fall below levels prescribed in international standards. The identification of such point and the corresponding level of discomfort supports decision making by facility managers.

The FM can use the module to simulate the thermal distribution, glare and CO2 concentration in the building and thus identify locations where the indoor environmental quality may fall below levels prescribed in international standards or cause occupant discomfort. He will then know where a corrective action needs to be implemented. Once the corrective action is implemented the indoor quality and thermal comfort should improve and the number of complaints of the occupants per week should drop.

5.2.6.1 Testing methodology

ESP-r module takes data from the BEMServer for the selected simulation time. It also takes outdoor data from BEMServer. It uses data on hourly basis, and data at the same frequency is available for Galway from BEMServer.

At the moment, the calibration is automatically done and the calibrated model is returned to BEM Server (as a URL). ESP-r module uses the Calibro module to conduct the calibration where indoor temperature and outdoor weather data are used in the calibration.

The module can be found at <https://portal.h2g-platform-core.nobatek.com/>. After login to the platform, the user can select the ESP-r module from the menu (following Figure)

Figure 166. Screenshot 1 of a ESP-r Platform

Figure 167. Screenshot 5 of a ESP-r Platform

In March 2019, three days technical meeting was held at the Alice Perry Engineering Building, the HIT2GAP pilot site in Galway - Ireland.

It has been the opportunity to work on field together with the building facility managers to reduce the energy performance gap by applying software modules that are hosted in the open source BEMServer platform, powered by the HIT2GAP project.

R2M-Solution, as pilot managers, together with ESRU group of University of Strathclyde, Cylon Controls and IRUSE group of NUIG, organized these sessions about dynamic simulations and energy models calibration to help the facility management staff to improve systems actual controls and occupants satisfaction.

Particularly we focused on the ESP-r module, powered by the well-known energy dynamic simulation software ESP-r, developed by the ESRU group of University of Strathclyde, whose staff presented software capabilities to the facility managers and gathered information in order to improve and customize the energy model of the selected rooms, in order to be closer to actual needs of the staff on field.

The working team reviewed the control features and layout of the considered systems branches. This also helped to check the proper operation of the BMS components. And an improve energy models has been completed and let available to the facility management staff.

A first set of dynamic simulations has been launched via the BEMServer platform, providing results in term of thermal and visual comfort according suitable international standard for the selected periods for the simulations.

These BEMServer capabilities and ESP-r module allow to make easier the access to powerful dynamic simulation tool.

Figure 168. Three days technical meeting was held at the Alice Perry Engineering Building

Figure 169. 3D air path in 2016/2017 Computer Labs and related simulation model in the ESPr interface.

The following test cases were undertaken:

- 0_ simulation run of the base model using EPS-r interface form connected to the BEMServer
- 1_ simulation run of the model improved according information exchanges with the facility manager on field (faults the temperature sensors then repaired, schedule and control strategies, etc.)
- 2_ simulation run of model calibrated with Calibro module, basing on measured data gathered on BEMServer (from BuildAX and other sensors installed)

As a part of the test, the user wants to evaluate the thermal comfort distribution and to identify the location and the cause of discomfort. For this, we will evaluate the thermal comfort distribution and we will compare results to occupants' feedbacks.

As a part of the test 0, After running the module at NUIG, the module reported the lack of thermal comfort level air 2016/2017 Computer Labs.

The validation was undertaken through two methods. The first method was checking the thermal comfort violation in the location which was undertaken and the results confirmed the module report. The second validation method was undertaken by checking all BMS parameters of the room through Cylon Active Energy. It was found that the reason of violating thermal comfort was due to faulty supply sensor (NUIG_AHU105_Ctrls_AHU105_Supply_Temp__D2_1138) which was gone since summer 2018. This can be seen and confirmed in the following Figure where the faulty sensor sent -1000 °C.

The next test (test 1) was performed when the faulty sensor was fixed April 2019 (can be found in the following Figure) when thermal comfort was confirmed by ESP-r module

Figure 170. Faulty supply sensor (NUIG_AHU105_Ctrls_AHU105_Supply_Temp__D2_1138) data (Source: Active Energy)

The comfort parameters and assessment report can be generated by ESP-r module. This includes assessing air quality, thermal quality and visual comfort. The ESP-r report shows assessment results in tabular and graph formats for the locations violating the standards. These results give the opportunity to FMs to get suitable knowledge on whether or not the building is compliant with all the international comfort standards and if not, the module informs the FM where the violated locations

are. The achieved information can be used for further evaluation in detecting and overcoming the reason of violation to bring back the building to the standard comfort level.

As regard to indoor air quality test, the ESP-r simulation was run for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 for 22/03/2019. The results and analysis can be seen in following figure. The figure lists rank-ordered assessment results for the locations that do not comply with the standard.

Area	Location	Frequency of CO ₂ concentration violating criteria (%)	Time of worst criteria violation (MM/DD HH:MM)
comp_lab	sen_01	18.2	3/22 13:00
	sen_02	18.2	3/22 13:00
	sen_03	18.2	3/22 13:00
	sen_04	18.2	3/22 13:00

Figure 171. rank-ordered assessment air quality results for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 in locations that do not comply with the standard

In the following figure, the comfort parameter values at violated locations are compared to the standard criteria (shown as dash lines).

Figure 172. rank-ordered assessment air quality results for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 in violated locations in comparison with standard criteria

ESP-r module was used to investigate the thermal comfort level for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 for 22/03/2019. The assessment results of thermal comfort simulation can be found in the following figure for all locations that do not comply with the standard, with comfort criteria. The results show the frequency of violation of the comfort criteria as well as the times of the day when these values were most flagrant.

Area	Location	Operative temperature	Floor temperature	Radiant asymmetry (ceiling)	Radiant asymmetry (wall)	Draught	Vertical air temperature difference	Daily temperature drift	Weekly temperature drift
Frequency of violation of the criteria associated with the metrics above (%)									
comp_lab	sen_01	45.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	sen_02	45.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	sen_03	45.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	sen_04	36.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Time of worst violation of the criteria associated with the metrics above (MM-DD HH:MM) (MM-DD+MM-DD)									
comp_lab	sen_01	03-22 17:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	sen_02	03-22 17:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	sen_03	03-22 17:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	sen_04	03-22 17:30	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Figure 173. rank-ordered assessment thermal quality results for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 in locations that do not comply with the standard

Figure 174. rank-ordered assessment thermal quality results for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 in violated locations in comparison with standard criteria

ESP-r module was also run to evaluate the visual comfort level for NUIG computer laboratory ENG-2016 for 22/03/2019. These results are also provided for the locations which are violating the standard comfort criterial. Based on the ESP-r analysis outcome, the visual comfort was not violated at computer laboratory ENG-2016. Under this circumstance, the module provides a report as can be seen in the following figure.

Analysis outcomes
 All locations, as analysed, have comfort metric values within the criteria and therefore are compliant with the standard.

Figure 175. Sample of report in ESP-r when there is no violation to standard comfort level

5.2.6.2 *Impact analysis and key performance indicators results*

ESP-r an easy access to a comprehensive and powerful energy dynamic simulation engine for buildings and to access to capabilities of IEQ analysis and report according to international standard. This allows FMs to launch energy simulation in easy way, selecting the desired time period, in order to visualize indoor comfort analysis, so the FMs do not need to be experts in dynamic energy simulation etc. but will still be able to perform these simulations.

The development of high-resolution models for use with BEMServer take 10 working days to develop and calibrate a high-resolution model of equivalent size to the NUIG model. This breaks down as 3 days for site visit for data collection and survey, 3 days for model development and 4 days for quality assurance and calibration. The daily rate is for this work is £650 (before VAT).

- ESP-r in BEMServer allows the building FMs and/or other stakeholders to have an easy access to a comprehensive and powerful energy dynamic simulation engine for buildings and to access to capabilities of IEQ analysis and report according to international standards. ESP-r is used to identify the reason of performance gap and allows a detailed appraisal of the energy and environmental performance of buildings which is a topic with increasing importance as energy and environmental awareness grows. The deployment of ESP-r module of BEMServer provides opportunities to the identification of inconsistencies between the building documentation and actual operation that may help tackling the energy performance gap. For example, a night ventilation model undertaken at NUIG building resulted in noticeable improvements in the performance of the building.
- The initial simulation model may be modified (by an experienced modeller) to create variants allowing the evaluation of changes in use, operation or in components (at rooms, zones or building levels). However, ESP-r allows FMs to launch energy simulation in easy way, selecting the desired time period, in order to visualize indoor comfort analysis, so even the FMs who are not experts in dynamic energy simulation will still be able to perform these simulations. In other word, the deployment of BEMServer can be facilitated by outsourcing the development of required energy models, so FMs do not need to build the model themselves (this is a service that can be offer by consultancy companies or HIT2GAP partners, e.g. UoS)
- With help of ESP-r module and studying the dynamic and local comfort level of the building (such as visual, thermal, CO2 comfort levels, etc) according to international standard, the defective components and/or BMS malfunctions can be detected in a promising time span. Based on the achieved results, the suitable corrective measures can be taken to overcome the comfort issue and violation. This not only saves inspection time, improves the BMS maintenance level and enhance the indoor quality and comfort level of the building, but also can considerably reduce the number of complaints made by occupants per week/month. For example, using the ESP-r model development, the HIT2GAP team and FMs detected that one of the main sensor of the considered AHU didn't work properly. This resulted in excessive air flow rate and fans speed and operation time violating the comfort level of the room. While running the ESP-r simulation, the location of the violation was promptly detected. This was a significant feature and had a great impact on saving the malfunction-inspection time considering the large size and complex structure of the NUIG building.
- ESP-r can provide high resolution, clear, straightforward and user-friendly reports including local visual images, times-series graph, 3D air path, 3D indoor temperature stratification, visual comfort, graphs difference in indoor air temperature between tests, etc. This saves a considerable amount of time for FM to assess and evaluate the results and take the sufficient measure which ease the process of building energy management.

- ESP-r supports fast-track strategies to establish:
 - patterns of heating and cooling demand over time,
 - the frequency of extreme conditions,
 - the frequency of minimal demand,
 - what might happen if heating or cooling failed,
 - what might happen if heating or cooling was critically undersized,
 - how often will the building work satisfactorily without mechanical intervention.

Such early indicators are valuable to members of the design team and may also result in well-founded opinions about demand side improvements and likely environmental control regimes. One of the early planning tasks is to identify the nature of assessments which will allow FMs to gain confidence in the model and modelling approach as well as deliver performance indicators well-matched to the design team goals

- ESP-r analyses are used to view the simulation results and undertake a variety of performance appraisals: changes to the model parameters can then follow depending on these appraisals. The ranges of analyses are essentially unrestricted, allowing the different performance indicators to be inter-related and these indicators to be translated to proposed design changes. Here are some examples indicating the impact of ESP-r:
 - It is often necessary to estimate the overheating risk of an office block with natural ventilation. Combined thermal and air flow simulations may be undertaken to determine the frequency distribution of internal summertime dry resultant temperatures for assumed occupancy and internal gains.
 - Some rooms and labs have strict requirements regarding the control of temperature and humidity and a need to operate within strict capital and running cost constraints. Combined simulation of the building and plant systems can save those cost and also can be used to compare various plant configurations and to determine optimum component sizes.
 - A large number of glazing and shading devices are available. ESP-r can be used to assess the relative merits of these in terms of thermal, lighting and acoustic comfort, and energy consumption.
 - To facilitate passive design, the benefits of techniques such as thermal mass, night purging and displacement ventilation can be quantified.
 - Many prestige office blocks now include atria and sunspaces. ESP-r can be used to assess solar and daylight utilisation as well as the inherent buffering effects.
 - In many buildings, heat recovery appears an attractive option. ESP-r can be used to quantify the corresponding energy benefits of both heat recovery and partial recirculation of air.
 - Many new buildings are being constructed which attempt to integrate new technologies, either as prestigious developments or as demonstration buildings. ESP-r is equipped to model the impact of advanced concepts such as daylight responsive light, heat recovery, transparent insulation, breathable construction, photovoltaic facades and ground source heat pumps.
 - In short, the integrated simulation approach is extremely powerful. That said, it does have limitations. To address these, ESP-r has been subjected to many validation trials to test the robustness and accuracy of the underlying mathematical models not only for NUIG building but also for other buildings during the last decades some of which have been referenced here.

5.2.6.3 *Improvement of the module following the feedbacks received*

The reports for thermal comfort and air quality now include time-series graphs with criteria highlighted. Graphs are only produced for locations that violate the standard. The visual comfort reports now include rendered images with annotations when the comfort criteria in the standard is violated. When results are saved to the portal, they are now properly tagged with events that should make retrieving results from the Nobatek platform easier.

5.3 Gap evaluation

The actions performed in the NUIG pilot site represented a comprehensive example of deployment of the HIT2GAP solution and completed workflow about them.

This has allowed to use in deeper way the installed BMS and to get more benefits from it. The NUIG pilot site is a modern building for educational, research laboratories and office spaces, with several controls and automation functionalities, managed by a wide BMS. Previously, the facility management staff could perform verification and analysis about statuses and performance, only by manual procedure, which can be made only for certain samples and for short period or for particular issues arisen. As it happens often, comprehensive BMSs, with many datapoints and functionalities, like the NUIG ones, are potentially very useful but they are used only partially or for short time period. Although the facility management staff put care and effort, this underuse of the BMS happened in the NUIG pilot too. The BEMServer platform and the software modules applied provided automatic functionalities for data visualization and analysis, for faults detection and diagnosis, for load forecasting, and for energy dynamic simulation. This helped a lot in the use of the BMS.

The gap in the best use of the installed BMS has been reduced thanks to the BEMServer platforms and the related modules.

The performed tests allowed to demonstrate in reliable way the functionalities of the developed modules and the whole platform. This gives values to the project results and solid bases for the exploitation developments.

Some of the software modules needed time to reach a good level of maturity. Meanwhile tests were performed at different stages of development for the modules and for the related specific models. For this, the test phase for the whole set of modules didn't take one whole year, but shorter periods. As decided at the beginning of the project, in order to reach clearer feedbacks for the developments and according the efforts foreseen, the HIT2GAP solution has been tested on four representative and relevant zones of the buildings, and the BMS has energy meters measuring the energy demand for different users for the whole buildings or for wide zones and not separately for each of the zones where tests were performed. As described, this brought to relevant results but the impact cannot always be quantified. Analysis and extensions have been made in order to assess performance gap reduction and impacts of the HIT2GAP solution.

The BEMServer platform allows to give access to the module for Faults Detection and Diagnosis (FDD-PCA) and to give as input to it the measured data from the BMS on field. So Measured data from the BMS can be automatically analysed in order to detected faults.

The deployed tests have shown that the module can detect successfully faults both in magnitude values both in correlation between the representing variables. The deployment of the BEMServer with FDD-PCA module makes it possible automatically, so the users should not analyse manually a large amount of datapoints, and for a large number of system components (e.g. AHUs, heating and cooling loops, etc. ...).

Thanks to this, the following positive impacts have been reached in the system selected in the NUIG building and they can be potentially extended to the similar system replicated in the buildings:

- Electrical energy savings (avoiding useless fan operation)
- Proper control of system (detecting faults in sensors and in actuators)
- Indoor comfort improvements
- Thermal energy savings (avoiding useless operation of systems components)

We extended the performed tests and we estimated potential savings, considered different scenarios of faults corresponding to the tested ones. In general, we calculated that, avoiding these kinds of faults, the estimated potential saving of 25-65 % in the electrical energy demand for fans in AHUs similar to this.

The following formulas have been used to calculate the monthly fan energy consumption and the coil thermal energy consumption with a half hour basis.

$$Fans\ Cons_{TOT} = \sum_i Fan\ Operation_i \cdot Fans\ Cons \cdot \Delta t$$

Where:

- $Fans\ Cons$ = is the Fans Consumption calculated as:

$$Fans\ Cons = N^{\circ} Fan_{Sup} \cdot Fan\ Power_{Sup} [kW] + N^{\circ} Fan_{Ret} \cdot Fan\ Power_{Ret} [kW]$$
- t = is the time interval in which the data is logged. Since the table calculate the result with a half hour basis, this value is fixed and equal to:

$$\Delta t = \frac{30}{60} = 0,5\ h$$

- $Fan\ Operation_i$ = is the fans operation schedule; its value can be between:
 - 1 when the fans are ON
 - 0 when the fans are OFF

The calculation of the related thermal energy consumption is based on the standard ISO 13790:2008, this represents an approximate estimation since only the energy related to heat losses and the heat gain for ventilation are considered, and not all the possible moist air transformations in detailed.

The formula used to calculate the thermal energy demand is the following:

$$Coils\ Cons_{TOT} = \sum_i Q_{ve,i} = \sum_i H_{ve,adj} \cdot \Delta T_i \cdot Fan\ Operation_i \cdot \Delta t$$

Where:

- $H_{ve,adj}$ = is the overall heat transfer coefficient by ventilation, adjusted for indoor-outdoor temperature difference:

$$H_{ve,adj} = \rho_a \cdot c_a \cdot b_{ve,k} \cdot q_{ve,k,mn}$$

Where:

- $\rho_a c_a$ = is the heat capacity of air per volume, expressed as 0,34 Wh/m³K
- $b_{ve,k}$ = is the temperature adjustment factor for air flow from a heat recovery unit is equal to:

$$b_{ve,k} = \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{100} \right)$$

Where β is the heat recovery efficiency (%); equal to 50% for cross flow heat exchange installed, and to 80% for rotating heat exchange.

- $q_{ve,k,mn}$ = is the time-average airflow rate of air flow element k in m³/s

- ΔT_i = the temperature difference is calculated as:

$$\Delta T = \theta_{supply} - \theta_{out}$$

Where:

- θ_{supply} = is the temperature supplied by the fan inside the building
- θ_{out} = is the outside temperature.

- t = Time interval in which the data is logged.

$$t = \frac{30}{60} = 0,5h$$

- $Fan\ Operation_i$ = Fans operation schedule; its value can be:
 - 1 when the fans are ON
 - 0 when the fans are OFF

A study of the calendar schedule and the fan usage for the AHU101 has been carried out. From this, results that there are 3 different periods for calendar schedules, one for the winter season, one for the summer season and the last is based on the holidays. The winter season has been considered from the 1st of January until the 31st of May and from the 1st of September until the 31th of December. In the winter mode, the AHU101 is ON from 8 am to 6 pm during the working week (Monday to Friday), from 11 am to 4 pm on Saturday and from 11 to 3 pm on Sunday.

The summer schedule has been considered from the 1st of June to the 31st of August. During this season, the AHU is ON from 8 am to 6 pm during the working week (Monday to Friday), from 11 am to 4 pm on Saturday and from 11 to 3 pm on Sunday. Instead, once is holiday, the AHU schedule has been considered always OFF. Based on the measured data, the fan speed is set to 60% for all the seasons of the Alice Perry building.

All this information has been inserted in an Excel spreadsheet (Figure 176) where can be also created different fan operation schedules by deciding the:

- weekly calendars (winter, summer and holidays);
- annual holidays;
- season mode of the building;
- fan usage of the weekly calendars [%].

Figure 176. AHU operation schedules.

To calculate the fans electrical energy consumption and the coils thermal energy consumption were considered also some building information such as the location of the building for the outside temperature, the winter and summer average setpoint temperature. Then, some data for the AHU101 was needed such as the air flow rate (8 100 m³/h) and the percentage of the heat recovery efficiency, the 80% for the AHU101.

Once all the parameters have been filled (Figure 177), the output of the process are the:

- fans electrical energy consumption;
- estimated coils thermal energy consumption.

Figure 177. AHUs specifications and results' excel sheet describes all the AHUs specification of the Alice Perry building.

The following faults scenarios have been considered and the potential energy savings reachable avoiding them have been calculated:

1. Faults scenario 1 (F1): the fans VSD (variable speed drive) is set to 100% instead of the original 60%;
2. Faults scenario 2 (F2): the weekly AHU's working schedule is 8 am - 9 pm instead of 8 am - 6 pm;
3. Faults scenario 3 (F3): in the month of September, the fans VSD (variable speed drive) is set to 100% h 24 without following the weekly schedules.

These kinds of faults reflect typical real issues which can happen during the operation and that can be detected by the FDD-PCA module in effective and precise way, as demonstrated in the performed tests. These can be broken sensors or

In Table 25, a comparison in terms of fan electrical consumptions of the three faults described against the optimal operation of the AHU101 (no faults) is showed.

Table 25: Monthly and annual fans electrical and coil thermal energy consumption according the considered scenarios of detectable faults

	Monthly Energy demand [kWh]							
	No Fault (electrical energy)	No Fault (thermal energy)	F1 (electrical energy)	F1 (thermal energy)	F2 (electrical energy)	F2 (thermal energy)	F3 (electrical energy)	F3 (thermal energy)
January	1'691	4'257	2'818	7'095	2'103	5'353	1'691	4'257
February	1'560	3'721	2'600	6'202	1'934	4'694	1'560	3'721
March	1'660	3'104	2'766	5'174	2'053	4'029	1'660	3'104
April	1'597	3'416	2'662	5'693	1'991	4'422	1'597	3'416
May	1'691	2'158	2'818	3'597	2'103	2'843	1'691	2'158
June	1'557	1'720	2'595	2'866	1'913	2'237	1'557	1'720
July	1'757	1'497	2'928	2'495	2'187	2'063	1'757	1'497
August	1'660	1'061	2'766	1'768	2'053	1'482	1'660	1'061
September	1'654	1'675	2'756	2'791	2'047	2'281	7'488	10'333
October	1'691	3'086	2'818	5'143	2'103	3'869	1'691	3'011
November	1'660	4'095	2'766	6'824	2'053	5'130	1'660	4'094
December	1'588	4'266	2'647	7'109	1'962	5'304	1'588	4'266
Energy demand [kWh]	19'765	34'055	32'942	56'757	24'501	43'706	25'600	42'637
Energy savings [%]			66.7%	66.7%	24.0%	28.3%	29.5%	25.2%
Energy savings [kWh]			-13'177	-22'703	-4'736	-9'652	-5'834	-8'583

Figure 178. Monthly and annual fans electrical and coil thermal energy consumption graphs

As can be seen from the graphs in Figure 178, each of the faults generate an increase in the fan electric consumption and in the coils thermal energy consumption.

Avoiding the first fault scenario (F1), represented by the VSD set to 100%, we reach a saving of 13'177 kWh (66.7%) in terms of fans electric energy consumption, which corresponds to a cost saving of about 1'635 €, and 56'757 kWh (28.3%) of coil thermal energy consumption, corresponding to a cost saving of about 2'753 €.

From the second fault scenario (F2) we avoid around 4'700 kWh (24%) of fan electric consumption, which corresponds to a cost saving of about 583 €, and 16'086 kWh (28.3%) of coil thermal energy consumption, corresponding to a cost saving of about 780 €.

Finally, in the last scenario (F3), we saved 5'834 kWh (29.5%) of fan electric consumption, which corresponds to a cost saving of about 724 €, and 7'415.98 kWh (13.1%) of coil thermal energy consumption, corresponding to a cost saving of about 360 €.

The potential savings are relevant both from energy both from costs point of view. This is also valid extended the estimation to the pilot site building and to the all the buildings in the university campus, as it is shown here below.

Table 26: Alice Perry building's AHUs specifications

	Air Flow Rate [m3/h]	Heat Recovery	Fan power supply [kW]	Fan power return [kW]
AHU 101A	8'100	Wheel heat exchange	6.00	4.40
AHU 102	2'880	Heat recovery coil	2.20	
AHU 103	38'160	Heat recovery coil	30.00	16.00
AHU 104	18'000	No heat recovery	12.00	8.80
AHU 105	5'580	Heat recovery coil	4.40	
AHU 106	25'740	No heat recovery	16.00	4.00
AHU 107	2'700	No heat recovery	2.20	
AHU 108	2'160	Wheel heat exchange	1.50	
AHU 109	5'400	No heat recovery	4.00	3.00
AHU 110	396	No heat recovery	0.55	
AHU 111	396	No heat recovery	0.55	

Extending the same analysis to all the 11 AHUs in the NUIG pilot site, which are listed in the Table 26, the following potential energy and cost savings are summarised in Table 27, where for the costs saving calculation the following values have been considered: electrical energy costs equal to 0.1241 €/kWh, costs for natural gas equal to 0.0388 €/kWh (statistical value, tax included, from Eurostat portal for Ireland), average efficiency ratio for the thermal system installed equal to 0.8.

Table 27: Potential energy and cost savings of the all Alice Perry building's AHUs

	Faults scenarios							
	No Fault (electrical energy)	No Fault (thermal energy)	F1 (electrical energy)	F1 (thermal energy)	F2 (electrical energy)	F2 (thermal energy)	F3 (electrical energy)	F3 (thermal energy)
Energy demand [kWh]	219'697	271'963	366'162	453'271	272'341	349'041	284'548	340'505
Energy savings [kWh]	-	-	146'465	181'308	52'644	77'078	64'851	68'542
Costs savings [€]	-	-	18'176	8'793	6'533	3'738	8'048	3'324

In Table 28, the same analysis has been extended to the whole NUIG campus by doing an estimation of the potential energy savings based on the campus buildings' volume. This has been done by

considering the whole campus building volume around 730'764 m³ and the Alice Perry Engineering building volume equal to 68'325 m³, corresponding to the 14 main buildings included in the campus plus some smaller ones. This could represent an interesting analysis as estimation for representative for these kinds of group of buildings, like university or office campuses.

Table 28: Potential energy savings of the whole NUIG campus' AHUs

Faults scenarios								
	No Fault (electrical energy)	No Fault (thermal energy)	F1 (electrical energy)	F1 (thermal energy)	F2 (electrical energy)	F2 (thermal energy)	F3 (electrical energy)	F3 (thermal energy)
Energy demand [kWh]	2'349'750	2'908'756	3'916'250	4'847'925	2'912'800	3'733'141	3'043'362	3'641'836
Energy savings [kWh]	-	-	1'566'500	1'939'169	563'050	824'385	693'612	733'080
Costs savings [€]	-	-	194'403	94'049	69'875	39'983	86'077	35'554

Similarly, for the FDD-ML module, since it bases on machine learning techniques, the module represents a high potential tool for the fault detection. It is now at level of development of prototype, which can be used by the developers, thanks to the connection with the BEMServer. The FDD-ML module has already given good results in term of faults detection, for a system characterized by a good number of variables (measuring datapoints of the selected AHU and served room) and in different operation way (heating and cooling ones).

Due to the time schedules, the module was tested for periods of some days or weeks and this doesn't allow to extensively quantify an impact. The use of module can be scaled and extend on more systems. Potentially the impact from this module could be similar to the one related to the FDD-PCA, for the energy savings for a typical AHU.

The modules related to the energy dynamic simulation allowed users who deployed them in the NUIG pilot, to have an easy access to powerful simulation tools. For the ESP-r module in the BEMServer also a functionality for automatic calibration with direct link to real measured data from the BMS has been made available.

The performed dynamic simulations with calibrated models allowed to evaluate possible strategy to improve indoor thermal comfort conditions and energy performance of the selected building zones, for example additional ventilation to avoid overheating.

The performance gap reduction was reached also during the deployment phase of the energy modelling, when rooms and systems features were reviewed in order to be represented in the model, which then was made available via the BEMServer platform. Together with the facility manager, a faulty sensor has been detected in the review process. Probably it was wrong for a long period and previously nobody had been able to recognize it: it consisted of the temperature sensor of the supply air of a related AHU, that sensed a fixed temperature of -100 °C. This wrong value made the system to request always for heating, bringing to worse comfort situation in rooms where overheating conditions already occurred, due to the high internal thermal loads for high occupancy levels and many computers installed there.

In this case, the FDD modules were not applied to these rooms, and the fault was recognized thanks to the deployment of the energy simulation service related to ESP-r.

Thanks to this the facility manager replaced the faulty sensor.

The functionalities deployed thanks to the ZUTEC tool brought to a consistent saving of time and to improved chances of control and verifications about the BMS and related information stream.

The tool is able to integrate and give a unique access to the following relevant functionalities:

- users can avoid to open several different tools and applications and they can use one tool;
- users can visualize the values of measured variables of many different building zones and systems in easier and faster way, with one look to the BIM model;
- clear and explicit information on the location of sensors and related sensed values is given: so users can avoid to lose information about it or to wrong the selection of the right components;
- relevant information (technical documentation, proper naming, etc.) is made accessible in easy and integrated way in one tool.

5.4 Lessons learnt during the operation

The performed tests shew a comprehensive example of the deployment of the HIT2GAP platform and modules. It gave positive results and it demonstrated reliable solution and related services.

Tests were performed in different stages and this allows important feedbacks for the modules developments, about users interfaces, access and integration through the BEMServer platform, calculation models for the module deployments, etc.

The services, which were put in place in NUIG pilot site basing on the BEMServer solution, are replicable in other similar buildings.

The deployed modules represent innovative tool to cover real needs of facility managers, energy managers, and other stakeholders involved. Also, the related services have been demonstrated in the test actions. These are services to develop proper models for the FDD modules or for the energy simulation tools. The models can be developed directly from the users, if they have expertise, or by the proper services providers acting as consultants.

During the preparation phases for the tests, a substantial effort had to be put in deepening the features of the BMS, as right names of the sensors and variables, actual locations and verification of correct operation, possible missing parts. After this, the deployment of a comprehensive visualization and information tool like the ZUTEC one can help a lot in gathering a large amount of information also about the BMS and to make them available in easy way.

It is relevant that BEMServer allowed to give easy access to comprehensive tools for dynamic simulations, like ESP-r, that usually can be used only by expert people. Thanks to the ESP-r module made available on the HIT2GAP platform the simulation engine can be used also by the involved NUIG staff. This is even more interesting since the module was completed by a functionality for automatic calibration of the models using the measured data from the BMS.

The BEMServer platform represents a relevant gateway to exploit the use of the BMS. The platform can easily connect a BMS with software modules, already developed or that will be developed in future.

The following achievements could be summarized for NUIG site:

- Successful creation of a database including 364 measured variables, for more than 12 months, fully interoperable with the BEMServer platform
- Real time, stable and reliable connection between amazon cloud server, where the pilot

site BMS stores all the measured data, and the BEMServer platform: a complete set of 364 variables was made available on the HIT2GAP platform and the comprehensive and reliable communication flow was set and verified

- Part of this large amount of measured data was made available as open access data on the scientific platform Zenodo: 2 sets of data were selected as significant for further research investigations, specifically about a complete monitoring layout of one of the AHU and about 2 selected energy meters, involved in the HIT2GAP test
- AHU malfunctioning captured and faults detected in reliable and precise way: they represent significant faults for the pilot site and in general typical faults that can happen in an AHU and to their sensors and components
- Achievable saving in electrical and thermal energy for AHUs of 25-65%
- Real time connection between BIM model and BMS of the building, so real time values from the installed data-points can be visualized in the 3-dimensional BIM environment
- Measured values outside acceptable comfort and operation ranges can be easily visualized in the BIM model with different colors, for fast and easy detection
- All the following functions successfully integrated in BIM environment thanks to the ZUTEC tool: 3-dimensional virtual visualization of building and systems components, architectural and MEP parts of the BIM model both involved, real time visualization of the measured data from the BMS, technical information, documents, photos and other information materials directly accessible and integrated, snags list and asset lists for AHUs and other components in order to check needed actions and features of buildings zones, components and systems parts
- Forecasting of demand of thermal energy for heating and electrical energy for cooling (for chillers) with average error between 0,7 and 16%
- A module to build in easy way energy models of building zones for simplified dynamic simulation, thanks to the MODSCO tool
- Comparison of simulated and actual performance of air handling units using MODSCO module
- An easy access to a comprehensive and powerful energy dynamic simulation engine for buildings and to access to capabilities of IEQ analysis and report according to international standard, thanks to ESP-r module, made available in the BEMServer platform
- Automatic calibration of energy simulation models according measured data from the BMS and improvements actions assessed thanks to energy dynamic simulation of automatic calibrated models

6 HIT2GAP Platform

This section describes the refinements implemented in the platform following the feedbacks received from the pilot sites managers. Here this requires an involvement of platform developers and modules developers.

Even though the different modules available in the HIT2GAP platform provide several results regarding data analysis, fault detection, gap evaluation and recommendations, it is mandatory that the platform provides simple data visualisation tools. For this reason, a module called Time Series Monitoring and Analytics was developed.

Figure 179. Time Series Monitoring and Analytics module in the BEMServer modules store

It allows the user to show the data in real time and navigate in the data as shown in Figure 180. This can be done for data coming from sensors, or from modules.

Figure 180. Data graph display in the Time Series Monitoring and Analytics module

Moreover, since a good quality of data is essential for most of the modules, a data treatment model has been included with the platform. Data treatment in the HIT2GAP platform includes:

- Clean data: BEMServer looks at the data received and try to identify missing and outliers. If some are found, errors are replaced with some inferred values.
- Resampling: module developers can access resampled data by specifying the frequency at which the data is needed – for instance, if a temperature sensor sends data every 5 sec, but one needs data every 10 sec, this can be done with this API.
- Unit conversion: similarly, the original unit can be modified. For example, temperature data collected in Kelvin can be transformed to Celsius Degree.
- Statistics on data: This gives the possibility to a module developer to quickly see when the last data were collected for a given data point, or when the first ones were collected, etc... This API is used to assess problems.
- Finally, different data points can be aggregated in a single one- for example, by taking the average of a number of sensors.

7 Conclusion

HIT2GAP platform and modules have been tested on 4 pilot sites: Challenger (France), Wilanow Town Hall (Poland), Nanogune (Spain) and National University of Galway (Ireland). Different modules have been tested on these sites, depending on the expectations and requirements of each site. The four sites were each different and hence the results of the testing and impact of HIT2GAP varied between the pilot sites.

Different gains can be obtained from the testing phase of the modules, such as: energy saving, occupants' comfort and satisfaction, reduction of man-months and others. Each of these benefits have been explained and demonstrated in this deliverable.

Finally, this report has demonstrated that there is a great potential for HIT2GAP to address different users depending on their needs and on their profile.

The table below shows the summary of the feedback from the pilot sites managers after the testing of the modules.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
Challenger	Load Forecasting	Forecasting precision was good for some applications (lighting and plug load consumption) and not okay for other applications (heating and cooling)	The module is mature.	The module is ergonomic but the selection of the models should be simplified.	The module can be used to identify discrepancies. However, the module should also predict future consumption (for energy performance contracts) and highlight alerts for discrepancies.
Challenger	Fault detection and diagnosis (FDD- PCA)	The module detects some relevant alerts but also some irrelevant ones. The analysis of the alerts as it is today is time consuming since not all of the alerts are relevant. The module needs to be improved or calibrated.	The module needs to be refined. There are too many alerts, some are relevant and some are not.	The interface needs to be simplified. The module as it is only allows the user to see the alerts per day and per model. It should allow the user to check the history of alerts and the distribution for all models for all the building,	Once the module is tuned, it is very useful to detect defaults on equipment.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomy	Evaluation of usefulness
				otherwise it is time consuming.	
Challenger	Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD- ML)	The module was not fully available for testing. However, a model has been generated for one air handling unit with some relevant alerts. The machine learning feature of the module is not visible.	Module was not fully available for testing.	Module was not fully available for testing.	The main alerts detected by the module concern incorrect supply air temperatures. The machine learning feature of the module is not visible.
Challenger	User behaviour module (BM-ML)	The module is useful to evaluate if the perceived comfort conditions are met. However, no real time alerts were available in the testing phase.	The comfort alerts were not tested: first because Challenger is adequate to comfort norms and second because no real time alerts were generated. The prediction of energy consumption is not relevant to the module objectives. I would say that the module is not mature enough.	The interface was not tested because of the absence of real time data during the testing phase.	The module is useful to evaluate whether or not the occupants are satisfied with indoor comfort conditions. It would have been better if the module allowed to identify best comfort conditions by taking into consideration occupants comfort, weather and energy consumption.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomy	Evaluation of usefulness
Challenger	User behaviour module (BM-Events)	The module allowed to detect overconsumptions during non-working hours.	Mature and commercialized.	Ergonomic and easy to use. However, the user needs to manually set the alert limits for each application and zone.	The module is useful to detect and quantify overconsumptions during non working hours.
Challenger	Energy Management (EM + EM Visualisation)	The module is useful to track global energy consumption, benchmark, energy invoices, energy loss, energy improvement actions, alerts from other modules.	Mature and commercialized.	It is not easy to use the module at first sight but the module comes with the right documentation and support.	The module is useful to track global energy consumption, benchmark, energy invoices, energy loss, energy improvement actions, alerts from other modules.
Challenger	Building Performance simulation Module (ESP-r)	The module simulates comfort distribution in any area. The simulation modules are heavy and require lots of time to prepare and to run.	Due to the difficulty in using the module, it cannot be commercialized as it is. Actual data measurements need to be well integrated in the module, otherwise the results are not accurate.	The report generating the results is basic but takes a lot of time to load. The simulations require an expert for modifications.	The module is useful to evaluate indoor comfort conditions. It can also be used to change input conditions and check the impact on comfort conditions.
Challenger	Renewable Energy Simulator (REnSIM)	The module detects problems in the installation as compared to simulation data. The alerts of the module need to be developed to allow easier use of the module.	The module is mature but some refinements are needed: alerting, ergonomy of the application.	The module is easy to use but several iterations are needed before finding the right derate factor which could be time consuming.	The module is useful to detect problems with the installation of Photovoltaics but does not allow to identify the source of the problems (whether shade or installation problems for example).

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
Challenger	Visualisation Module (FM Visualisation)	The module is useful to identify whether HVAC equipment are functioning in optimal conditions.	Module was not available for testing.	Some of the graphs need to be simplified (heat maps and signature plots are not easily understood).	The module is useful to identify whether HVAC equipment are functioning in optimal conditions.
Challenger	Visualisation Module (Building Occupants Module)	The module is a simple visualization tool for occupants to track energy consumption, energy actions, indoor measurements and outdoor weather conditions.	Mature and ready to be used.	Ergonomic and easy to use.	The module is useful to convey simple information for occupants. The module can be improved by adding dynamic information to occupants regarding energy actions or general communication messages.
Wilanów Town Hall	Load Forecasting	Module tested in the polish pilot site. Module has been successfully connected to the platform. Reference models have been created for specific area of interest (electricity and heating systems). The accuracy of forecasting is good and correspond to the real energy consumption.	Mature and ready to be used.	Clear and intuitive interface. The User Guide available directly from the module interface. The interface in only English language can be a problem for non-English speakers. The module needs some preliminary work in order to create the appropriate (reference) models.	Module can be use in order to detect any deviation in energy uses, for instance overconsumption by comparing the predictions with the real values.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
Wilanów Town Hall	Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD- PCA)	Module tested in the polish pilot site. Module has been successfully connected to the platform. Reference models have been created for specific area of interest (AHU NW1 and the conference rooms served by this AHU). Correct identification of the malfunction of the chiller that serves AHU NW1.	Mature and ready to be used.	Clear and intuitive interface. The User Guide available directly from the module interface. The interface in only English language can be a problem for non-English speakers. The module needs some preliminary work in order to create the appropriate (reference) models.	Module can be use in order to detect any abnormal behaviour in building's installation and sending alerts to the Facility Manager. The alert may lead to quick action and prevent from additional costs caused by failures.
Wilanów Town Hall	Energy Management (EM + EM Visualisation)	Module tested in the polish pilot site. Module has been successfully connected to the platform and populated with data, both from the bills and the sensors. Sankey diagram has been created and the module enables to visualize the performance of the building among the several years on the graphs.	Fully mature and already available in the market.	The interface is highly user-friendly. Data on the Sankey diagram and other graphs are presented in a very clear way. The interface in only English language can be a problem for non-English speakers.	Module can be use in order to visualise the energy performance of the building by presenting the energy consumption data on the graphs and to compare it among several years to investigate any progress or regress in energy performance. Module also enables to investigate the most energy consuming areas (systems) in the building.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
Wilanów Town Hall	Visualisation Module (BIM Visualisation)	Module tested in the polish pilot site. Module enables to visualize historical data from the Wilanów Town Hall in the 3D model of the building.	Fully mature and already available in the market. From the Polish Pilot Site perspective, module should also enable visualization of the real time data in order to be fully functional - testing this functionality at Wilanów Pilot was not possible due to indirect connection with BEMServer (through Plat.One).	Data visualization on the 3D model significantly reduces the time spent on inspecting the installation. The interface is clear, however the only English language can be a problem for non-English speakers.	Module can be use in order to visualize data on the 3D model and enables reviewing historical data (which is very important during negotiating with several tenants).
Nanogune	Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD- PCA)		Currently the module has slight maturity problems, some of the parameters cause some crash in the application.	It is a correct and intuitive interface, easy to use.	It allows to know values in a fast and efficient way
Nanogune	Load Forecasting		Currently the module has slight maturity problems, some of the parameters cause some crash in the application.	It is a correct and intuitive interface, easy to use.	It allows to know values in a fast way and efficient way
Nanogune	Energy Management (EM + EM Visualisation)		You are at the right time of maturity	The interface is not very intuitive, it should be revised to get a more comfortable interface.	The results obtained make it possible to manage energy consumption efficiently.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
Nanogune	Gap Reasoner	We haven't been able to verify it because we haven't had access			
Nanogune	Visualisation Module (FM Visualisation)	We haven't been able to verify it because we haven't had access			
Nanogune	User behaviour module (BM-ML)		You are at the right time of maturity.	Straightforward and easy to use interface, although with a loose design, the colors of some of the graphics are not well distinguished.	Practical and easy, great ease of data sampling.
National University of Galway	Fault detection and diagnosis (FDD- PCA)	Comprehensive tests successfully performed, faults are detected in reliable way, the module performed in a useable manner and results were generated which enabled comparative review.	Ready to be used in professional services.	Clear and useful interface available, comprehensive integration with the BEMServer platform.	Automatic detection of faults, with direct connection with the BMS thanks to the BEMServer.
National University of Galway	Fault detection and diagnosis (FDD-ML)	Tested in progressive stages of development, tested in short periods with good first results.	Comprehensive prototype.	Further developments would lead to an user friendly interface, now not available.	Automatic detection of faults, potentially useful and powerful, it needs some further developments to be ready for a larger use.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
National University of Galway	Load Forecasting	Realiabe results on different kinds of energy carriers and uses, forecasting models have to be based on relevant related variables (e.g. outdoor temperature, occupancy, etc.).	Ready to be used in professional services.	Clear and useful interface available, comprehensive integration with the BEMServe platform.	Automatic forecasting of energy demand with different level of details, with direct connection with the BMS thanks to the BEMServer, useful for energy management, RES management, demand response measures, etc.
National University of Galway	Building Performance Simulation Module (ESP-r)	The integration with BEMServer gives easy access to this powerful tool and the opportunity to use automatic calibration engine, interesting results of the tests.	Mature and fully available on the market.	Clear and useful interface available, easy access from the BEMServer platform.	Easy access to this powerful energy dynamic simulation tool for comfort and energy performance assessment, automatic calibration of the energy models with direct connection to the BMS measured values, the deployment phase allow to find faults in components reducing the gap even in that phase.
National University of Galway	Building Performance Simulation Module (ModSCO)	A comprehensive work flow / process have been deployed and demonstrated.	Reliable calculation engines ready to be used, interface needs	Clear and useful interface available, easy access from the	Easy access to this reliable and fast to use energy dynamic simulation tool.

Pilot site	Module	Summary of feedback	Evaluation of maturity	Evaluation of ergonomomy	Evaluation of usefulness
			to be completed for some actions.	BEMServer platform.	
National University of Galway	Visualisation Module (BIM Visualisation)	Successful and comprehensive application of this tool, allowing to offer functionalities of the BIM environment, effective and useful visualizations, and automatic connection to the BMS measured values and information.	Mature and fully available on the market.	Fully developed, attractive, and effective interface, plenty of functionalities.	Innovative and effective tool to empower the use of BIM models, integrating with BMS, systems controls and monitoring, and facility management.

8 Acronyms and abbreviations

AHU	Air Handling Unit
API	APINTECH
BES	Bouygues Energies et Services
BM	Behaviour Modelling
BME	Behaviour Modelling Event driven
BMS	Building Management System
BPS	Building Performance Simulation
BRE	Building Research Establishment
CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Coordinator
DOA	Description of the action
DRV	Débit Réfrigérant Variable (cooling system)
ECM	Energy Conservation Measure
EM	Energy manager
EMB	Exploitation Management Board
EnMS	Energy Management System
EnPI	Energy Performance Indicator
EU	European Union
EUR	EURECAT
FDD	Fault Detection and Diagnosis
FDD-PCA	Fault Detection and Diagnosis – Principal Component Analysis
FDD-ML	Fault Detection and Diagnosis –Machine learning based
FISE	Fraunhofer ISE
FM	Facility Manager
GA	Grant Agreement
GIR	GIROA
GM	General Meeting
GPL	General Public License
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
IO	Improvement Opportunity
IP	Intellectual Property
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
LIU	LIUPPA Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
ML	Machine Learning
MOS	MOSTOSTAL
NBK	Nobatek
NC	Non-Conformity
NUIG	National University of Ireland Galway
NWD	Non-Working Days
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PDCA	Plan Do Check Act
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QA	Quality Assurance
ROM	Reduced Order Model

SA Sensitivity Analysis
UA Uncertainty Analysis
WD Working Days
WP Work Package

9 Annexes

9.1 Annex 1: Identification of the performance improvement capacity of the tool – Key performance indicators

9.1.1 Energy performance indicators

Electricity consumption per square meter (kWh/m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the electricity consumption per square meter requires to compare historical electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Electricity consumption per occupant/employee (kWh/occupant):

Evaluating the reduction of the electricity consumption per occupant/employee requires to compare historical electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of occupants or employees of the building or the zone are needed. There are two ways to measure the number of occupants: Considering the nominal number of occupants (e.g. number of working stations, number of sits in lecture rooms, etc.) or the actual measured ones (e.g. average in the considered period of the heads counted by occupancy sensors). As there aren't sensors to measure the number of occupants in all of the pilot sites it is important to calculate it with the nominal number of occupants first to be able to compare the results of the demonstration sites. Then the pilots with the right sensors can calculate it with the measured number of occupants.

Costs of electricity consumption per square meter ((kWh * €) / m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the costs of electricity consumption per square meter requires to compare historical electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed. It is also necessary to find the price of a kWh in euros (€) thanks to the utility bills or the energy supplier tariffs.

Costs of electricity consumption per occupant/employee ((kWh * €) / Occupant):

Evaluating the reduction of the costs of electricity consumption per occupant/employee requires to compare historical electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of occupants or employees of the building or the zone are needed. It is also necessary to find the price of a kWh in euros (€) thanks to the utility bills or the energy supplier tariffs.

Electricity production per square meter (kWh/m²):

Evaluating the production of the electricity per square meter requires to compare historical electric production retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the electric production after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Table 29: Electricity performance indicators

Energy Performance Indicators				
Electricity				
Module	Electricity consumption per square meter	Electricity consumption per occupant/employee	Costs of electricity consumption per square meter	Electricity production per square meter
Forecasting				
FDD-PCA	yes		yes	
FDD-ML	yes		yes	
BM-Semantic	yes			
BM-Event	yes	yes		
EnMS	yes		yes	
ModSCO	yes			
ESP-r	yes			
Calibro				
Gap Reasoner	yes			
RENSim				yes
Visualisation				

Lighting electricity consumption per square meter (kWh/m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the lighting electricity consumption per square meter requires to compare historical electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the lighting electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Domestic hot water electricity consumption per square meter (kWh/m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the domestic hot water electricity consumption per square meter requires to compare historical domestic hot water electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the domestic hot water electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Mechanical ventilation electricity consumption per square meter (kWh/m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the mechanical ventilation electricity consumption per square meter requires to compare historical mechanical ventilation electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the mechanical ventilation electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Plug load electricity consumption per square meter (kWh/m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the plug load electricity consumption per square meter requires to compare historical plug load electric consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the plug load electric consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Table 30: Electricity performance indicators per energy use

Module	Energy Performance Indicators			
	Electricity per use			
	Lighting electricity consumption per square meter	Domestic hot water electricity consumption per square meter	Mechanical ventilation electricity consumption per square meter	Plug load electricity consumption per square meter
Forecasting				
FDD-PCA	yes	yes	yes	yes
FDD-ML	yes	yes	yes	yes
BM-Semantic	yes	yes	yes	yes
BM-Event	yes	yes	yes	yes
EnMS				
ModSCO			yes	
ESP-r	yes		yes	
Calibro				
Gap Reasoner				
RENSim				
Visualisation				

9.1.2 Heating and cooling energy performance indicators

Heating energy consumption per square meter (Unit of heating energy source / m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the heating energy consumption per square meter requires to compare historical heating energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the heating energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Heating energy consumption per occupant/employee (Unit of heating energy source / occupant):

Evaluating the reduction of the heating energy consumption per occupant/employee requires to compare historical heating energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the heating energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of occupants or employees of the building or the zone are needed.

Heating energy consumption per degree-day (Unit of heating energy source / HDD):

Evaluating the reduction of heating energy consumption per degree-day requires to compare historical heating energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the heating energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The weather conditions data from the nearest weather station is required.

Calculation of HDD:

$$HDDt_i/t_{HL} = \sum(t_i - t_a) \text{ when } t_a \leq \text{limit temperature } ^\circ\text{C}$$

HDD Heating degree days [(°C·d)/a]

n Number of days in the period under consideration for which applies: $t_a < t_{HL}$

t_i	Base temperature [°C]; the baseline reference temperature changes with respect to the countries.
t_a	Mean ambient temperature [°C]
t_{HL}	Heat limit temperature [°C]

Costs of heating energy consumption per square meter ((Unit of heating energy source * €) / m²):
Evaluating the reduction of the costs of heating energy consumption per square meter requires to compare historical heating energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the heating energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed. It is also necessary to find the price of a kWh in euros (€) thanks to the utility bills or the energy supplier tariffs.

Costs of heating energy consumption per occupant/employee ((Unit of heating energy source * €) / occupant):

Evaluating the reduction of the costs of heating energy consumption per occupant/employee requires to compare historical heating energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the heating energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of occupants or employees of the building or the zone are needed. It is also necessary to find the price of a kWh in euros (€) thanks to the utility bills or the energy supplier tariffs.

Cooling energy consumption per square meter (Unit of cooling energy source / m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the cooling energy consumption per square meter requires to compare historical cooling energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the cooling energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of square meters of the building or the zone are needed.

Cooling energy consumption per occupant/employee (Unit of cooling energy source / occupant):

Evaluating the reduction of the cooling energy consumption per occupant/employee requires to compare historical cooling energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the cooling energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of occupants or employees of the building or the zone are needed.

Cooling energy consumption per degree-day (Unit of cooling energy source / CDD):

Evaluating the reduction of cooling energy consumption per degree-day requires to compare historical cooling energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the cooling energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The weather conditions data from the nearest weather station is required.

Calculation of CDD

$$CDD_{t_i/t_{CL}} = \sum (t_a - t_i) \text{ when } t_a \geq \text{limit temperature } ^\circ\text{C}$$

CDD Cooling degree days [(°C·d)/a]

n Number of days in the period under consideration for which applies: $t_a > t_{CL}$

t_i Base temperature [°C]; the baseline reference temperature changes with respect to the countries

t_a Mean ambient temperature [°C]

t_{CL} Cool limit temperature [°C]

Costs of cooling energy consumption per square meter ((Unit of cooling energy source * €) / m²):

Evaluating the reduction of the costs of cooling energy consumption per square meter requires to compare historical cooling energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the cooling energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of

square meters of the building or the zone are needed. It is also necessary to find the price of a kWh in euros (€) thanks to the utility bills or the energy supplier tariffs.

Costs of cooling energy consumption per occupant/employee ((Unit of cooling energy source * €) / occupant):

Evaluating the reduction of the costs of cooling energy consumption per occupant/employee requires to compare historical cooling energy consumption retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the cooling energy consumption after HIT2GAP implementation. The number of occupants or employees of the building or the zone are needed. It is also necessary to find the price of a kWh in euros (€) thanks to the utility bills or the energy supplier tariffs.

Table 31: Heating and cooling performance indicators

Module	Energy Performance Indicators					
	Heating			Cooling		
	Heating energy consumption per square meter	Heating energy consumption per occupant/employee	Costs of heating energy consumption per square meter	Cooling energy consumption per square meter	Cooling energy consumption per occupant/employee	Costs of cooling energy consumption per square meter
Forecasting						
FDD-PCA	yes			yes		
FDD-ML	yes			yes		
BM-Semantic						
BM-Event						
EnMS						
ModSCO	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
ESP-r						
Calibro						
Gap Reasoner						
RENSim						
Visualisation						

9.1.3 Indoor quality indicators

Improvements in indoor quality:

Evaluating the improvements of the indoor quality requires to compare historical concentration of CO₂ in the air of the zone or building retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the concentration of CO₂ after HIT2GAP implementation. The analysis also considers the percentage of occupied hours above the comfort limit value fixed at 1000 ppm.

Improvements in thermal comfort conditions:

Evaluating the improvements of the thermal comfort conditions requires to compare historical indoor temperature (°C), the relative humidity (%) and the air velocity (m/s) of the indoor air of the zone or building retrieved from the BMS before the platform integration and the same measures after the HIT2GAP implementation. The analysis also considers the percentage of occupied hours above the comfort limit value fixed below:

Recommended / Reference values according to ISO 7730:

Indoor air temperature (°C): 22-24

Relative humidity (%): 30-70

Air velocity (m/s): 0.16

Number of complaints per week:

Evaluating the decrease of complaints of the occupants per week requires to compare historical number of complaints retrieved from the tool tracking complaints of the zone or building before the platform integration and the number of complaints after HIT2GAP implementation.

Table 32: Environment and indoor quality indicators

Environmental and Indoor Quality Indicators			
Indoor quality			
Module	Improvements in indoor quality	Improvements in thermal comfort conditions	Number of complaints per week
Forecasting			
FDD-PCA		yes	yes
FDD-ML		yes	yes
BM-Semantic	yes	yes	yes
BM-Event			
EnMS			
ModSCO		yes	
ESP-r	yes	yes	yes
Calibro			
Gap Reasoner			
RENSim			
Visualisation			

9.1.4 Organization and management indicators

Man-months of the staff EM – FM:

Evaluating the decrease of time the Energy Manager or Facility Manager spends on a task requires to know how much time the staff took to do the task before the HIT2GAP tool and compare it to the time they take with the tool.

Salary cost per month:

Evaluating the decrease of the salary cost per month of the staff requires to know the % of time reduction or the number of hours saved per month. The approximate or average salary per month in euros is also required.

Table 33: Organizational and management indicators

Organization and Management Indicators		
Module	Man-months of the staff (EM - FM)	Salary cost per month
Forecasting	yes	yes
FDD-PCA	yes	yes
FDD-ML	yes	yes
BM-Semantic	yes	yes
BM-Event	yes	yes
EnMS	yes	yes
ModSCO	yes	yes
ESP-r	yes	yes
Calibro		
Gap Reasoner		
RENSim	yes	yes
Visualisation		

9.1.5 Application performance indicators

Relevance of alerts / notifications:

- Should the alert / notification exist?
- Is the alert / notification relevant?
- Does the alert / notification give all the necessary information?
- Is the information given by the alert / notification correct?

Ergonomics / User-friendly:

Method of operating:

A usability test is an essential part of the quality assurance of the software, website or application. This is a test where a series of individuals use a software or website under supervision to know if visitors can use it successfully. It must be conducted in a context as close as possible to the actual use. Users perform the main tasks for which the software was designed.

The observer gives the user instructions that will lead him to perform typical tasks of the software or the website. It is essential not to help him except, of course, in case of deadlock. In order to clearly identify problems, it is best to leave the user "fend for themselves" as he would do alone with the software. The observer notes mistakes made, misunderstandings, dead ends, any event that shows a difficulty in using the software. These different observations are subject, once the test is finished, to a "hot analysis" with the user, in order to understand the causes of the problems.

Measure usability:

To determine usability objectively, we calculate the user's performance, ie the accuracy of the task compared to the resources consumed. In other words: was the user able to complete the task correctly and in the required time? Measuring usability consists in doing 3 types of measurements:

Effectiveness: Verify that the objectives targeted by the user are achieved.

Efficiency: Measure the resources needed to achieve these goals, such as the time taken by the user to complete the task.

Satisfaction: Determine if the system is comfortable to use, for example by counting down the number of negative comments made by users during the test.

Investment return (years):

Evaluating the investment return requires to know the cost of the implementation of the module in euros and the savings achieved per year thanks to the module in euros (€ / year)

User satisfaction:

Choose the relevant criteria to measure:

Easy to use, information easy to find, visual, logical, managed to do what he wanted to do etc.

A descriptive scale that measures a customer's response from unsatisfied to satisfied. The customer is given a short list of responses to choose from that range from "very unsatisfied" to "very satisfied."

Precision of the module:

Some modules such as load forecasting directly indicate the accuracy of the module.

Table 34: Application performance indicators

Application performance indicators					
Module	Relevance of alerts / notifications	Ergonomy / User-friendly	Investment return	Users satisfaction	Precision of the module
Forecasting			yes	yes	yes
FDD-PCA	yes		yes	yes	
FDD-ML	yes		yes	yes	
BM-Semantic	yes		yes	yes	
BM-Event	yes	yes	yes	yes	
EnMS			yes	yes	
ModSCO			yes	yes	
ESP-r	yes		yes	yes	
Calibro					
Gap Reasoner	yes		yes	yes	yes
RENSim		yes	yes	yes	yes
Visualisation	yes	yes	yes	yes	